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List of Abbreviations

EoI	Expression of Interest
ERA	European Research Area
FAIR	Findable-Accessible-Interoperable-Reusable
FRIS	Flanders Research Information Space
IT	Information Technology
MOOC	Massive-Open-Online Course
PPTSC	Public-, private-, and 3 rd sector collaboration cluster
RCC	Research Coordination Cluster
REA	Research Executive Agency
RI	Research Infrastructure
R&I	Research & Innovation
RIR	Research Infrastructure and Resources
RTD	Directorate-General for Research and Innovation
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics
WP	Work Package

List of Una.Resin Beneficiaries

Number	Name	Short Name
1	THE UNIVERSITY OF EDINBURGH	UEDIN
2	HELSINGIN YLIOPISTO	UH
3	ALMA MATER STUDIORUM – UNIVERSITA DI BOLOGNA	UNIBO
4	UNIVERSIDAD COMPLUTENSE DE MADRID	UCM
5	FREIE UNIVERSITAET BERLIN	FUB
6	KATHOLIEKE UNIVERSITEIT LEUVEN	KU Leuven
7	UNIwersytet Jagiellonski	UJ
8	UNIVERSITE PARIS I PANTHEON-SORBONNE	UP1

List of Una.Resin Work Packages (WPs)

WP Number	WP Title
WP1	Una Europa Research & Innovation
WP2	Una Europa Infrastructure & Resources
WP3	Una Europa Strengthening Human Capital
WP4	Management, coordination, and dissemination, including cooperation with other Alliances
WP5	Ethics requirements

Introduction

Una Europa brings together leading European research-intensive universities that have global reputation and reach to create a truly inter-university environment, where outstanding research is continuously linked to transnational learning and innovative critical thinking. The Alliance aims to drive forward both the European Research Area and the European Higher Education Area by pushing the boundaries of what is feasible in transnational collaboration today. Una.Resin is Una Europa's flagship Horizon 2020 project.

The Una *Research and Innovation* (Una.Resin) project was set up with an objective to develop common strategies and action plans on joint research cooperation, research infrastructure and resources, and human resources, and test these through the implementation of pilot projects. In successfully meeting this objective, the Una.Resin project has taken the first steps towards creating a common, seamless research and innovation (R&I) ecosystem for researchers and partners. In developing an initial shape to this common ecosystem, the project has advanced institutional transformation both in R&I and towards a university of the future where students, researchers, and staff work together to address global challenges in collaboration with our shared partners and communities. This University of the Future will be an international, value-driven, innovative, and democratic community of researchers, students, and professional services that is truly open and inclusive, allowing everyone to thrive.

Una.Resin's main achievement has been the development of preliminary shared strategies on R&I and Sharing Research Infrastructure and Resources (RIRs), and recommendations towards the development of a future Una.Europa strategy on Strengthening Human Capital. For each of these strategies, the project developed accompanying action plans and roadmaps through a series of pilot projects. More precisely, Una.Resin tested innovative models for barrier-free, interdisciplinary cross-border collaboration and team science to address societal challenges. The project team also tested new ways of sharing our existing research infrastructures (RIs) with a wider group of academic, non-academic, and citizen stakeholders. Throughout our pilot projects, Una.Resin incorporated specific elements to ensure the mainstreaming of Open Science, and to fully embed both citizens and other non-academic actors in all stages of the R&I lifecycle.

The present deliverable consists of three sections: a brief on project outcomes, evaluation of the Una.Resin pilot projects, and reflections and recommendations from across the breadth of the project. It is also followed by an Annex with a summary of the pilot evaluations, as well a supporting document which includes documents that fed into this deliverable: i.e., the full text of the pilot valuations, the blueprint for a common catalogue of RIs developed within the third Una.Resin pilot project, and the European Research Area (ERA) Progress and Policy Report produced within the Una.Resin project using the template provided by the Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (RTD) and the European Research Executive Agency (REA).

The first section provides the reader with an overview of the project's most important outcomes. It briefly explains how Una.Resin has been instrumental in supporting development towards a seamless Una Europa R&I ecosystem. The Una.Resin outcomes that have contributed to this development are the aforementioned preliminary joint strategies and pilot projects, with outcomes also relating to the strengthening of the Alliance's governance. The

strategies and pilots provide direction for future Alliance activities and frameworks, with the project directly contributing to integral prioritisation exercises.

The second section presents key reflections and recommendations emerging from the eight different pilot projects implemented during the Una.Resin lifecycle. Drawing from the detailed evaluations of the pilots¹, this section summarises how the projects have made integral first steps towards collaboration, openness, interconnection, and sharing and, ultimately, lay the foundation for establishing a common R&I ecosystem that reaches beyond the academic community to the wider society and industry. The Una.Resin pilots have started to address barriers to collaboration and openness, and the initial concepts and designs advanced via the pilots now need to be scaled up. A further three institutions – University College Dublin, Universität Zürich and Universiteit Leiden – joined the Alliance in 2022. This expansion not only illustrates the success of Una Europa and the Una.Resin project but, as active members of Una Europa governing bodies, these new institutions have offered vital insights regarding the potential of, and wider desire for, scaling up the pilot activities. Scaling up of the pilots will not only support continued progress against the Alliance ambition of creating a common R&I ecosystem, but will also further contribute to the European Union’s objectives of empowering the university sector in its own transformation efforts towards a future 2030 vision in the field of R&I.

Finally, the third section provides reflections and recommendations for further policy development. This section details the challenges our Alliance encountered in the present reporting period regarding cooperation between universities in the field of R&I in relation to the institutional change areas (transformation modules), as well as how these challenges were tackled. In overcoming challenges and through shaping Una Europa’s ambitions in R&I, the Una.Resin project offers many valuable learnings. This final section presents the key learnings and the associated recommendations, whilst highlighting the importance of developing a dedicated funding instrument for strategic collaborations across universities, and providing a long-term funding perspective across education and R&I. With the provision of long-term sustainability, these recommendations will undoubtedly prove fundamental as Una Europa continues in its ambition of creating a common R&I ecosystem.

Project Outcomes

Una Europa’s flagship Horizon 2020 project, Una.Resin, has been a key vehicle to driving the Alliance’s R&I dimension, and is central to our ambition of creating a **seamless Una Europa ecosystem for R&I**. The Una.Resin project has generated a number of outcomes that have advanced progress and produced vital insights as Una Europa continues to make advances against this ambition. Ultimately the project has provided an initial foundation from which Una Europa institutions can build from to strengthen multi-, inter-, and transdisciplinary R&I activities to address global challenges, whilst also advancing key understandings of how to further increase the internationalisation and collaboration of research activities across the Alliance. These developments have supported progress towards institutional change in areas of transformation both within the Alliance and the wider European University Initiative.

¹ The detailed pilot evaluations have been submitted as supporting document to the present deliverable, and the executive summaries of each pilot evaluation have been provided in Annex 1.

The Una.Resin project has been instrumental in further developing the governance of the Alliance. The Una Europa Research Strategy Group was established as part of the Una.Resin project, bringing together Vice Rectors for Research Policy (or equivalent) as part of the Alliance's formal governance structure. Likewise, the Una.Resin project established different **clusters of professional staff** working on R&I, providing a space for exchange and mutual learning, and for developing flexible and creative solutions for inter-institutional collaboration. These clusters focus on research coordination, RIs, research careers and culture, third sector cooperation, open research, and citizen engagement. Together, they provide the backbone of Una Europa expertise and act as ad-hoc advisory bodies for new initiatives, including the Una.Resin pilot projects, whilst also supporting their implementation. The continuous engagement of cluster members is contributing to the development of each partner university and the career development of our staff as we share ideas and embrace change. The cluster have, thus, supported institutional transformation by breaking down barriers and encouraging collaboration and cooperation.

The Una.Resin project has provided space for the **development of preliminary joint strategies and growing pilot initiatives** across three key inter-connected transformation modules: building a common R&I agenda, sharing infrastructure and resources, and strengthening human capital. In addition, three further areas – cooperation with non-academic actors, Open Science, and embedding citizens and society – were dealt with transversally in the project. Una.Resin had made progress against three joint strategies. The Una Europa Research and Innovation Strategy² sets forth three strategic areas of action: strengthening the Una Europa Focus Areas, engaging researcher broadly, and opening up research and data infrastructures. The strategy, and core objectives that are at its heart, have provided the Alliance with the strategic direction and prioritisation guidance required to cultivate an R&I ecosystem that promotes value-driven, impactful collaborations, whilst ensuring a sustained and common effort towards this goal.

The R&I Strategy developed under Una.Resin will be taken forward into the Una.Futura project, which is the second phase of funding for Una Europa under the umbrella of Erasmus+. Una.Futura will build on the achievements of Una.Resin to ensure the true integration of the Alliance's education, and R&I visions. This R&I vision is anchored in three strategic overarching objectives: supporting the development of Una Europa's interdisciplinary hubs, providing a transnational framework for training early-career researchers, and opening up research and data infrastructures and resources. Una Europa's R&I vision is strongly linked to the Una.Resin project and to the developed R&I Strategy, which identified the establishment of interdisciplinary hubs, the training of researchers for the future, and opening up research and data infrastructure as key strategic activities in developing a common R&I ecosystem. The R&I vision continues the work of the Una.Resin project and sets forth the broad strategic R&I ambitions for the Alliance that will, in turn, drive the Alliance's work through the development and implementation of a range projects, both current and prospective.

The second joint strategy preliminary developed under Una.Resin is the Una Europa Strategy

² The Una Europa Research & Innovation Strategy was presented in the Una.Resin Project Deliverable D1.2.

and Action plan for sharing and opening up Research and Data Infrastructures³, which forms part of the overall R&I strategy. A seamless R&I ecosystem necessitate openness, and this preliminary strategy offers an initial framework for advancing connections between, and the openness of, research and data infrastructures. The final primary strategy makes advance towards an Una Europa Human Capital Development Strategy⁴. Una.Resin recommended this strategy centre around five goals – career path development, performance assessment, well-being, societal engagement, and support for early-career researchers – that together offer an important point of reference for guiding the Alliance in future policy decisions in the area of human capital development. In addition, the strategy identified tools and methods to foster inter-university cooperation and joint action in the achievement of these human capital focused goals.

The Una.Resin project, via the initial developments towards these three strategies, has supported the advancement of the overall R&I direction of the Alliance. The project has been key to identifying strategic priorities and actions that, in their development, will support the implementation of an R&I vision that can yield the greatest impact for the Alliance and, ultimately, empower the university sector in its own transformation efforts towards a future 2030 vision in the field of R&I. The strategies have animated key outcomes that have laid the foundations for high-impact collaborations both within and beyond academia, enabled new avenues to exploit RIs of Una Europa partners, and promoted a framework of excellence, well-being, equality, diversity and inclusion, Open Science, and citizen science across Alliance activities and collaborations.

The Una.Resin pilot initiatives address the same transformation module as the joint strategies. They sought to build upon these preliminary strategies and the associated action plans by identifying and testing solutions that align to the strategies and action plans. For example, one of the pilot initiatives designed and implemented Horizon Europe matchmaking workshops for researchers in all Una Europa Focus Areas, as well as match-making opportunities among RIs in the field of Cultural Heritage (Museums and Digital Collections) and One Health (Genomics). Such initiatives have been instrumental in developing spaces for collaboration and connection across various communities of the partner universities.

The Una.Resin joint strategies and pilot projects have played a crucial role in shaping Una Europa's ambitions in the field of R&I and the drivers to many great successes for the Alliance. Notably, they have directly contributed to the development of the Una Europa R&I matrix exercise. The matrix presents potential future activities in R&I across the three strategic overarching objectives and encourages prioritisation at the highest decision-making levels. A dedicated online survey was designed to allow Una Europa partner universities to make strategic choices in a transparent manner. Based on the survey results, iterations of a joint R&I Action Plan are currently under discussion, with the final Action Plan due to be adopted in June 2024. In addition to activities under each of the three strategic overarching objectives, the Action Plan will include the roll-out of Una Europa's professional service clusters.

In the context of a lack of Horizon Europe funding available to secure the follow-up of the

³ This strategy and action plan is presented in 'A Shared Una Europa Strategy for Sharing Research Infrastructures and Resources', Una.Resin Project Deliverable D2.2.

⁴ Presented in the Una.Resin Project Deliverable 3.2: 'Recommendations for the future Una Europa Human Capital Development Strategy'.

Una.Resin project, the Una Europa Board of Directors agreed that the Alliance's roll-out project funded under the Erasmus+ programme, Una.Futura, should be holistic in nature covering education and R&I initiatives. As such, the Una.Futura project builds upon the results of the Una.Resin project. For instance, a specific WP is dedicated to researchers, under which there is a specific deliverable entitled "Una.Resin benchmarking". The deliverable will ensure, as far as is feasible, that the outcomes of the Una.Resin project are taken up to the benefit of the Alliance's research community.

In conclusion, the Una.Resin project has been vital in developing preliminary steps towards establishing joint strategies and in testing different pilots in the field of R&I at the level of Una Europa. The Una.Resin project was instrumental in establishing adequate joint governance and operational structures to oversee the development of the R&I strategy and activities in this field beyond the timescale of the project. The next phase of consolidation will shift focus to the implementation and scaling of initiatives under the framework of the joint strategy. Both internal and external funding will be critical to the successful implementation and scaling of these initiatives.

Evaluation of Pilots

The Una.Resin pilots aimed to collectively identify and test solutions to overcome barriers that may hinder the establishment of a **seamless, common R&I ecosystem**. Furthermore, they sought to contribute to the European Union's goals of **empowering the university sector in its own transformation** efforts towards a future 2030 vision in the field of R&I. The findings of the initial Una.Resin benchmarking exercise⁵ informed the development of a series of co-creation workshops that, in turn, provided the foundation for the advancement and implementation of eight pilot actions:

1. Developing a format for supporting the systematic collaboration on the Una Europa priority global challenges;
2. Developing a concept for a Una Europa collaboration platform;
3. Blueprint for a common catalogue of RIs;
4. Matchmaking formats to improve the Una Europa RI sharing;
5. Una Europa Citizen Science toolkit;
6. The Open Science pilot;
7. The Team Science pilot; and
8. Fostering business-academia cooperation ([UNA Transfer :: Pilot 2023 \(una-transfer.eu\)](https://una-transfer.eu)).

The outcomes and impacts of each pilot have been evaluated in detail, with a view to disseminating lessons learnt, best practices, and recommendations.⁶

The pilot projects produced a number of **tangible outputs that together address all seven transformation modules**. Collaboration has been at the heart of all the pilots. For example, one of the pilots created and tested an interdisciplinary matchmaking process to establish an

⁵ The benchmarking exercises are directly linked to the preliminary joint strategies developed as part of the Una.Resin project: D1.1 Benchmarking R&I Strategies and Priorities for a Joint Una Europa Strategy; D2.1 Mapping RIRs and priorities for joint strategy; and D3.1 Mapping HR Strategies and priorities for joint strategy.

⁶ The full pilot evaluations are provided in the supporting document submitted alongside this deliverable. Annex A to this deliverable provides a summary of each pilot evaluation.

effective approach for responding to interdisciplinary funding Horizon Europe Pillar II calls across the Alliance. This matchmaking process not only resulted in the submission of two consortium proposals, but the findings from the pilot have been instrumental for the Research Coordination Cluster (RCC), an expert group of research funding advisors, being appointed as a permanent Una Europa body. Matchmaking workshops have also been designed and implemented to support the development of a collaboration platform across RIs, and to connect participating RIs with the Una Europa Cultural Heritage and One Health self-steering committees. Establishing these connections ensures RIs will support activities that have been endorsed in the self-steering committees' action plans. Furthermore, the workshops are designed and repeated so that they empower RIs to set forth their own vision and suggest their own collaboration activities for research enhancement which, in turn, increases the number of actors driving collaboration.

The Una.Resin pilots have further **fostered collaboration and networking** across the Una Europa R&I system by, for example, advancing a pilot activity that developed an initial collaboration platform concept and another pilot that conceived of a blueprint for a common digital catalogue of RIs. Several of the pilots have sought to develop initial concepts and advance recommendations to promote collaboration beyond the sphere of academia by identifying pathways to engage industry and wider society and address barriers around visibility and accessibility (e.g., via designed tools to access information on research group activities that are potentially transferable to industry). The Una.Resin pilots have made advancement towards developing spaces, tools, and platforms for connection and networking both within, but crucially beyond Una Europa, and these are essential first steps in fostering impactful collaboration and creating a common ecosystem.

A common ecosystem, built on a foundation of collaboration and connection, will be inherently hindered by a lack of **sharing and openness**. The Una.Resin project pilots are united in addressing the barriers impacting the capacity for openness and testing solutions that seek to open, expand, and diversify spaces of sharing. The pilot projects have raised awareness among RIs of the importance of open infrastructures, alongside the need to adopt Open Science principles in their operations and activities and promote openness and shareability of their data and services. What is more, the pilots have experimented with novel methodologies and designed possible common tools for empowering RIs as a driving force of international collaboration and prompted a shift in institutional vision, with the RI no longer being solely viewed as a support system but as a key player in the development of global solutions on openness and shareability.

Three further Una.Resin pilots address openness: the creation of an open Citizen Science Toolkit, the Open Science pilot, and the creation of a massive-online-open course (MOOC) and practically-oriented workshop on Team Science. The developed toolkit provides a mechanism to increase the number of citizen science projects and stimulate collaborative, interdisciplinary projects that address global issues. The toolkit itself represents an innovative and open approach to jointly constructing knowledge, exemplifying how collective expertise can yield innovation and novel understandings. Via the Open Science pilot, Una.Resin has made a significant contribution to the increased understanding of the nature of Open Science practices. The Team Science pilot has initiated an integral step in spotlighting good practices in interdisciplinary team sciences across the partner universities, and has been pivotal in

translating and synthesising Una.Resin's knowledge and innovations into an accessible, open format. The Una.Resin pilots have taken the first steps in identifying and addressing the barriers that prevent openness and sharing and Una Europa will need to continue to address these barriers in its ambition to create a seamless, common ecosystem. Yet, the Una.Resin pilots acutely illustrate how European Universities require support, at both a national and European level, if they are to have capacity and ability to tackle these persistent barriers in a meaningful and sustainable way.

The Una.Resin pilot evaluations illustrate the importance of collaboration, openness, interconnection, and sharing for establishing a common R&I ecosystem. They have developed, advanced and tested processes, events, tools, concepts, and platforms that can support the creation of this ecosystem and have highlighted the requirement to put academic and professional staff's needs – and the skills and expertise they need to drive this ecosystem – at the forefront of such developments. The pilot evaluations, and the recommendations and lessons learnt through their implementation, are vital for creating the University of the Future. However, they are just the first step. The insights and outputs that have been advanced offer direction for Una Europa as it continues in its ambition to create a seamless R&I ecosystem; the outputs now need to be scaled up and the pilot evaluations offer lessons learnt and recommendations of how to implement the next stage of activity.

Scaling up activities initially advanced in the Una.Resin pilot project needs to be an ongoing focus of the Alliance. The three institutions – University College Dublin, Universität Zürich and Universiteit Leiden – that joined the Alliance in 2022 provide a perfect space for understanding the desire for scaling up each pilot initiative and a testbed for trialling methods of scaling up. Scaling up the Una.Resin pilots, whether to new partners, new focus areas or new disciplines, requires direction and commitment at an Alliance level but, crucially, necessitates continued support – both in terms of **funding and policy development** – at the European level. The pilot evaluations have illustrated how this direction needs a commonality that extends across alliances, as currently many alliances are proceeding separately with varying approaches. Creating opportunities for exchanging information and good practices among the alliances should be encouraged as a priority.

Developing, organising, and facilitating collaboration initiatives is time-intensive, costly, and requires an understanding of local contexts and networks. Following the completion of the pilots, it was immediately clear that a prioritisation exercise, which included an assessment of added value and a cost-benefit analysis, was required. Una Europa have started to carry out this prioritisation work as part of their matrix exercise. Where such assessment/analysis indicates a high return, dedicated funding and resources are imperative for the benefits to be realised and sustained. In addition to the importance of **dedicated resources**, the Una.Resin pilots highlight the need for decisions that allow for, and advance the development of, specific funding calls committed to supporting bottom-up networking and community building as a prerequisite for collaboration, sharing, and openness. The findings, results, and impacts of the Una.Resin pilots must be mobilised to **influence decision-makers** to take such decisions and, ultimately, promote connection and integration. The pilot evaluations exemplify the need for connection and integration to extend beyond academia and for both Una Europa and policy makers to put special emphasis on developing ways to explore ways of **deeper collaboration with non-academic actors** in the partner universities' ecosystems. This will be supported by

adopting broader definitions, for example of citizen science and Open Science, that encompass understandings and knowledge that extend beyond the academic community.

The Una.Resin pilot evaluations contribute to the European Union's objectives of empowering the university sector in its own transformation efforts towards a future 2030 vision in the field of R&I. The pilot evaluations indicated the importance of securing funding at the Alliance (i.e., multi-institutional) level to ensure connection, collaboration, and openness across the RIs, as well as establishing a continuous discussion with citizens and the industrial sector. Hence, they offer valuable insights on how the European universities can be better equipped and supported to show resilience, and ultimately increase the European presence in the higher education and R&I domains.

The initial steps that the pilots advance towards a seamless R&I ecosystem put the **professional development** of the researchers and professional staff at the forefront, and thus, contribute to making the University of the Future a truly inclusive, democratic, and flexible environment where everyone can thrive. Furthermore, the envisioned common R&I ecosystem is expected to act as an actor of change in the digital transition – this is heavily supported by the various tools suggested via the pilot evaluations (e.g., the blueprint for a common catalogue, the Citizen Science Toolkit, the MOOC, etc.). The Una.Resin pilots underline the importance of having an **open, outward look and approach** central to this European way of life, alongside a willingness to share data and services beyond academia with society and industry.

The Una.Resin pilots have proven instrumental in advancing the first steps in conceiving of how to practically promote and materialise collaboration and openness and, ultimately, have offered an invaluable contribution as the Alliance continues to progress in its ambition of creating a seamless Una Europa ecosystem for R&I.

Reflections and Recommendations

The Una.Resin project has played a crucial role in shaping Una Europa's ambitions in the area of R&I. The project was the **driver of many great successes** for the Alliance, such as the launch of Una Europa's first joint R&I Strategy, and an important testing ground for pilot initiatives. Based on the pilot phase and experiences in this incubator period, the Alliance has drawn many valuable learnings that have informed a number of recommendations, which will undoubtedly prove key as Una Europa continues in its ambition of creating a common R&I ecosystem.

The outcomes and learnings from the Una.Resin project illustrate the importance of **supporting and connecting the whole university community**, and our recommendation is for this to be the central focus of the Alliance – and potentially also the European University Initiative – going forward. The project provided an important space for connecting different communities across the Una Europa partner universities, and the pilot initiatives have shown great promise that have already piqued the interest of the Una Europa community in this initial incubator period. Further investment will be key to both ensure bottom-up engagement and put the whole university communities of academics, professional staff, and students in the

driving seat.

The second recommendation focuses upon **academic collaboration in the Focus Areas**. The six Una Europa Focus Areas are at the core of the Alliance's transnational research ecosystem, and serve as unique fora for the creation of inter-, trans- and multi-disciplinary collaboration and understanding among partner universities. Going forward, Una Europa will promote the evolution of the Focus Areas into international hubs for education, R&I, and societal outreach. The Una.Resin pilot projects, with their focus on collaboration and openness, have underlined the importance of creating interdisciplinary hubs where academics can find a space to discuss topics beyond their field of expertise and establish new collaborations. Continued investment is needed to create strong long-term partnerships and joint R&I agendas between the best researchers across Europe and support the development of more interconnected, meaningful, and impactful R&I that can benefit society as a whole – both in Europe and across the globe. This concerns, for example, support for attracting external funding for research partnerships, designing matchmaking opportunities, and developing seed funding initiatives.

Creating a common ecosystem cannot be separated from **developing an ecosystem for early-career researchers**. Una.Resin has illustrated how early-career researchers will play a pivotal role in shaping the R&I landscape of tomorrow, whilst also advancing events, tools, and platforms that can be utilised to support networking and connection among this vital demographic. European Universities are uniquely positioned to empower early-career researchers to thrive, fostering mobility and exchange of young talents across the partner universities. Based on first experiences, Una Europa believes in the importance of continued investment in joint curriculum development in doctoral programmes, alongside the establishment of a transnational framework for training. Such a framework would provide European Research Councils with the opportunities needed to develop attractive and sustainable R&I careers – the development of this training would benefit from drawing on the lessons learnt from the Una.Resin pilots. In this regard, additional support for transversal skills development around leadership, interdisciplinarity, and international collaboration, as well as further funding for **international short-term mobilities** of early-career researchers, such as the vital need for interdisciplinary summer/winter schools that are flexible in nature.

The Una Europa clusters bring together dedicated professional services colleagues in a wide variety of domains – including citizen science, human capital, RIs, industry-academia collaboration, and doctoral studies. These clusters have been key to the success of the Una.Resin project, i.e., in the areas of Open Science and RIs, and to support both professional and institutional development. **Professional clusters** will continue to be pivotal to strengthening collaboration, providing support for the Una Europa academic community, and shaping the practices and values that define European higher education. Therefore, a strategic decision has been made to continue to select clusters, such as the Research Coordination cluster, beyond the life-time of the Una.Resin project.

Based on the success in the Una.Resin project and the response of the Una Europa community, it is clear that **continued funding for capacity building** is vital in the mission to create future-looking models for both higher education and research. This continued funding is not just crucial for European universities themselves, but to ensure that alliances are in a

position to continue to stimulate transformation and share good practices with other stakeholders across the ERA. At the same time, recent enlargements of alliances, which were incentivised as part of the European Universities Initiative roll-out phase, underline the need for further funding in the area of R&I capacity-building that reaches new partners and puts all partners in an alliance on equal footing. Continued funding for capacity building can support the achievement of equality within and among the Alliance and, in doing so, address barriers to excellence.

Moving forward, we additionally recommend a stronger focus on **driving the dimension of excellence and global competitiveness** of Europe's strongest higher education institutions on the world stage. This focus acutely aligns to the initial concept behind the European Universities Initiative. Excellence is not a quick win but requires time, dedication, and appropriate human and financial resources beyond what has been provided in the framework of the H2020 programme. At the same time, Una.Resin exemplified the challenge of working across numerous ERA policy priorities simultaneously without sufficient funding. This preliminary experience has shown that, in the future, it is crucial for Una Europa to be able to focus on a smaller number of policy priorities that align with our overall strategy and where clear added value can be created for the partnership.

The outward looking dimension of European Universities remains insufficiently supported. The Una Europa partner universities are global actors each with a long history of international collaboration, and as an Alliance, there is the potential to have ever more reach and impact and a greater **global dimension**. The Una.Resin project has illustrated the need to understanding this reach as a responsibility and opportunity to address global challenges, whilst providing tangible evidence in support of the Una Europa belief in the need to address global challenges from diverse perspectives. Una Europa has made great progress in this regard in relation to collaboration with Africa: for instance, with the launch of a first strategic project focusing on virtual mobility, UnaVEx, and a dedicated Seed Funding Initiative to initiate first collaborations across the Una Europa-Africa Partnership. Going forward, the European Commission must focus more on supporting the global dimension of alliances to ensure that they are not inward-looking but develop into open global flagships for Europe.

The project-based funding approach has led to difficulties in internal resourcing, as well as uncertainty in terms of staff retention and staff turnover at the participating universities. These difficulties have been increasingly apparent in the second half of the Una.Resin reporting period. Una. Resin has exemplified the need for a **sustainable, holistic funding framework** and, thus, Una Europa reiterates the call for the development of a dedicated funding instrument for strategic collaborations of universities that allows for co-investment of regional, national, and European sources and for the provision of a long-term funding vision across education, and R&I. Such a funding instrument should:

- Be competitive in nature and always geared towards the principles of quality, excellence, and impact, in line with the core principles of the European R&I programmes;
- Represent an additional investment and not take away from existing R&I priorities and their associated funding;
- Recognise and support the diversity of higher education collaboration in Europe to preserve individual research strengths, maintain and boost excellence, and deliver unique and innovative concepts for the continent and the world;

- Pay increased attention to driving the visibility and global competitiveness of Europe's strongest higher education institutions on the world stage; and
- Be open to the world, encouraging participation and co-investment from like-minded institutions in different parts of the globe.

Investment in the long-term sustainability of actions is key, as this will ultimately determine the long-term sustainability of the alliances themselves. In the ever-continuing quest for new and innovative actions, the Una.Resin pilot projects illustrate the need for sufficient consideration for the long-term sustainability of existing actions. Alliances need to be afforded the appropriate time and funding to focus on deepening their processes and practices and scaling their initial concepts, blueprints, and designs, in order to strengthen the European R&I landscape in a bottom-up manner.

Currently, there is no other cross-border initiative that garners as much enthusiasm and political support at regional and national levels as the European Universities Initiative. This must be leveraged in the future, in order to ensure true **co-ownership of the initiative at regional, national, and European levels both in terms of policy and funding**. In this respect, the European Commission must play a coordinating role in encouraging increased alignment of both policies and funding streams, not just across EU Member States but with the involvement of important neighbouring countries, such as Switzerland and the United Kingdom, to create a genuine lever for collaboration.

The recommendations arising from the Una.Resin project will, with the provision on long-term sustainability via dedicated funding and supportive decision-making, undoubtedly prove fundamental as Una Europa continues in its ambition of creating a common R&I ecosystem.

Annex 1: Summary of Pilot Evaluations

The Una.Resin pilots have been evaluated with a view to disseminate lessons learnt, best practices, and recommendations and, ultimately, to provide direction and insight into future activities to support Una Europa in achieving its aim of establishing a common R&I ecosystem. The aim of the evaluations is to assess the impact and outcome of each pilot in relation to its objectives and offer recommendations. Each evaluation presents a narrative detailing the insights and considerations of both the design and implementation phase. They also draw out learnings and explain what worked well and why, describe the challenges that were faced and how these were overcome, and provide an understanding of the sustainability of the pilot, giving particular attention to opportunities for improvements in future implementations.

Here, we offer a summary of each pilot evaluation with the full evaluations presented in the 'Evaluation of Pilots' that has been submitted as a supporting document to this deliverable.

Pilot Evaluation 1: Developing a format for supporting systematic collaboration on the Una Europa priority global challenges

The aim of this pilot project was to develop a format for supporting systematic collaboration on the Una Europa priority global challenges. Under this pilot were two distinct actions: 1) a Una Europa R&I strategy workshop, and 2) piloting a Horizon Europe Pillar II Call process called matchmaking.

The pilot aligned broadly with the Una.Resin project objectives to create a common, barrier-free R&I eco-system for our researchers and partners, and to strive to make our research increasingly more interdisciplinary and international. Thus, the pilot was linked to all seven transformation modules, but was most closely aligned to the module around developing a common R&I agenda and module focusing on the exploration of joint university structures.

Una Europa R&I strategy workshop

The aim of this pilot activity was to develop an online format for strategic future discussions to identify emerging research areas in interdisciplinary collaborative settings. The research community holds great insight regarding future developments but, due to the slow self-correcting nature of research, researchers are sometimes hesitant to co-create and express their insights prior to pre-reviewed processes. This pilot aimed to find a way to encourage academics to discuss their insights and find new collaborations beyond their research fields. The format the project opted to pilot was an online workshop preceded by a pre-assignment.

The workshop consisted of keynotes and facilitated group discussions. To lead the participants in the grand challenges approach and the EU's "Approach to International R&I Collaboration in a Changing World", the workshop included two keynote speeches: Aleksi Neuvonen, Demos Helsinki think tank, and Nienke Buisman, Head of Unit, Directorate-General for R&I, Global Approach & International Partnerships, International Cooperation. The workshop was co-designed and co-facilitated by the think tank Demos Helsinki.

The feedback from attendees was generally positive and enthusiastic. Many participants found that they lacked the skills and traditions required for this kind of multi-/interdisciplinary workshop approach and valued an introduction to this working method. There is future potential to use this workshop format when developing the Una Europa Focus Areas into interdisciplinary hubs and as part of the community engagement in the general Una Europa strategic work. However, further use of co-creative workshops will necessitate dedicated ownership within the Alliance for both their organisation and facilitation.

Piloting a process Horizon Europe Pillar II Call matchmaking

The aim of this pilot activity was to develop a process for interdisciplinary matchmaking for Horizon Europe Pillar II calls. According to the Una.Resin WP1 benchmarking phase, there is a major interest and unused potential in our Alliance regarding European funding, and particularly, Horizon Europe Pillar II funding. Whilst most partner universities have existing support service structures, there is potential to build systematic and sustainable support for the calls at an Una Europa level and to share best practice. The pilot project identified the enabling and hindering structures, processes, and cultures at the partner universities and at the Alliance level, whilst sharing best practice and tools to create an ideal process.

The pilot action was designed and facilitated in close collaboration with the Una Europa Research Coordination Cluster, the One Health self-steering committee, and the Una Europa vzw external funding manager. Jean-Charles Cavitte, an EC Research Policy Officer, provided a keynote at the first of the two matchmaking workshops, which familiarised participants with EC policy and EU-funded research linked to One Health.

The feedback from participants was positive and illustrated how, with refinement, the matchmaking format offered a highly successful approach for responding to interdisciplinary funding Horizon Europe Pillar II calls. The tight schedule and the process for identifying proposal coordinators was the most problematic element of the pilot.

In the Horizon Pillar II matchmaking process, the Alliance should support the following: 1) identifying topics and coordinators (starting point); 2) collecting Expressions of Interest (Eols); 3) matchmaking workshops; and 4) general information sessions about the funding instrument. On the other hand, the proposal writing support – including grant writer resources and potential travel funds – should be provided by the coordinating university. We also learned that there is a need for an online platform allowing for the interactive collection of Eols.

The most important **outcome** of the pilot was the development of the co-creation workshop and matchmaking formats and processes themselves, which are ready for future use. The pilot allowed us to develop and test the processes step-by-step and to identify the tools, skills, and human resources needed to collaboratively pursue an interdisciplinary pathway.

In terms of **lessons learnt**, it should be noted that organising these kinds of workshops or matchmaking events is time-intensive and requires an understanding of local contexts and networks. The process and the tools are not enough, with skilled facilitators and systematic communication also being key for success. The universities should consider the designing and facilitation of collaborative workshops, both online and on-site, as a specialist skill of

research professionals, and dedicated training for the development of this skill would be highly beneficial. To accelerate interdisciplinary research collaboration, Una Europa must pay more attention to matching Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) and Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) fields and foster collaboration across Focus Areas.

Pilot Evaluation 2: Developing a concept for a Una Europa collaboration platform

The aim of this pilot was to develop a concept for an Una Europa collaboration platform. The platform was envisioned to consist of an evolving set of tools and services for cross-disciplinary and cross-sectoral collaboration and networking within the Una Europa ecosystem and throughout the R&I lifecycle on the prioritised global challenges. Initially, a number of signature projects were planned to be selected for testing the tools, activities, and consolidated support services.

The approach to develop the pilot was comprehensive and linked to all seven transformation modules, with the following modules being the main focus of the pilot: (2) strengthen human capital'; (3) sharing infrastructure and resources; (4) engage non-academic actors; and (7) explore joint university structures.

The development of the pilot was achieved by a number of actions that can be separated into two categories:

- A series of consultations and workshops: The potential needs and requirements of a collaboration platform were first identified and discussed in regular Una Europa RCC meetings and in two dedicated workshop sessions, one with the One Health steering committee and one with the public-, private-, and 3rd sector collaboration cluster (PPTSC). Further input was gained via a questionnaire circulated among all the Una.Resin WPs and clusters. From this questionnaire, the main desires and needs of a collaborative platform could be distilled.
- Mapping procedures: A preliminary mapping of existing research portals at the 11 partner institutions was conducted. This preliminary activity laid the groundwork of a potential and substantial follow-up mapping of commercial platforms, as identified in the consultations and workshops. Pre-existing platforms could either be used as best practice examples from which to base an Una Europa platform, or in their existing form.

The key project **outcome** was the identification, in consultation with the Una Europa community, of the needs and desirable functionalities of a collaborative platform and, in turn, the aspects that should be addressed by the platform and areas in which the platform should foster collaboration. These can be summarised as follows:

- Developing careers and skills.
- Research Funding Portals.
- Research Portals (Research Information System).
- Sharing information on RIRs.
- Enhancing citizen science in research.

The most important insight gained from stakeholder consultations was that the platform should be simple, intuitive, and easy to use. All given information would need to be visible and as transparent as possible. For this to be an efficient tool for researchers and external partners, it should facilitate their work and not add more complexity to their daily tasks. The target users of the platform are not homogenous, and the functions needed are dependent on the user. The two key users will be academic researchers and research professionals. Under the first group, the early and advanced career stage researchers may need different support and, thus, also different tools. On the other hand, the research professionals need tools to support the researchers, but also tools to advance their own career and distil best practices, which will benefit both the individual professionals and their institutions.

During the project lifecycle, Una.Futura was launched as the second phase of funding for Una Europa under the umbrella of Erasmus+. As part of Una.Futura, Una Europa vzw was tasked to design and develop a comprehensive platform, "Una.Connect". Una.Resin is working closely with Una Europa vzw to make sure that the **lessons learnt** and insights from this project are used in the process of conceptualising a broader Una Europa platform, with WP1 members participating in the stakeholder consultations for the design of the platform. The main findings and preliminary results of this pilot have been communicated to the Una Europa vzw and this report will be used in the further conceptualisation of the Una.Connect platform. This phase will start in 2024 and the final product will be live by the end of the Una Futura project in 2026.

To address urgent research-related needs in the short term, prior to the establishment of a comprehensive platform, Una Europa should leverage commercially available products and further develop its website. These urgent needs include information on research funding calls, tools to facilitate Eols and subsequent matchmaking, and listing our partner institutions' research portals to aid in identifying potential collaborators. Additionally, tools are needed to share online training courses for researchers and research professionals that are offered by our partner institutions or which have been jointly developed. Coordination of these efforts will be the responsibility of Una Europa vzw, with research professionals taking on advisory roles. In the medium term, a tool for sharing information on research and data infrastructures will be required. In the long term, Una Europa should aim to explore the possibilities of developing AI-based tools that can collect data from our partner universities' research portals, enabling seamless matchmaking between researchers, research groups, and interdisciplinary units. Some of our partner universities are currently developing similar approaches that could serve as pilots and support with identifying best practice.

Pilot Evaluation 3: Blueprint for a common catalogue of research infrastructures

The aim of this pilot action was to undertake the first steps towards developing a Una Europa digital catalogue of RIs and a portal of services. The project, thus, sought to develop a platform that provided a unified system for managing RI data, enabling institutions to easily share information and collaborate on research activities. There is a need, as expressed by stakeholders, to share information and knowledge on RIs and resources available in the Una Europa universities. This sharing is regarded as a prerequisite for facilitating cross-institutional

access and R&I collaborations and is the rationale behind the pilot concept. The pilot addressed the following transformation modules: sharing infrastructure and resources, and (indirectly) comprehensive mainstreaming of Open Science practices.

The methodology aimed to involve relevant stakeholders in specific discussion meetings. A working group of Information Technology (IT) experts of Una Europa institutions was created, and 14 participants from eight Una Europa universities were involved in four meetings, including a specific seminar to share best practices on RIs catalogues. This seminar involved guest experts who designed the Flanders Research Information Space (FRIS) that collects information on publicly funded research in Flanders, from the Flemish department of Science, Economy and Innovation.

Preliminary data on institutional RIs catalogue was collected from stakeholders to provide an overview of the different catalogues and approaches at institutional level, taking into consideration that some institutions have not yet developed such a catalogue. This overview provided a starting point from which to develop a first prototype and provided a concrete example of how a common RIs catalogue could work, whilst also illustrating the resulting benefits. Via the process of advancing the first prototype, stakeholders had an opportunity to feed into an initial discussion on the definition of a data model and to the development of governance processes so as to ensure data quality. From a technical point of view, participants discussed an approach that would avoid both the duplication of work and an increasing effort from institutions in terms of human and financial resources. The outcome was a set of preliminary recommendations for the design and development of a common catalogue based on a process of harvesting the RIs information available at the institutional level, with an automatic system to collect and display the existing data in a single place (web platform). Interoperability with existing catalogues, also at regional and national level, was discussed as a key point.

The pilot succeeded in bringing together stakeholders, and engaging RIs and IT experts, to start sharing a common vision and produce concrete recommendations for the development of a common RIs catalogue, including specific indications for universities that have not yet developed an institutional catalogue. These recommendations were condensed in a preliminary blueprint⁷. This **outcome** is of interest to different actors within and beyond the Una Europa community (researchers, RI managers, data experts, decision-makers, other universities and alliances), and provides a foundation that, with a commitment from institutional decision-makers, can be developed further.

The key medium-long term impacts are related to the concrete development of a Una Europa common RIs catalogue and portal of services (e.g., booking, training). This catalogue and portal will increase awareness among the academic and professional community of the RIs available across the Una Europa universities and facilitate access to them. This will foster R&I cooperation and an efficient use of RIs that, in turn, will positively impact financial sustainability. RIs among non-academic public, private, and third sector users will also be promoted, as well as their use among citizens. Furthermore, a common catalogue and portal of services will contribute to the promotion of Open Science principles in RIs operations and activities. In general, a common catalogue can greatly benefit the academic and professional

⁷ The preliminary blueprint is provided in the Supporting Document accompanying this deliverable.

community by fostering new collaborations in R&I and education, and inducing an institutional change towards the opening and sharing of RIs across the Alliance.

In terms of **lessons learnt**, it is worth underlining the importance of: 1) sharing best practices and experiences within the Alliance, but also taking into consideration the approaches of other alliances and projects; 2) adopting a technical methodology that avoids increasing or duplicating the effort of personnel working on RIs catalogues; 3) having a clear commitment from institutional decision-makers that, in turn, will promote the active involvement of relevant professionals from the Una Europa universities; and 4) carefully assessing costs for the creation and maintenance of a common catalogue, and defining an effective management model with clear roles and responsibilities.

The key recommendation is to scale up this pilot project to produce an advanced version of the blueprint, based on a shared commitment from the governing members of the Alliance. The scaling up of the blueprint was also recommended in the Una Europa Strategy for Sharing RIRs (Una.Resin Deliverable 2.2). The advanced blueprint will need to address technical requirements, including indications for the development of further functionalities and services, as well as a costing analysis that factors in the requirement for dedicated personnel and an associated management model.

Pilot Evaluation 4: Matchmaking formats to improve the Una Europa RIR Sharing

The aim of this pilot action was to experiment with a matchmaking format that brings together representatives of Una Europa RIs (researchers and RIs managers) to discuss possible paths for opening and sharing infrastructures and establishing collaborations in R&I and education. This RI matchmaking exercise was carried out in the thematic fields of Cultural Heritage and One Health wherein two case studies were defined: Museums and Digital Collections, and Genomics.

The rationale for the pilot action resided in the need to create communities on RIs by connecting and creating networks of researchers and RI managers across the Alliance. Matchmaking events provide the opportunity for researchers and RI managers to get to know each other, share interests, ideas and expertise, and establish collaborations. The pilot addressed the sharing infrastructure and resources transformation module, and indirectly the comprehensive mainstreaming of Open Science practices module.

The first activity of the pilot was to define the scope for each thematic field in agreement with the RIs Cluster, and the Cultural Heritage and One Health self-steering committees. Based on the selected scope, the WP2 team identified the relevant RIs to engage in the pilot, with key Una.Resin stakeholders asked to identify further RIs that may be interested. For each case study, a call for EoIs was launched that targeted the relevant group of RIs through a specific form used to collect basic information, alongside preliminary inputs on needs and expectations of participants. This data was used to shape the workshops' agenda and drive the discussions. The group of RIs that expressed interest were invited to attend two matchmaking workshops, where sessions dedicated to the mutual knowledge of participants were followed by a more

specific discussion on mutual interests, ideas for joint actions, collaboration opportunities in relation to self-steering committees' activities, and paths (considering barriers and enablers) towards opening and sharing RIs. The workshop illustrated how developing links with the strategies and action plans of the relevant self-steering committees was key, as was empowering infrastructures to offer their own proposals and visions. The output was a report that presented ideas for undertaking concrete actions in the short, medium, and long run.

The pilot has achieved important **outcomes** through the implementation of the matchmaking format in the Cultural Heritage and One Health fields. The primary achievement is the establishment of networks consisting of RIs managers and responsible researchers in the field of Museums and Digital collections, and Genomics. The workshops allowed participants to connect with each other and, in doing so, understand their specificities and needs and define their mutual interests. The pilot project illustrated how establishing a network of RIs goes beyond the mere exchange of experiences and best practices and fosters joint collaborative activities (including research or educational projects) based on the impetus provided by researchers. Another important outcome of the pilot is the establishment of the direct connections between participating RIs and the Cultural Heritage and One Health self-steering committees. Both self-steering committees expressed interest in taking forward the collaboration with RIs in the framework of Una.Futura.

The connection between the participating RIs and the self-steering committees holds multiple benefits and prospective impacts. Firstly, it enables the RIs to support activities that will be validated as part of the Una.Futura project action plan, whilst empowering RIs to bring their own vision and suggest their own collaboration activities for research enhancement. In a long-term perspective, empowering RIs as actors of international collaboration could transform the institutional vision of infrastructure from solely being a support system, with RIs also being perceived as a driving force behind research activities. This change in perception could help improve the valorisation of RIs, and both encourage and support policy makers in developing global solutions on openness and shareability.

The key **lessons learnt** from the pilot are as follows: 1) matchmaking workshops enable the establishment and strengthening of networks, laying the basis for fruitful collaborations; 2) continuing and scaling up of the workshops to different types of RIs, disciplines, and Focus Areas is crucial for creating a knowledge community of RIs; 3) identifying mutual interest and implementing joint activities is a crucial step for the opening up and potential sharing of RIs; 4) collaborations forged through workshops and matchmaking activities can serve as a springboard for joint research projects, collaborative grants, and educational initiatives; and 5) the alignment and synergy between the Una Europa's Focus Areas and RIs are essential for unlocking the full potential of collaboration. By identifying areas of convergence, Una Europa could leverage the expertise and resources of RIs to address the challenges and research questions within the Focus Areas.

The most important recommendations are related to the development of an improved and consolidated matchmaking format with the view of continuation and scaling-up, which was also suggested in the Una Europa Strategy for Sharing RIRs (Una.Resin Deliverable 2.2). Planning a series of workshops dedicated to RIs presentations and discussions is highly recommended to aid matchmaking. It would also be useful to build in time for small-group

workshops/seminars that address specific issues (e.g., costing and funding models; Findable-Accessible-Interoperable-Reusable (FAIR) data management) or for sharing knowledge and expertise on topics of common interest, since these could further facilitate discussion. A digital platform – including articles, newsletters, and success stories – could be created to facilitate the connection among RIs representatives and give visibility to activities across the network. Representatives from the Una Europa self-steering committees should be present during the workshops in order to provide the necessary context and information on the framework of the Focus Area activities. It is also important to find synergies with other collaborative actions of the Alliance, including educational programmes.

Pilot Evaluation 5: Una Europa Citizen Science Toolkit

The Citizen Science Toolkit is a pilot project dedicated to citizen science. This project has a dual focus on two transformation modules: embedding citizens and society and strengthening human capital. Its primary goal is to remove obstacles hindering cross-border and cross-sectoral R&I collaboration by empowering Una Europa early-stage researchers to initiate citizen science projects.

The project adopted a structured four-step approach. The initial phases involved mapping strategies, policies, support services, and best practices in the field of citizen science. Data was collected through two questionnaires distributed to administrative staff, researchers, and university policy makers across the Alliance. Additionally, a series of webinars showcasing exemplary citizen science projects and a cartography of citizen science initiatives in two Focus Areas, One Health and Cultural Heritage, was developed. The subsequent phases focused on brainstorming sessions and workshops organised by the Citizen Engagement Cluster. These sessions aimed to facilitate an exchange of experiences, delve into challenges, and propose potential solutions to enhance citizen science within the Alliance. After collating and providing a synthesis of the outputs from the brainstorming sessions and workshop, the pilot concept was developed and presented during an additional brainstorming session in September 2022 in Edinburgh.

The pilot consists of eight interviews, representing the eight universities participating in the Una.Resin project, conducted with researchers who are experts in the field of citizen science. Each interview addresses key aspects of citizen science, such as project design, citizen engagement, impact evaluation, and advice for early-stage researchers. These interviews are publicly accessible on the Una Europa website and are accompanied by guidelines distilled from the insights shared within them. Together, these interviews and guidelines form a toolkit that researchers engaging in participative research can use in the preparation of a citizen science project. Importantly, the toolkit is licensed as an Open Education Resource, aligning with Una Europa's commitment to openness, inclusivity, and the dissemination of innovative work.

The pilot's main **outcome** is the production of a Citizen Science toolkit, comprised of educational support materials for implementing citizen science projects. This toolkit increases awareness of various citizen science practices and methodologies, benefiting researchers at all career stages. In addition, the toolkit offers recommendations aimed at institutions and

alliances on how to enhance citizen science initiatives and amplify citizen participation in research. It also helps research managers understand how to better support citizen science projects. Finally, the toolkit provides participating researchers with a platform to showcase their projects to a broader audience and lays the foundation for a network of researchers who specialise in participatory research.

The project holds the capacity to mobilise a cultural transformation among researchers, research support officers, and policymakers, which would further lead to a shift in the R&I landscape of Una Europa universities. The project seeks to catalyse an increase in the number of citizen science projects and stimulate collaborative, interdisciplinary projects that address global issues.

Considering the interdisciplinary nature of projects, **lessons learnt** from the pilot project highlight the importance of embracing a wide definition of citizen science. Collaboration with stakeholders, experts in citizen science, and other researchers (for Una Europa, the self-steering committees of the Focus Areas) will be crucial in further developments of the pilot, and for ensuring the project remains both relevant to its intended beneficiaries and responsive to their needs. Therefore, a clearly defined and coherent understanding of the target group from the project's outset is essential.

The pilot project suggests a clear and reusable format that can be scaled up. It could be extended to other disciplines or Focus Areas, providing a multifaceted perspective on participative practices. At the same time, the format could be upgraded via more active involvement of citizens and third parties (i.e., not the researchers). The toolkit could be expanded to encompass networking events or by including additional support materials in a variety of formats. If the toolkit proves to be successful overtime, there may be potential to transform it into an online educational course.

Pilot Evaluation 6: Open Science

This Open Science pilot project was designed to simultaneously develop and experiment with two issues. First, discussing key policy issues in the framework of a European University alliance via a mechanism of formulating and debating bold hypotheses. Second, offering a fresh look at the idea of Open Science to further develop the concept of Open Science, and make it more understandable to researchers, professional staff members, and the public. In doing so, the pilot addressed the following transformation modules: foster Open Science and open access to scientific results and data, develop material for integration of science and society in curricula, and engage with multiple stakeholders for R&I decision-making at local, national, regional EU or global level.

In the first stage, the topic of the pilot project (i.e., the question of how Open Science should be understood) was chosen through an open discussion and consultations with various stakeholders (including Una.Resin WPs, Una Europa Future University Lab, clusters, Una.Resin Project Steering Committee). In the second stage, Una Europa's think tank, the Future University Lab, was entrusted with developing a concept note to provide a novel approach for understanding Open Science. In the third stage, the draft of the concept note

was discussed internally (i.e., within the Una.Resin project) and updated accordingly. In the fourth stage, the final version of the concept note was adopted by the Future University Lab's Steering Committee, presented to the Una.Resin Project Steering Committee and the Una Europa Board of Directors, and distributed online among the Una Europa Community and beyond. In the fifth and final stage, the concept note was discussed in an online panel discussion, open to anyone interested.

In terms of important **outcomes**, it can be noted that this pilot project significantly contributed to increasing the understanding of the nature of Open Science practices and, in particular, how the openness of science constitutes an integral aspect of any rational scientific inquiry among the Una Europa community. Similarly, it showcased the usefulness of a methodology that uses bold (and often controversial) ideas to fuel broad discussions of policy-related issues. These outcomes may potentially lead to institutional change, both at the level of the Una Europa Alliance and in the broader context of the ERA. They influence understandings of Open Science and help researchers and professional staff members see how Open Science is intertwined with the quality of research, as well as with the social responsibility of the researcher.

As far as the **lessons learned** are concerned, it should be underlined that researchers and professional staff members tend to understand Open Science in a narrow way, making it difficult for them to see the real benefits it offers. Hence, a broader understanding of Open Science as a value may be beneficial to creating a more coherent view of science, one in which the quality of research is strengthened by both the individual and the public understanding of what science is. It is essential to reshape the academic culture to embrace a broader, more integrated understanding of Open Science, and illustrate how this can enhance the overall quality of research. Finally, environments that encourage critical discussions of unconventional ideas should be encouraged so as to challenge the status quo and promote intellectual growth.

Pilot Evaluation 7: Team Science

The Team Science pilot project focused on developing and experimenting with an innovative format for enriching the human capital development framework of the Una Europa Alliance in relation to the issue of Team Science. More precisely, the pilot centred on developing a joint MOOC on Team Science and a practically-oriented workshop for researchers and professional staff members. The MOOC and the workshop together constitute an experimental format for future skill development and for an Una Europa certification framework, but one that is transferrable and scalable to other European University alliances. At its core, the pilot aimed to emphasise the importance and intricacies of interdisciplinary collaboration in research. In meeting these aims, the pilot project strategically engaged with multiple transformation modules, including: anticipation of research impact, promotion of R&I standards, broadening the scope of R&I activities, stakeholder engagement in R&I decision-making, and advocacy for Open Science.

The pilot consisted of six distinct stages: identification of the joint team for developing the format, development of the content of the MOOC as well as the workshop, recording of the

MOOC, participation in the MOOC by selected researchers/professional staff members, the online workshop, and collecting feedback. The creation of a MOOC tailored for researchers and professionals marked a significant **outcome** in standardising interdisciplinary team science. The course not only provided knowledge on the subject but also demonstrated collaborative principles through its structure and delivery.

The pilot project further developed the comprehensive understanding of Team Science and its importance – a topic which is very much neglected in skills development programs and HR policies. The MOOC has played a pivotal role in translating and synthesising Una.Resin's knowledge and innovations into an accessible format. By making this course more broadly available, the pilot will ensure that the synthesised knowledge reaches a broader audience, further amplifying its impact. The potential for influence is vast. For example, the pilot emphasises the need for interdisciplinary approaches that, in turn, may inform policies related to research collaboration and standardisation.

The **lessons learned** from implementing the pilot underline the need to pool expertise and support at the Alliance level, as well as facilitate collaborative environments and address often overlooked areas of skills development. By integrating the lessons learnt, future initiatives can be structured to maximise the effectiveness and reach of professional development programs within the Alliance.

Pilot Evaluation 8: Fostering business-academia cooperation

The purpose of this pilot is to develop a preliminary prototype of a common catalogue of research groups and transferable research activities at the Una.Resin level, and ultimately, examine the potential for creating a catalogue in the future. This pilot project, thus, addressed the following transformation modules: enlarge the scope of R&I activities by fostering business-academia cooperation, and promoting cooperation between research groups.

Universities cannot exist in isolation from society. Close collaboration between academia and business brings benefits to both researchers and industry. Two main needs were identified and, then, addressed in the preliminary prototype to promote business-academia cooperation:

- The need to promote cooperation between different research groups, which is essential to be able to respond to complex industry demands. The pilot project started by fostering such cooperation, providing researchers with access to information about the activities and characteristics of other research groups within the Alliance.
- The need to identify and give visibility to the activities developed by the research groups that can be transferable to industry. The pilot, thus, sought to collect this information and make it accessible to potential users.

The **outcome** of this pilot project is a prototype of research groups and a transfer catalogue (Una.Transfer | Una Europa (una-europa.eu)). If this information (research groups/transfer activities) is shared at the Alliance level, in an accessible and simple way, the different universities could benefit in several ways. For example, increased international collaborations between research groups will be established. Moreover, the markets for transferable research activities at international level will be widened. The pilot has produced a highly accessible

prototype that synthesises the main results. A final version of this prototype could be shared with the general public in the future.

Based on the **lessons learnt** from this pilot project, it is important that the Alliance and participating universities provide a framework that both allows information to be easily shared and quickly identifies transferable activities that can promote business-academia cooperation.

Supporting Documents

Evaluation of Pilots

Final Version	Theoni Massara, Ciara Merrick, Elina Tonteri, Klaus Wiehl, Alessia Franchini, Francisco Javier Pérez Trujillo, Elżbieta Binczycka-Gacek, Bartosz Brożek, Mateusz Hohol, Ekaterina Smoliakova	30/01/2024
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Introduction

The Una.Resin pilot projects aimed to collectively identify and test solutions to overcome barriers that may hinder the establishment of a seamless, common research and innovation (R&I) ecosystem. Furthermore, they sought to contribute to the European Union’s goals of empowering the university sector in its own transformation efforts towards a future 2030 vision in the field of R&I. Una.Resin commenced with initial benchmarking exercises that were conducted in 2021/2022.⁸ The findings from this exercise informed the development of a series of co-creation workshops⁹ that, in turn, led to the advancement and implementation of eight pilot actions:

1. R&I - Developing a format for supporting systematic collaboration on the Una Europa priority global challenges.
2. Developing a concept for a Una Europa collaboration platform.
3. Blueprint for a common catalogue of research infrastructures.
4. Matchmaking formats to improve the Una Europa research infrastructures sharing.
5. Una Europa Citizen Science Toolkit.
6. The Open Science pilot.
7. The Team Science pilot.
8. Fostering business-academia cooperation.

The pilot projects intended to test and implement models within the Cultural Heritage and One Health Una Europa Focus Areas and collectively they addressed all seven transformation modules.

The Una.Resin pilots have been evaluated with a view to disseminate lessons learnt, best practices, and recommendations and, ultimately, to provide direction and insight into future activities to support Una Europa in achieving its aim of establishing a common R&I ecosystem. The evaluations assess the impact and outcome of each pilot in relation to its objectives and aims and offer recommendations. Each evaluation provides a narrative presenting the insights and considerations of both the design and implementation phase. They also draw out learnings and explain what worked well and why, describe the challenges that were faced and how these were

⁸ The three benchmarking exercises were: D1.1 Benchmarking R&I Strategies and Priorities for a Joint Una Europa Strategy; D2.1 Mapping RIRs and priorities for joint strategy; and D3.1 Mapping HR Strategies and priorities for joint strategy. These benchmarking exercises align to the join strategy modules that were initiated as part of the Una.Resin project.

⁹ The Una.Resin co-creation workshops were: 1) R&I; 2) Towards a Una Europa Strategy and Action plan for sharing RIRs; 3) Excellent research and beyond; 4) Creative environment for happy people; and 5) Breaking down boundaries with citizens science.

overcome, and provide an understanding of the sustainability of the pilot, giving particular attention to opportunities for improvements in future implementations.

Presentation of Una.Resin Pilot Evaluations

Pilot Evaluation 1: Developing a format for supporting systematic collaboration on the Una Europa priority global challenges

Objectives and aims of the pilot

The aim of the pilot was to develop and test methods to accelerate cross-disciplinary and cross-sectoral collaboration and networking in addressing the Una Europa priority global challenges. This comprised of two separate actions: 1) a Una Europa R&I strategy workshop and 2) piloting a process Horizon Europe Pillar II Call matchmaking. Via these two actions, the pilot sought to understand the barriers and enablers in the following areas:

- Building the Una Europa Network for collaborative research:
 - The areas targeted in particular: international research collaboration, research infrastructures, ecosystems with non-academic actors and research lifecycle (e.g., sharing, management, support, training personnel, opening collaboration to non-academic organisational partners and citizens).
- Working cultures:
 - Inter-, Trans-, Crossdisciplinarity and challenge-based approach in research collaboration.
 - Co-creation of a workshop-type in the research context.
 - Foresight and futures literacy, and understanding the grand challenges in the context of excellence and impact (the key goals of the Una Europa partner universities).
- Institutional processes:
 - General institutional enablers and barriers for international research collaboration.
 - Support for research funding: alignment of the structures and priorities of the partner universities.
- Incentives and practices for researchers to build a successful Horizon Europa Pillar II proposal.

The pilot also aimed to satisfy the following aims when planning and appointing the participants and speakers for both the workshop and matchmaking event:

- Equality both from the gender and the career stage perspective;
- Emphasising the safe space for new ideas; and
- The European Commission (EC) context both in terms of the grand challenges and research funding instruments.

The approach was comprehensive and, thus, linked to all seven transformation modules. However, the most directly addressed transformation modules were: 1) develop a common R&I agenda, and 7) explore joint university structures. In term of institution change, the objective of the pilot are closely linked to the following modules: 1) develop activities to

anticipate the potential social, environmental, and economic impacts of research (e.g., risk assessment, threat assessment, foresight, impact assessment, gender analysis; 2) help develop R&I standards that enhance social responsibility, inclusiveness, sustainability of R&I processes and products; 3) develop material for integration of science and society in curricula (e.g., covering Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM), public engagement, ethics, gender); and 4) enlarge the scope of R&I activities by fostering informal science education (museums, science centres), promoting citizen science, engaging civil society actors and citizens.

The pilot primarily aimed to target the Una.Resin project itself by informing the R&I strategy development. In addition to creating an online working format, the workshop aimed to identify research themes the Una Europa community deems as important in the future to respond to the grand challenges and identify enablers and barriers to international research collaboration. In addition, the pilot also intended to target research performing organisations, researchers, businesses and industry engaged in Research & Development (R&D), citizens and Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs), and public authorities. The beneficiaries of the pilot are Una Europa organisations and participating researchers.

Simultaneously to the pilot, the University of Helsinki was developing a roadmap to implement its strategic aim of interdisciplinary research. The process was conducted in an innovative way using the methods of co-creation. It provided many useful pedagogical learnings for our pilot about how to engage workshop participants and the mindset of co-learning.

Initial design and implementation of the pilot project

Una Europa R&I strategy workshop

The pilot “developing a format for supporting systematic collaboration on the Una Europa priority global challenges” was originally scheduled to take place in the second half of the Una.Resin project. The COVID-19 pandemic forced the pilot to move online and, consequently, a workshop that could be hosted and delivered online was designed. The pandemic complicated not only the implementation of the pilot, but also the development of the Una Europa R&I strategy, which is the flagship development of the Una.Resin project. The workshop, however, provided a space to collect insights to feed into the Una Europa R&I strategy development. The workshop aimed to identify the true needs of researchers and the barriers that they perceive as potentially hindering Una Europa R&I collaboration, as well as the challenges of building a larger ecosystem. Based on these aims, a three-hour online workshop was designed that was preceded by a pre-assignment.

During the planning phase, continuous discussions were held with Una Europa vzw and with the team preparing the Una Europa 2030 strategy. The process and the relevant working questions were designed with other Una.Resin Work Packages (WPs) and the research coordination cluster members. The Una.Resin project managers at each partner university provided necessary support by identifying and inviting participants for the workshop. The Una.Resin WP2 colleagues helped articulate relevant questions around research infrastructures and their input ensure that the workshop outcomes also satisfied their work towards the Una Europa Research Infrastructure and Resources (RIR) strategy. The Demos Helsinki Think Tank, who have vast experience of organising co-creative futures workshops, were recruited to support with designing and facilitating the R&I strategy workshop. The

discussion groups were facilitated by colleagues from the Una Europa Research Coordination Cluster and other Una.Resin WP members.

The pre-assignment sought to tune participants to potential future visions and emerging research themes, whilst also supporting the preparation of workshop discussion questions. As most of the participants were not familiar with Una Europa, a series of materials were provided including information on the excellence of the Una Europa universities, on the Alliance's current priority areas, on the grand challenges¹⁰ and key strategic orientations, on the Horizon Europe clusters, and on the UN Sustainable Development goals (<https://sdgs.un.org/goals>). As a technical solution, the interactive on-line platform Flinga (<https://flinga.fi/>) was utilised.

The online workshop consisted of two parts. First, there were keynotes addressing Una Europa, grand challenges, and the EU's approach to international R&I collaboration in a changing world. The second part of the workshop consisted of group discussions, where online canvases were used to structure the discussions. Each group had their own facilitator.

The following challenges were faced, and overcome, in designing and implementing the Una Europa R&I strategy workshop:

- This type of online co-working, as well as the interdisciplinary futures approach, was largely new to both the research professionals involved in planning and facilitating and the academic participants. At the time of the workshop, Una Europa was relatively new and unknown resulting in some resistance from the project side to this novel approach. The pre-assignment aimed to address this challenge. However, the pre-assignment turned out to be too complicated, with too many materials provided. There was also confusion from the researchers about the purpose of the workshop, which was perceived as not directly related to their current research. However, during and after the workshop and once participants were familiar with the new way of working, there was excitement in the air and many participants expressed interest in a follow-up workshop.
- There were cultural differences among participants in terms of both familiarity with online working and with co-creation working. The involvement of researchers from different career stages, research fields, and cultural backgrounds was emphasised, but it was challenge to get a sound representation as participant numbers had to be limited to six per partner university. In future, special emphasis should be put on expanding the target group to citizens and non-academics with diverse backgrounds. However, five participants plus the facilitator proved to be a suitable group size for this type of workshop.
- Unfortunately, not all registered participants showed up and there were participants coming and going throughout the workshop. This underlined the essential role of facilitators who could reorganise the groups during the workshop. The disappearance of the participants during the workshop must be anticipated and there must be a readiness to reform the groups if needed.
- Due to the tight planning schedule, there was limited time to brief facilitators prior to the workshop and the facilitator role was new to many of those supporting the delivery of the workshop. In future, the universities should consider hosting collaborative workshops both online and in-person. Designing and facilitating co-creation workshops could be

¹⁰ The grand challenges materials were produced by Sitra (<https://www.sitra.fi/en/>) and Demos Helsinki.

promoted as a special skill for research professionals, with the provision of specific training to support the development of this skill.

- Project budget was very limited, and Demos Helsinki provided support at a low cost due to their personal interest. Their support was integral to creating a successful workshop format for future use.

Piloting a process Horizon Europe Pillar II Call matchmaking

The initiative to pilot matchmaking under the Horizon Europe Pillar II call came from the Una Europa One self-steering committee and from the Una Europa external funding officer. Matchmaking aligned with the pilots aim to further develop methods to accelerate cross-disciplinary and cross-sectoral collaboration in addressing the priority challenges, as well as to the format and the lessons learnt from the Una Europa R&I strategy workshop.

The whole process, from first planning meetings to the evaluation phase, lasted from February 2022 until September 2023. The pilot included the following steps:

1. Collection of Eols via the online Lyyti platform (<https://www.lyyti.com/en/>).
2. Identification and briefing of potential coordinators.
3. An online workshop that included a general session highlighting European goals and the particularities of the Horizon Europe Pillar II call, as well as a facilitated group discussion aimed at drafting the core idea of the proposal and appointing the core group for the proposal preparation. This online workshop was based on the template created in the R&I strategy workshop (Zoom as a meeting platform and Google Slides for the online canvases).
4. A hybrid (online and in-person) workshop for the groups of researchers who engaged with proposal preparation (Teams). In this workshop the participants had a chance to:
 - 1) learn about the particularities of the call and proposal writing in the plenary sessions,
 - 2) get support for the proposal drafting, and
 - 3) participate in the Una Europa One Health networking event. The workshop was organised in connection to the Una Europa General Assembly.
5. A proposal preparation phase.
6. An online evaluation questionnaire after the process (Lyyti platform).

The pilot action was designed in close collaboration with several Una Europa bodies via online and in-person meetings and workshops. The Una Europa Research Coordination Cluster (RCC) had a pivotal role in understanding the internal processes and shared best practices from their home institutions, e.g., the ideal questions for the Eol template. The RCC identified the contact points for academics, as well as a pathway for approaching research funding professionals. The group also had an essential role in advising on the particularities of European funding and the local research funding service structures and processes. The One Health self-steering committee acted as the academic owner of the process. The RCC and One Health self-steering committee provided an important understanding of the needs of the academics participating involved and identified the themes from the Horizon Europe Pillar II Call that the matchmaking event centred around. The Una Europa vzw external funding manager supported with the identification of the roles and provided up-to-date information about the Pillar II call preparation status. Una Europa vzw also supported with the identification and invitation of the keynote speaker, Jean-Charles Cavitte (EC Research Policy Officer), of the online workshop, who presented insights on policy and EU-funded research in the area of

One Health. In addition, each academic group preparing a proposal was supported by an experienced research funding professional appointed by two Una Europa universities, the University of Helsinki and the KU Leuven.

The Una Europa external funding officer conducted the preselection activity, listing 37 Horizon Europe Pillar II call topics that were presented to the One Health self-steering committee. In the end, four topics were chosen. The EoI invitation was sent to 74 academics representing the Una Europa Focus Areas, who were asked to share the invitations with their colleagues. The EoI invitation was also shared by the RCC using the internal channels at the partner institutions. In the EoI phase, 79 answers were received from five Una Europa universities. Due to minimal interest in one of the topics, three were chosen for the online workshop. There were 35 academics participating in the workshop from the same five universities, with research professionals facilitating and observing the workshop. Finally, there were 30 participants in the hybrid proposal preparation meeting. The evaluation questionnaire was sent to everyone who received the original EoI invitation, and 12 answers were received from the same five universities that were involved from the beginning of the process.

The following challenges were faced in piloting the Horizon Europe Pillar II Call matchmaking process, which also offer a number of recommendations:

- The aim was to have research participants from various fields across STEM and the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) subjects. To meet this aim, the short call descriptions indicated SSH input was essential for a successful proposal, even where the call was One Health focused. We advertised the matchmaking to all Focus Areas and relevant researchers at all universities. Still, mainly natural scientists were interested. As the Una Europa Focus Areas are further developed into research hubs, cross-focus matchmaking and bi-annual strategic workshops aimed at each focus area, self-steering committees and different career-stage researchers should give serious consideration to build long-term collaboration and develop the in-depth understanding required for new knowledge and the development of successful proposals. Increasingly general awareness of Una Europa and the common communication channels should further support this aim.
- The message we got from our research community was, that besides the matchmaking, they also wished for grant writing support from Una Europa. The pilot illustrated how the level of support at the proposal preparation stage differs across the partner universities. In all cases, the most extensive support (including an appointed grant writer) is provided only to the proposals coordinated by the university and securing this support is generally not possible in Una Europa. One of the nine involved partner universities has an internal selection process for proposals coordinated by them, and so, it is important to ensure that the Una Europa process now, or in the future, do not conflict with this process. In this pilot, we navigated the above-mentioned conditions and needs by 1) providing general presentations about the Horizon Europe Pillar II particularities, and 2) inviting grant coaches from the coordinating universities to the onsite workshop at KU Leuven.
- We planned to use an interactive platform for collecting EoIs. The idea was that in an ideal situation the researchers could have initiated the discussion about the research topics already online. There were some platforms, like B2B, that would have been suitable and reasonably priced. However, they were still too expensive for our very limited project budget. Instead, we used an online questionnaire platform, which allowed

us to turn the answers into an excel format and, in the end, to a sharable catalogue. The University of Helsinki (UH) appointed additional human resources to do this. Manually creating shareable catalogues is time intensive and Una Europa should consider investing in an online platform, making this phase both easy and interactive in the future.

- The schedule of the pilot was tight and we needed to proceed at full speed, learning as we went. The tight timeframe resulted in a degree of confusion when running the workshops. The time gap between the online and the in-person workshops was short and left little time for travel arrangements, and the participating academics asked us to organise the meeting in a hybrid mode to allow them all to participate. However, a hybrid meeting may not have been the most suitable mode for the workshop with one participant stating: “Very few attendees were present in Leuven. Interaction through mixed channels (in-person plus online) is difficult and time-consuming.” Another participant provided the following feedback: “The hybrid mode (online and onsite) especially, was not suitable for in-depth planning and discussion”. There was also major confusion that the workshop was an Una Europa signature event and there was support with travel costs, which was not the case. The difficulties experienced in the implementation of the workshop did, however, produced a valuable understanding of the expectations.
- Appointing coordinators was challenging. We received a lot of EoIs to participate in the call, but few experienced researchers were interested in coordinating calls. In the evaluation phase, we received the most negative feedback. This was mostly due to the tight schedule. We had very little time to identify and brief the potential coordinators before the online workshop. Moreover, throughout the pilot, as well as during the two workshops, we had problems with engagement and participants jumping between the call topic groups. This made it hard for the coordinators to identify their “own” group. In the future, it would make sense to have separate workshops for each topic.
- We received only 12 answers to the pilot evaluation form, despite indicating to participants that feedback would be used for development purposes. It would make sense to ask for feedback after the end of each stage, when it is still fresh in the memory of the participants.

Outcomes and impact of the pilot project

With this pilot we aimed to understand the institutional barriers and identify enablers to create conditions for barrier-free collaboration. The pilot provided essential understanding for the Una Europa R&I strategy preparation and resulted in two submitted Horizon Europe Pillar II consortium proposals. One of the two made it to the reserve list. In addition, one proposal was prepared, but not submitted in this round. These are very concrete outcomes. The most important outcome of the pilot was the development of the workshop and matchmaking processes that are now ready for the future use. The pilot allowed us to develop and test the process step by step and to identify the tools, skills, and human resources needed to carry out such creative collaborative interdisciplinary processes. The outcomes have been presented in more detail in the Una.Resin WP1 deliverable D1.1.

The Una Europa Focus Areas serve as excellent communities for the creation of interdisciplinary understanding and cross-discipline matchmaking. Matchmaking seems to be particularly effective within the Alliance context because there are additional drivers for cooperation (e.g., institutional support and strategic alignment). We have already shared the

lessons learnt with the Unite!, an alliance of research intensive and technical universities, and have identified collaboration opportunities to respond to interdisciplinary consortium calls in the area of sustainability.

The EC has asked Una Europa for more bottom-up collaborative research opportunities that are both open in scope and allow for interdisciplinary research perspectives. Una Europa is committed in its strategies (i.e., the Una Europa 2030 strategy and the Una Europa R&I strategy) to support bold interdisciplinary research and empower early-career researchers. The pilot provides essential tools and a new kind of mindset to explore inter-, trans- and multidisciplinary cooperation around the R&I activities in Una Europa and beyond. The R&I strategy workshop provided an experimental approach to increase understanding and support researchers in identifying weakness in emerging research areas that are pivotal for responding to the grand challenges of our time. The Horizon Pillar II process takes this to a more practical level and provides concrete tools for matchmaking and proposal ideation.

The feedback from the attendees of the R&I strategy, co-creation workshop was positive. However, some participants found that they lacked skills and traditions for this kind of multi-/interdisciplinary approach and would have benefitted from a more comprehensive introduction to this working method. We found that the research themes raised in this workshop were often crosscutting, reflecting scientific understandings that the grand challenges are interlinked and cannot be treated as separate phenomena. Terminologies and approaches such as “grand challenges” are hence not always the most fruitful way to engage researchers with this kind of workshop, as researchers tend to formulate their interests within the terminology and culture of their discipline. Una Europa is in an excellent position to share understanding between the research community and European decision makers.

The participants of the Horizon Europe Pillar II Call matchmaking represented five of the (at the time) nine Una Europa universities. Not getting EoIs from four of the universities reflects partly the One Health focus, but also the difference in the funding policies in the different partner countries. In some of the universities there is a strong national funding base, and the Horizon Europe calls are considered administratively heavy and thus not desired. In addition, at the time of our pilot, the UK member association to the Horizon Europe was still not secure and it was unclear if the UK participating university would be eligible for Horizon Europe funding. However, the feedback illustrated that the pilot was found most successful in “establishing new contacts” and “learning about consortium-based proposal preparation”; this is a remarkable outcome.

In particular, the workshop and matchmaking provided an opportunity for the early career researchers to widen their networks. Una Europa stands for diversity, academic freedom, and well-being, and the pilot indicates how institutional barriers and hierarchies could be overcome should alliances have the opportunity to propose call initiatives. The process also provides early career researchers with an opportunity to learn about the proposal process and the Horizon projects, preparing them to become coordinators themselves in the future.

Researchers’ feedback to the Una Europa pilot on Horizon Europe matchmaking

Following the matchmaking event, feedback was collected from researchers who participated in the event. The feedback consultation period ran from the 20/06/2023 to the 15/09/2023 and

took the form of a questionnaire, which also provided an opportunity to collect more general feedback (see Figure 1). The feedback gained tended to be positive (see Figure 2 and Figure 3) and has proven instrumental in understanding and collating lessons learnt and guiding the resulting recommendations.

Participant A: "In general, the whole strategy was well devised. With the lessons learned we for sure can refine and mature this approach to have a winning recipe for funding."

Participant B: "The Una Europa pilot for matchmaking was useful to discover opportunities and get to know complementary research teams in participating universities. Sadly enough, the mechanics of the proposal preparation were not targeted enough towards a winner application (as it happens in other proposals outside the Una Europa umbrella...)"

Participant C: "The idea to support proposal building for EU calls is great but I think the process needs to start earlier to allow the participants to really connect and know each other. More work with the potential coordinators in the beginning to consider the proposal text and scope."

Figure 1: General feedback from researchers who participated in the matchmaking event

Figure 2: Participants' answers to the question "I found the pilot helpful for..." (multiple answers allowed)

Figure 3: Participants' answers to the question "How satisfied were you with the different pilot phases?"

Question	Yes	No	Do not know
Was the structure of the workshop appropriate?	10	0	0
Did you find the templates and facilitation appropriate?	9	0	1
Did you find the presentations useful?	10	0	0
Did you find the technical platforms appropriate (Zoom & Google sheets)?	9	0	1

Table 1: Participants' answers in relation to the online workshop

Sustainability of the pilot project

In the coming years, the Una Europa Focus Areas are developing into interdisciplinary hubs for research and education. The hubs widen the ecosystem beyond academia to encompass local actors in the partner countries. Co-creation of the strategic understanding and cross-focus area matchmaking will have a pivotal role in this development. The Una Europa R&I strategy format supports this work perfectly. The workshop format could also be useful as part of the continuous, collaborative strategic work that is essential for this kind of Alliance. However, there is not yet a recognised owner who could facilitate such a workshop in the Alliance.

We are very confident that the Horizon Pillar II matchmaking process will be scaled up to a continuous Una Europa process. This process was included as a recommended action in the Una Europa R&I Funding Pathway (Una Europa R&I strategy Annex 1, WP1 Delivery 1.2.). As part of the R&I strategy implementation Roadmap (Una Europa R&I strategy Annex 2, WP1 Deliverable 1.2), the Una Europa partner institutions are currently discussing how the activities to implement the Una Europa R&I strategy should be prioritised. This process was prioritised with the highest score by the Una Europa vice rectors of research in their meeting on the 11th October 2023.

The Una Europa RCC, the expert group of research funding advisors, has now been appointed as a permanent Una Europa body. This is largely because of the learnings we gained in this pilot and the RCC has already taken ownership of the matchmaking process. There is also natural continuity as UH was the responsible organisation for this pilot and the RCC is chaired by UH. Thus, all lessons learnt and the formats created will be handed over to the future users.

The Una Europa Focus Areas are excellent incubators of interdisciplinary ideas and understanding. The Pillar II topics are still to be defined, and there may be rather little time to prepare the proposals after the call is announced. This leads to suboptimal processes and makes it difficult to ensure inclusivity of matchmaking. Bottom-up interdisciplinary funding would solve this.

Non-academic collaborations are crucial to successful consortium proposals and one of the ambitious aims of the Una.Resin project was to find ways to collaborate with non-academic partners throughout the Una Europa R&I ecosystem. However, developing such an ecosystem takes time. At the stage of planning the pilot, we did not have a ready ecosystem to reach out to. As our primary aim was to learn about the structures and processes at the partner universities and pilot the process on the Una Europa level, we decided to restrict the participation to the Una Europa level but invite some external key-note speakers. As a next

step, the process should be further developed at an institutional level to build ways to systematically identify infrastructures and non-academic collaborations relevant for the proposals. Support for responding to Pillar II and other major European research funding opportunities should be pro-active and the highest priority for the new vzw External Funding Officer. Alliance-level industry collaboration, like common fairs, is not a priority at this stage but should be a longer-term goal. Connection with industry and societal actors should draw from the activities of academic hubs, such as doctoral education activities and funding calls.

Una Europa institutions are global actors, and as an Alliance, we have an even broader reach. Understanding this reach as a responsibility and opportunity to address global challenges from diverse perspectives, Una Europa aims to establish multi-lateral global partnerships and engage global talent. The collaboration with the Una Europa strategic partner higher education institutions in Africa is progressively taking shape, and Una Europa should involve African partner institutions more systematically in matchmaking. In addition, Una Europa should support partners in solving mobility issues, like visas, of the African collaborators in participating the events organised in Europe.

Lessons learnt

A series of lessons have been identified from designing and implementing this pilot:

- Participants of both the R&I strategy workshop and the Horizon Europe Pillar II matchmaking process were eager and pleased to work together, confirming there is a vast, largely untapped potential for this type of Una Europa-led research collaboration.
- In the Horizon Europe Pillar II matchmaking process, the Una Europa External funding offices and the RCC should support the following: 1) identification of the topics and coordinators; 2) collection of the Eols; 3) matchmaking workshops; and 4) general information sessions about the funding instrument. The proposal writing support, including grant writer resources and potential travel funds, should be provided by the coordinating university. This must be communicated clearly.
- Due to the Una.Resin project, the One Health self-steering committee meeting and the Una Europa general assembly schedules, the Pillar II matchmaking process started too late leaving little time between the two workshops and for the identification of the coordinators. In the future, time between the different phases of the process needs to be built into the schedule. However, the consolidation of research cooperation in Focus Areas and increased awareness of the Alliance among the academic community should also contribute to the readiness to prepare joint applications.
- Organising this kind of workshop is time intensive and requires an understanding of local contexts and networks. The process and the tools are not enough, with skilled facilitators and systematic communication also being key for success. It is important to make sure that the universities appoint working time of the RCC members and other relevant professionals for the facilitation of such workshops and processes.
- The co-creation concept, futures approach, and online workshops are new to many academics. As an example, the workshop started with a discussion instead of passive listening to encourage the participants to become active owners of the workshop rather than passive followers. This format can be initially confusing to participants, who tend to be more familiar with others setting the agenda and the tone of workshops. Despite initial discomfort, participants were willing to collaborate from the outset and build ideas together. Una Europa should pay attention to innovative pedagogies in the future, even

if it is not always the most familiar or common way to run a workshop.

Recommendations for the future

The pilot offers a number of recommendations giving direction to future activity:

- There is a need for an online platform allowing interactive collection of Eols. Una Europa could use an existing platform in the short term and, in the longer term, European platforms could be developed. In the short term, Una Europa should also share links to the research portals of each partner university. In the longer term, Una Europa could develop a way to harvest existing data from the research portals to support matchmaking.
- The universities should consider designing and facilitating collaborative workshops, both online and in-person. This could constitute a special skill for the research professionals and would require specific training.
- Una Europa must pay more attention to matching the SSH and STEM fields and foster interdisciplinary collaboration. Communication with participants illustrated how the community believe more can be done in this arena and Una Europa have a role to play in fostering a collaborative mindset across the Alliance.
- Una Europa should consider ways to fund mobility to advance consortium building. The current situation, where some universities and some fields have funding and others do not, creates inequality and is a barrier to excellence.
- Una Europa should put special emphasis on developing ways to involve non-academic collaborators to the consortium at an institutional level.

Pilot Evaluation 2: Developing a concept for a Una Europa collaboration platform

Objectives and aims of the pilot project

Una.Resin WP1 was first tasked to pilot methods to accelerate cross-disciplinary and cross-sectoral collaboration and networking with the aim of addressing the priority global challenges, with this pilot action focused on developing a concept for an Una Europa collaboration platform. The platform was envisioned to consist of an evolving set of tools and services for cross-disciplinary and cross-sectoral collaboration and networking within the Una Europa ecosystem and throughout the R&I lifecycle, with a specific focus on fostering collaboration and networking that was responsive to the priority global challenges. The main ideas for a joint collaborative platform included these tasks:

- Increase the visibility and fields of expertise of the Una Europa researchers;
- Allow for matchmaking and collaboration to create high-quality consortia for acquiring competitive funding;
- Allow for matchmaking for early-career researcher for joint projects;
- Allow for joint international doctoral training modules to be stored and processed;
- Allow the search for specific profiles and keywords, and the posting of calls of interest, in particular in the interest of early-career researchers; and
- Allow for collaboration beyond the sphere of academia, e.g., in citizen science projects.

The primary aim for the pilot was to establish a digitally enhanced one-stop-shop or efficient

combination of modules for fostering research collaboration within the Alliance. This resource could offer support in identifying relevant funding opportunities, advancing research initiatives, and facilitating innovation within the shared Una Europa ecosystem. The overall aim of Una.Resin has been to lay the groundwork for the development of the common Una Europa R&I ecosystem. As a part of this, this pilot has sought to develop a collaborative tool for advancing cooperation in R&I within the universities and beyond the sphere of academia.

The approach to develop the pilot was comprehensive and linked to all seven transformation modules but acutely addressed the following modules: (2) strengthen human capital; (3) share research infrastructures; (4) engage non-academic actors; and (7) explore joint university structures.

Initial design and implementation of the pilot project

Consultations and Workshops

The potential needs and requirements of a collaboration platform were discussed in regular meetings and in two dedicated workshop sessions, namely:

- Workshops in connection to RCC meetings: 13/12/2021 (online), 14/02/2022 (online), 17/03/2022 in Paris, 02/06/2022 in Helsinki, 29/11/2022 in Edinburgh, 08/06/2023 in Leiden.
- Workshop with the One Health Focus area self-steering committee in Bertinoro in February 2022.
- PPTSC workshop at the Freie Universität Berlin, 04-06/04/2022.
- Strategic discussions with the chairs of the Una Europa self-steering committee in February 2023.
- Pilot Evaluation 1: Una Europa R&I strategy workshop and the Horizon Europe Pillar II matchmaking process.

The Una Europa RCC, in close collaboration with WP1, played a major role supporting the development of the internal processes and sharing best practices from their home institutions. The RCC members helped to identify the processes and the potential user groups. Their input was of great value with regards to the technical and administrative feasibility of the whole pilot. They also served as contact points for engaging academics, as well as research funding professionals. The One Health self-steering committee was a main point of contact for this pilot.

Further input was gained via a questionnaire circulated among all the Una.Resin WPs and clusters. The following key questions were posed:

- Based on the Una.Resin outcomes, what communication needs did you identify? What support for matchmaking is needed?
- What are the main tasks an Una Europa communication platform would need to fulfil from your WP/Cluster's perspective?
- What are the main support needs for communication and matchmaking from the Una Europa vzw?

From this questionnaire, the main desires and needs of a collaborative platform could be distilled.

Mapping

In the consultations with the academic community, they stressed the need to have access to information about the research areas and experiences of other Una Europa colleagues. A mapping exercise of existing research portals at the 11 partner institutions was carried out that, as a first step, could be shared on the Una Europa joint platform/homepage. At a later stage, this could serve as the basis for a joint portal that researchers could use to connect with suitable colleagues for matchmaking purposes or joint applications.

The pilot also aimed to map commercial platforms that could fit the needs expressed below. During the project lifecycle, Una Futura was launched as the second phase of funding for Una Europa under the umbrella of Erasmus+. As part of Una.Futura, Una Europa vzw was tasked to design and develop a comprehensive platform, “Una.Connect”. Existing commercial platforms should be further explored during the conceptualisation Una.Connect as examples of best practices or simply for use in their existing form.

Challenges and solutions

Shortly after the initiation of the project it was apparent that a universal platform, which incorporates a whole range of tools, would need to be developed and implemented. The design and implementation, understood as two separate tasks to be performed in the lifetime of one pilot, soon proved to be unfeasible from the viewpoint of human and financial resources. It was assumed that there would already be active research collaboration wherein the platform could be piloted during the lifetime of Una.Resin, however this assumption turned out to be incorrect. Thus, it was decided that the limited resources dedicated to the pilot would be focused on understanding the needs and expectations of a collaborative platform and drafting a concept for such a platform.

Outcomes and impact of the pilot project

The key findings regarding the desired functionalities for such a platform are listed below.

Research funding portal

Target group: Academics and research funding professionals

Aims: Sharing information about research funding opportunities and matchmaking for calls

Features needed:

- Joint pool of funding opportunities.
- European funding opportunities.
- National and regional funding opportunities.
- Institutional funding opportunities.
- Platform for researchers' matchmaking for joint applications.
- Collection of interest of researchers at the EoI phase.
- Creation of a repository of relevant information about funding opportunities on a national and European level (e.g., documents, training sessions on how to apply, taking the Horizon call preparatory sessions as an example, etc.).
- Facilitation of interaction between participants (e.g., via a chat functionality).

Who should maintain/operate:

- A commercial platform could be used.
- Research professionals, identified by RCC members, at each university.
- Senior External Funding Advisor at vzw.

- IT-professional(s) at vzw or partner universities.

Strategic goals addressed:

- Supporting Bottom-Up Initiatives.
- Promoting Mobility and Community Building.
- Training Researchers of the Future.
- Digitalising Collaboration.
- Establishing Interdisciplinary Hubs.

Existing commercial products: To be mapped.

Short, middle and long-term goals:

A number of development stages would be required to satisfy all the expressed desired functionalities, although easy workarounds could be used on a short-term perspective that could be then scaled for some functionalities. It is important to note that the tools do not necessarily have to be on the same platform for them to work. At least in the initial stage of this process, Una Europa could use adaptable platforms, like B2B (for more see below). The functions need to be user-friendly and easily found. A feasible process could start with implementing tools that address only specific tasks in the beginning that can then be combined with other functionalities at a later date and if technically possible. This would allow for the process to start rather than waiting until a highly complex digital architecture, which encompasses all desired functionalities, is developed.

A first step, for example, could be to establish a tool for research funding matchmaking, collection of Eols, systematic announcements of international calls, major national and regional funding formats, and institutional funding opportunities. In a long-term perspective, scientists could use the envisaged platform to start discussing collaborations and elaborate on projects. An overview of the research conducted within the funding and organisational framework of Una Europa, as well as the researchers conducting this research, would provide a good opportunity to showcase the thematic Focus Areas within the respective partner institutions, within Una Europa, and beyond academia. Thus, a platform of this kind could also give ample visibility to the Alliance and enable Una Europa to better serve society as a whole, especially by facilitating industrial contacts. External partners would also be able to scout projects that are of interest to them, contact scientists and start matchmaking autonomously.

Developing careers and skills

Target group: Academics and higher education staff

Aims:

- Sharing academic and professional positions available at the partner institutions.
- Training on transversal skills (e.g., interdisciplinary research, open research and research data management, particularities of the academic funding landscape and careers at the partner universities/countries).

Features needed:

- Ability to share and store webinar videos and/or presentations.
- Ability to register for workshop participants.

Who should maintain/operate:

- Ideally the Una Europa vzw would maintain the platform and the features could potentially be added to the Una.Connect platform.
- Research professionals at each university would produce the content as part of the

ongoing initiatives/projects. If other professionals would be needed, they could be identified by RCC or other cluster members.

- IT-support professional(s).

Strategic goals addressed:

- Strengthening Collaboration Beyond Academia.
- Supporting Bottom-Up Initiatives.
- Promoting Mobility and Community Building.
- Digitalising Collaboration.

Existing commercial products: To be mapped.

Short, middle and long-term goals:

In the short term, a list with links to the job announcement platforms of individual universities could suffice. For skills training, a page with announcements of future events is a short-term goal. In the middle to long-term perspective, job announcements could be harvested from individual universities' portals and placed on the Una Europa platform to provide an enhanced overview. Regarding the skills training, storing of webinar recordings would be short term goal, with a function to register for announced webinars being a longer-term goal.

Research Portal (Research Information System)

Target group: Academics and higher education staff.

Aims:

- Sharing information on researcher's profiles, publications, patents as well as research results.
- Facilitate matchmaking between researchers for potential cooperation.

Features needed:

- Interoperability of existing research portals of individual universities.
- Harvest data from existing portals.
- Key words search and other search filters (e.g., disciplines).

Who should maintain/operate:

- IT-professionals appointed to coordinate and build the system supported by IT staff at each university, if needed. Academics should not have to manually update data, rather data should be automatically updated

Strategic goals addressed:

- Establishing Interdisciplinary Hubs.
- Training Researchers of the Future.
- Strengthening Collaboration Beyond Academia.
- Supporting Bottom-Up Initiatives.
- Promoting Mobility and Community Building.
- Digitalising Collaboration.
- Promoting openness of RIs and data infrastructures to foster research collaboration.
- Strengthening Research and Data Infrastructure Skills.
- Developing a stronger and more integrated Una Europa Research Infrastructure Ecosystem.

Existing research portals at Una Europa Partner universities:

- UEDIN: [University of Edinburgh Research Explorer](#)
- UH: [University of Helsinki Research Portal](#)

- UNIBO: Directories
- UP1: Pages Personnelles Enseignants Chercheurs and Expert Finder System (beta version)
- JU: Staff search engine
- KU Leuven: a research portal with funded projects and information on research infrastructures; a Publication repository (LIRIAS) with all publication output of KU Leuven researchers; an institutional research data repository (RDR) for the publication of research data; KU Leuven Who-is-who
- FUB: no RIS in place yet, considerations to use VIVO; research data base with research projects, FUB's academic Departments and Central Institutes
- UCM: Portal de la Investigation
- UCD: Research Portal
- UZ: no RIS in place yet.
- UL: Universiteit Leiden's Academic Staff

Existing commercial products: SciVal, SciVal Experts, Pure, Research in View, Converis, Symplectic Elements, VIVO.

Short, middle and long-term goals:

At the beginning, links to the research portals (research information systems) of individual universities could be listed on the platform (Una.Connect or Una Europa Web Pages). Research information systems are already in place in most of the Una Europa universities. For the universities that still do not have such a portal, this could be a good opportunity to both align their needs with the process of developing a platform early on and as an additional resource to create the best possible environment for their academic community. At a later stage, Una Europa could develop ways to harvest data from the individual research information systems, incorporate it in its platform, and ensure its synchronisation and interoperability. The Una Europa platform's data set could commence by harvesting the profiles of researchers and then expand to include publications, patents, and research results. Initial discussion on the possibility to create such functionality started with KU Leuven and University of Edinburgh, where such functions have been developed in-house.

Sharing information on RIRs

Target group: Academic and higher education staff.

Aims:

- Sharing information on RIRs at the partner institutions.
- Giving access to scientists from partner universities.
- Connect the academic community and facilitate interdisciplinary research cooperation.

Features needed:

- Searching tools for connected RIRs and harvesting data from existing catalogues on RIRs at the partner institutions.
- Sharing of instructive webinars on how to use RIRs.
- Information on events, projects, networking opportunities, and funding opportunities for the RIRs.
- Storage of relevant documents, papers and books regarding the RIRs.
- Matchmaking between RIRs (see above).
- Presentation of best practices to the interested public.

- Newsletter on recently added RIR, upcoming webinars, etc.
- Entry point to the RIR.

Who should maintain/operate:

- Research professionals at each university.
- IT professionals.

Strategic goals addressed:

- Establishing Interdisciplinary Hubs.
- Training Researchers of the Future.
- Strengthening Collaboration Beyond Academia.
- Supporting Bottom-Up Initiatives.
- Promoting Mobility and Community Building.
- Digitalising Collaboration.
- Strengthening Research and Data Infrastructure Skills.

Existing commercial products: Hevo Data, GigaSpaces, Airbyte, Snowflake's Unistore, Stitch.

Short, middle and long-term goals:

The first short-term goal would be to establish an Una Europa digital catalogue (operational data store) of the RIR by harvesting data from the existing sources, including setting up a searching tool. The dedicated Una Europa platform could then successively add information on events, projects, networking, and funding opportunities related to the RIR. In the medium term, the collaboration requires data infrastructures. The long-term perspective is for the platform to be the central place for accessing the shared RIRs in Una Europa. Funding opportunities at the European level would be useful to develop data sharing tools and identify legal barriers. A matchmaking between RIRs could be part of a broader matchmaking page for Una Europa researchers, where they can express interest and needs and post information and opportunities. Ideally, Una Europa should develop a systematic way to link the infrastructures to research funding matchmaking.

Enhancing citizen science in research

Target group: Academics, higher education staff, citizens.

Aim:

- Presentation and communication of research projects to the general public.
- Project incubator as an open forum to suggest projects and engage with citizens.
- Matchmaking between researchers for joint citizen science projects.
- Matchmaking between researchers and/or research support staff for exchanging experience and best practice.

Features needed:

- Presentation of citizen engagement projects.
- Portal for matchmaking and expression of interest for joint projects.
- Online training.
- Storage of workshop recordings.

Who should maintain/operate:

- Research professionals at each university for specified research areas.
- IT professionals.

Strategic goals addressed:

- Establishing Interdisciplinary Hubs.

- Training Researchers of the Future.
- Strengthening Collaboration Beyond Academia.
- Supporting Bottom-Up Initiatives.
- Promoting Mobility and Community Building.
- Digitalising Collaboration.
- Promoting openness of RIs and data infrastructures to foster research collaboration.
- Strengthening Research and Data Infrastructure Skills.
- Developing a stronger and more integrated Una Europa Research Infrastructure Ecosystem.

Existing commercial products: See above.

Short, middle and long-term goals:

The first step to allow for a more concentrated approach would be to establish easy and efficient ways of communication and matchmaking between Una Europa researchers interested in citizen science, as well as between researchers and citizens. To this end, links to existing data bases with citizen science projects at individual universities could be gathered on the Una Europa Platform. In the medium term, a search for researchers doing projects on citizen science, or researchers interested in them should be possible on the Una Europa research information system via a label or hashtag system that could be added to researchers/projects profile. A search engine should be able to provide a specific search for such labels/hashtags. Similarly, the Una Europa platform dedicated to research funding opportunities should contain information on calls relevant to citizen science, which will require developing an associated filter. Alternatively, citizen science projects can have a separate page and be curated by research teams.

Sustainability of the pilot project

In the short term, the sustainability of the project may be best achieved by adapting commercial platforms, as developing a platform with all the desired functionality will require a highly complex digital architecture. There are skills and knowledge on harvesting data within our partner universities, e.g., at KU Leuven and at the University of Edinburgh, and Una Europa should take advantage of these existing skills.

Una.Resin WP1 has been in contact with Una Europa vzw about the pilot findings, which will feed into the process of designing an Una.Connect collaborative platform. Although a preliminary mapping of commercial platforms has already revealed some potential costs, there is need to carry out a cost analysis to inform the next stage of activity and to determine the value of further work. A considerable amount of additional funding will undoubtedly be required to develop a holistic, Alliance-wide platform that satisfies the needs of project management, communication within the Alliance, data storage, and the specific desires identified by researchers in this pilot.

Lessons learnt

Considerable resource is required to conceive, develop, and implement a collaborative platform and, due to not having the financial or human resource required, the development and testing of tools at a large scale could not be carried out. However, a number of important lessons were still learnt. The most important outcome from the stakeholder consultations was that the platform should be simple, intuitive, and easy to use. All given information needs to

be visible and transparent. For a collaborative platform to be an efficient tool for researchers and external partners, it needs to facilitate their work and not add more complexity to their daily tasks. This is a challenge for an Alliance that has a number of different projects, each with their own tasks, functions, and rationale. Even if Una Europa aimed not to use just one platform but to collect features from different sources, every aspect has to be clearly communicated on the Una Europa website to guarantee easy access and to avoid the current situation where multiple landing pages and platforms are simultaneously in use at the same time.

Recommendations for the future

To ensure that the needs of the researchers are heard, Una.Resin is working closely with Una Europa vzw to make sure that the insights from this pilot are used in the process of conceptualising a broader Una Europa platform. WP1 members have participated in the stakeholder consultations for the design of the Una.Connect platform, where preliminary results of this mapping have already been discussed. WP1 will continue to provide feedback on the proposed platform. This pilot evaluation will also be used in the process of developing the Una.Connet platform and to give direction to future research collaborations within Una Europa, but also possibly within other university consortia of similar size and aspiration. For a platform to function in the long run, it would be necessary to guarantee ample funding for the findings to be put to use.

Pilot Evaluation 3: Blueprint for a common catalogue of research infrastructures

Objectives and Aims of the pilot

The aim of this pilot action was to undertake the first steps towards developing a Una Europa digital catalogue of research infrastructures and a portal of services. The project, thus, sought to develop a platform that provided a unified system for managing research infrastructure data, enabling institutions to easily share information and collaborate on research activities. There is a need, as expressed by stakeholders, to share information and knowledge on research infrastructures and resources available in the Una Europa universities. This sharing is regarded as a prerequisite for facilitating cross-institutional access and R&I collaborations and is the rationale behind the pilot concept. The transformation module this pilot project aimed to address is “Sharing Infrastructure and Resources”. Considering the potential benefit of a common catalogue of RIs to promote Open Science principles in RIs operations and activities, the pilot also indirectly contributed to the “Comprehensive mainstreaming of Open Science practices” module.

The barriers to cross-border and cross-sectoral R&I collaboration addressed by the pilot project are the following:

- The lack of mutual and up to date information on available RIs and resources. Information on the knowledge of assets, expertise, and services related to RIs is also lacking, as is an understanding of the resources available in each Una Europa university for the different disciplines. The mapping exercises carried out in the first phase of Una.Resin activity illustrated how this information needs regularly updating, and collating and updating such data is resource and time intensive.

- The lack of a unified access point for information on Una Europa RIs that can ease cross-institutional access to infrastructures.
- The lack of knowledge of Una Europa infrastructures for external users, including universities but also non-academic actors and civil society.

This pilot aims to foster Open Science and open access to scientific results and data (e.g., online open notebooks, Open Educational Resources (OERs), open data, etc.), whilst also encouraging an opening and sharing of RIs. In doing so, the pilot seeks to support a desired institutional change towards opening and sharing. To support the achievement of this change, the intended audiences of the pilot project are:

- In the short term: Universities in general, research performing organisation, researchers, and professional staff of RIs.
- In the medium/long term: Universities in general, research performing organisations, researchers, businesses and industry engaging in R&D, citizens, NGOs, and professional staff of RIs.

The beneficiaries of the pilot are as follows:

- In the short term: Researchers, RI managers, and funding officers.
- In the medium/long term: Researchers, teaching staff and students, RI managers and experts, funding and policy officers, external users (academic and non-academic), citizens, other universities, and European University Alliances.

This pilot did not draw from any other pilots. The cooperation with the pilot action “Business-Academia Cooperation”, led by UCM, is however worth underlining; among the possible services that could be added to the prospective Una Europa catalogue and portal of RIs, there could be the link to a platform/catalogue of research teams from Una Europa universities and their transferable research results.

Initial Design and Implementation of the pilot project

The format of the pilot was initially devised during the first phase of Una.Resin activity. In this initial phase, WP2 activities focused on a threefold mapping exercise: 1) benchmarking Una Europa universities’ RIs strategies, policies, initiatives, as well as organisational and funding models; 2) mapping of the RIs related to the challenge “exploring cultural heritage to strengthen inclusion and participative communities”; and 3) mapping of the RIs related to the challenge “promoting the wellbeing of human and animals in a sustainable and healthy environment”. This task was followed by the organisation of a co-creation workshop aimed at collecting ideas and inputs from the academic and professional community to develop a shared Una Europa strategy for sharing RIRs (D2.2), and to design and plan the WP2 pilot actions.

One of the key inputs emerging from the mapping exercise, which was further discussed during the co-creation workshop, was the need to know the RIRs available in the Una Europa universities. Having an understanding of the available RIRs is a prerequisite to collaborate on RIs, especially if we consider that Una Europa institutions are largely comprehensive universities, which makes it difficult to have a complete and up to date overview of the infrastructures and expertise available. Mapping exercises take a lot of time and effort and require a constant update vis-à-vis the changing landscape of infrastructures and resources in universities and are therefore not the optimal instrument to give an up-to-date overview of

available RIs at our universities. WP2, thus, devised a pilot to undertake the first steps towards developing common digital tools to share information and knowledge related to RIs and ease cross-institutional access, i.e., the development of a preliminary blueprint that can lay the basis for the creation of a common digital catalogue of RIs and a prospective portal of services.

A working group of IT experts of Una Europa institutions was created to undertake this pilot project. From across the eight Una Europa universities, 14 participants from eight Una Europa universities were involved and four discussion meetings were organised, including a specific seminar to share best practices on RIs catalogues. The seminar also involved guest experts from the Flemish department Science, Economy and Innovation, who designed the Flanders Research Information Space. The output from this process was the creation of a blueprint (see Annex 1) that provides guidelines for the development of an information technology platform to manage a common catalogue of RIs across the Una Europa institutions. This platform aims to provide a unified system for managing RI data, enabling institutions to easily share information and collaborate on research activities.

The blueprint includes the following contents: 1) catalogues of infrastructures available in the Una Europa universities; 2) best practices; 3) lessons learnt from the prototype that was created to show the potentialities of a common catalogue; 4) recommendations for a future shared catalogue (architecture, system, taxonomy); 5) guidelines to develop a new catalogue of infrastructures at institutional level; 6) a service portal for Una Europa infrastructures as a future improvement; and 7) next steps.

From a technical point of view, the proposed approach to the catalogue is based on harvesting the existing information in university databases on Una Europa RIs. Starting from the information available at the institutional level, the catalogue envisages an automatic system to collect and display the existing data in a single place (web platform). The rationale of this methodology is the need to reduce the level of effort for the production and maintenance of the catalogue. The document represents the outcome of the preliminary discussion carried out in the framework of Una.Resin that, in the medium-long term, could lead the Alliance to a common digital catalogue of RIs and, by extension, a portal of services.

Implementation of the pilot included the collection of data on the RIs catalogues available (if any) at institutional level, so as to have an exhaustive view on the existing tools and approaches across different universities. The data collected for this purpose were the following:

- Name of the digital catalogue tool of RIRs;
- Web resource/web site URL;
- Management software, portal, data base or excel/access file where the information is stored;
- Type of interoperability interface available to share the information outside the university (or instance Web APIs, JSON, CSV and flat file download); and
- Notes.

Further data (although limited) was collected to develop a prototype as a concrete example of an RIs catalogue. This allowed participants to provide input to the blueprint on the definition of a data model, as well as on the rules to ensure data quality. The data collected (through an

excel file) for this purpose was as follows:

- ID: RI unique identifier in the local catalogue (mandatory);
- Host Institution: the host institution name (mandatory);
- Name: The short name of the RI (mandatory);
- Type: Equipment/Laboratory (mandatory);
- Description: RI description (mandatory);
- Location: Address, building, room where the RI is located (mandatory);
- Contact name and contact email address (mandatory);
- Acquisition year (optional);
- Free keywords (optional);
- Open access (Y/N) (optional);
- Services provided (Y/N) (optional); and
- Web site URL (optional).

The “seminar on research infrastructures catalogue: best practices”, held on the 21st of March 2023, allowed for more in-depth analysis and discussion of the experiences of UH and FUB, alongside the FRIS experience of collecting publicly-funded research information in Flanders. This specific seminar and the discussion meetings succeeded in bringing together stakeholders to start reflecting on a possible path towards a common catalogue of infrastructures, taking into consideration best practices and assessing costs and benefits.

The pilot action was planned and carried out with the contribution of the RI cluster members. The cluster members cooperated in defining the format and methodology and, in the implementation phase, consulted and involved their respective IT experts. The pilot action was then implemented via four meetings aimed to: 1) start a discussion about the common catalogue, 2) discuss the prototype, 3) explore the best practices of the catalogues available, and 4) finalise and validate the blueprint. Considering that the main focus was on technical aspects, the self-steering committees were not directly involved in this pilot action, but a prospective catalogue and portal of services will be beneficial for all Focus Areas.

The differences across the Una Europa universities in terms of RIs catalogues were a challenge in the discussions among the IT experts. Therefore, the first step was to collect data on institutional catalogues to gain an understanding of differences. The presence of universities at different stages of catalogue development, allowed experts to discuss possible common strategies within the Alliance and to think about technical solutions that could guarantee the maximum level of interoperability of each institution’s catalogue, observing what is already up and running and guiding what has to be developed. In this regard, it is important to note that UNIBO, UJ, and UP1 have not yet developed an RIs catalogue. To address this point and make the action useful for all Una Europa institutions, the blueprint includes a chapter that offers recommendations for developing an institutional catalogue.

Different participants have different perceptions of the added value that would be gained from developing a RIs catalogue at the Alliance level. The development of a prototype was crucial to show the potential benefits of a common tool for sharing information about RIs that avoids both the duplication of work and increased human and financial resource. The opportunity to share best practices (including the case of FRIS) was highly appreciated by participants and further highlighted the added value of a common catalogue. An assessment of the added

value, along with a cost-benefits analysis, needs to be taken forward if the institutional decision-makers are to endorse the continuation of this action. In this regard, it is key to continue the exchange of knowledge and best practices among experts, considering the differences across the Una Europa universities and taking into account the experiences of other universities and alliances.

Another challenge was related to the resources available in Una.Resin. Limited resources allowed for only the first step (the Blueprint) towards the medium-long term development of a common catalogue of RIs, thus raising awareness about the potential benefits and criticalities of this path. In order to see an advancement towards this goal, it is crucial to have dedicated resources.

Outcomes and Impact of the pilot project

The main outcomes of the pilot can be summarised as follows:

- Creation of a working group of RIs and IT experts who have shared information and best practices, and who have taken the first steps towards the development of a common RIs catalogue at the Alliance level. The working group has finalised a blueprint that provides concrete recommendations to guide next steps.
- The blueprint was disseminated among the Una Europa community (for example, at the Una Europa event in Leiden, June 2023 and at the final event) and external stakeholders (at the final event in Brussels, November 2023), including other European universities alliances (for example, at the joint event of the SwafS projects of the alliances on the 30th of November and the 1st of December 2023). This will allow for connection and knowledge exchange with other universities and other projects working on common catalogues. For example, the Una.Resin WP2 team met the [aUPaEU project](#) team to discuss respective approaches to the development of a common catalogue. The synergy with this project creates opportunities for exchanging knowledge and experiences on RIs.
- It is also important to mention that universities that have not yet developed a catalogue have had the opportunity to get acquainted with the systems already in use at other universities, whilst also benefiting from the specific recommendations included in Chapter 5 of the blueprint “guidelines to develop a new catalogue of infrastructures at institutional level”.

The key medium-long term impacts are related to the concrete development of a Una Europa common RIs catalogue and portal of services (e.g., booking, training). This development will, first of all, increase awareness among of the academic and professional community about the RIs available across the Una Europa universities and facilitate access to them. This will foster R&I cooperation and an efficient use of RIs, with a positive impact on their financial sustainability. Moreover, RIs among non-academic public, private, and third sector users will be promoted, as well as their use among citizens. A common catalogue and portal of services will also contribute to the promotion of Open Science principles in RIs operation and activities. Together, these expected impacts have the potential to induce a significant institutional change towards opening and sharing RIRs across the Alliance.

The pilot project has successfully achieved its stated goals and laid the basis for promoting a barrier-free collaboration in R&I. As previously mentioned, Una.Resin has undertaken only the

first steps of a longer and more articulated path that will lead towards the development of common tools (catalogue and portal of services) for sharing information on RIs. These tools can greatly benefit the academic and professional community and contribute to igniting new collaborations in R&I and education by facilitating the visibility of RIs and related expertise (within and beyond the Alliance), as well as cross-institutional access to RIs.

It is important to mention that there is a crucial synergy with the WP2 pilot action “match-making formats to improve the Una Europa research infrastructures sharing”, since the collaborative RI activities could be strongly supported and enhanced by the tools for sharing information on RIs. In general, all stakeholders involved in WP2 activities – including the One Health and Cultural Heritage self-steering committees – emphasised that having an updated landscape of the available assets and expertise is crucial to initiating collaboration. In both WP2 pilots, RIs are considered not solely a support system but also as a driving force behind research activities – a veritable “catalyser” of new ideas and scientific collaborations able to create a strong added value in R&I within the Alliance.

The outcomes of the discussions among experts and of the best practice sharing seminar are synthesised in the blueprint, an initial document that provides concrete recommendations aimed at different stakeholders. For example, the recommendations for a future common catalogue in terms of architecture, system, and taxonomy will interest IT experts of the Una Europa universities, while the next steps listed in Chapter 7 are important for institutional decision-makers. Chapter 6, on the portal of services delineating a scenario with prospective opportunities, will appeal to the academic and professional community. The structure of the document makes it easy for different stakeholders to access the recommendations relevant to their interest. In general, the document is also a good basis for exchanging knowledge with other alliances (or projects).

The outcomes of this pilot project informed the Una Europa Strategy and Action Plan for Sharing Research Infrastructures and Resources (Una.Resin Deliverable 2.2), where the need to develop common tools to share information and knowledge on RIs is underlined. The recommendations of D2.2 were shared with the institutional decision-makers of the Una Europa universities: the Board of Directors and Research Strategy Group approved the project deliverables and recognised the importance of the Una.Resin strategies. In particular, the R&I Strategy (Una.Resin Deliverable 1.2) and the Strategy and Action Plan for Sharing RIRs (Una.Resin Deliverable 2.2) informed the Una Europa Vision on the transversal theme of R&I in the Una.Futura project.

In parallel, a two-phase survey was launched within the Alliance to prioritise R&I actions and allocate resources for implementation. In this framework, institutional decision makers are evaluating the possibility of taking forward the pilot action related to the Blueprint for a common catalogue of RIs, starting from the creation of an advanced version of the Blueprint developed in Una.Resin. In the future, the outcomes of this pilot action could influence decision-makers at European level who are seeking to facilitate efforts of the alliances to build common catalogues of RIs, as an important tool to foster sharing and the opening of infrastructures and to strengthen the connection and integration of RIs in the alliances. For example, the EC could allocate dedicated funding or at least actively facilitate the exchange of experiences and best practices, as well as provide some form of coordination. This would be extremely beneficial

because many alliances are proceeding separately with different approaches.

Sustainability of the pilot project

At this stage, it is still not precisely defined how and when the insights and outcomes delivered through the pilot project will be continued. In relation to a possible continuation of the Blueprint pilot, it is important to consider that this action is part of the “Una Europa Strategy and action plan on sharing RIRs” (Una.Resin Deliverable 2.2). In this document, the proposed action, named “Development of tools to share information and knowledge related to RIs” (see Una.Resin Deliverable 2.2, Pillar 1 - Action 4), is focused on the creation of an advanced version of the blueprint towards the development of a common RIs digital catalogue and, in the long run, a common portal including RIs and services. The priorities and actions on research and data infrastructures proposed in the Una.Resin Deliverable 2.2 have informed the Una Europa R&I vision and are now being assessed to inform prioritisation by the governing Alliance members.

More specifically, a prioritisation exercise at the highest decision-making levels of the Alliance has been initiated in relation to potential future activities in the area of R&I. This exercise is based on a matrix of potential actions, including the priorities on infrastructures proposed in the Una.Resin Deliverable 2.2, which will be ranked through a survey. This exercise will also define the preferred level of ambition and resources that would be allocated for the prioritised actions. The outcomes of this exercise will inform the development of a common R&I Action Plan for the Alliance. This plan will be discussed by the Board of Directors and Research Strategy Group and, based on a clear agreement on the prioritised actions and resources to be committed, actions will either be implemented with institutional resources, or with institutional resources focused on attracting external funding.

The blueprint developed in Una.Resin is a preliminary step and, in order to scale up this pilot, it will be crucial that each institution recognises the added value of the action and decides to allocate adequate human and financial resources. An EC funding call to further develop this action would be needed, as well as concrete support to facilitate the exchange of knowledge across different European universities Alliances.

In terms of cost-benefit analysis, it is important to consider that engaging experts from different universities requires time and resources. Considering the differences in existing tools and approaches across the Una Europa universities, it was challenging to start working on a common vision and deliver preliminary recommendations. Producing an advanced version of the blueprint would require a clear commitment from all institutions involved. A careful assessment of the resources and cost implications related to the development, maintenance, and management of a shared RIs catalogue would also be required, taking into consideration the cost for catalogue and platform creation, continuous updating, promotion of the catalogue, and training and assistance to users. Also, potential financial risks should be assessed such as decreased funding, increased maintenance costs, or loss of team members.

Continuing to advance the blueprint could substantially accelerate the institutional transformation towards sharing RIs and, in general, foster collaboration in R&I and education across the Alliance. The benefits of this continued advancement can be summarised as follows:

- Increased awareness of the academic community about the RIs available across the Una Europa universities and facilitate access.
- Promote collaboration around RIs that can stimulate new collaborative research projects as well as an efficient use of RIs.
- Connect RIs and promote Open Science principles in their operation and activities.
- Promote RIs among possible non-academic public, private, and third-sector users and also towards citizens.
- Improve the economic sustainability of the infrastructure.

Lessons learnt

A series of lessons have been identified from designing and implementing this pilot:

- It is crucial to share best practices, knowledge and experiences, not only within the Alliance but also taking into consideration the approaches of other alliances and projects (e.g., aUPaEu project). What is more, the EC should have a role in facilitating this process.
- Adopting a methodology (e.g., based on the harvesting of information on RIs available at institutional level) that avoids increasing or duplicating the effort required to create and maintain of a common catalogue of RIs is key. It is also important to consider the interoperability with (and among) existing catalogues.
- The creation of a common catalogue of RIs needs to be harmonised with (and become part of) the broader knowledge information systems at institutional level, and will require engaging different professionals from different divisions within universities (in particular, RI and IT experts). Having the clear commitment of institutional decision-makers (based on a clear perception of the added value) is key to proceed towards the creation of a common catalogue and portal of services.
- The assessment of costs and the need for dedicated personnel for the creation and maintenance of a common catalogue/portal is a crucial step, together with the definition of an effective management model with clear roles and responsibilities.
- It is important to consider other existing ecosystems and partnerships of the universities at the local and national level (for example, FUB is part of Berlin University Alliance), since this may impact their desire to have another catalogue of RIs shared with Una Europa partners.

Recommendations for the future

To set up the common RIs catalogue, Una Europa should ensure the following steps:

- The development of a clear commitment from the governing Alliance members thereby guaranteeing the long-term engagement of the individual institutions to work together on the development of a common catalogue of RIs, based on an accurate assessment of the resources available at institutional level.
- Continue the exploration of best practices, experiences, and approaches of other alliances and projects to exploit possible synergies, useful tools, and lessons learnt.
- Prepare an advanced version of the blueprint (as suggested in the Una. Resin Deliverable 2.2) that should include:
 - An in-depth SWOT analysis that can help with selecting the architecture, system, and taxonomy to be adopted in the common catalogue.
 - Determining an adequate budget for the development and management of the

- shared RIs catalogue, which considers the costs for catalogue creation, continuous updating, promotion, and training and assistance to users. In this regard, it is important to identify potential financial risks associated with the project, such as decreased funding, increased maintenance costs, or loss of team members. It is necessary to plan how to deal with these risks and find alternative solutions to ensure the financial viability of the project.
- Defining roles and responsibilities of the participating institutions to ensure a balanced distribution of activities and efficient management of available resources across institutions.
 - Identifying efficient processes for the systematic update of RI information through regular data collection.
 - Identification of potential services and functionalities for further development, such as:
 - Link between the RI identifier and publication/data outputs achieved by using the RI, this would also allow for a link to be created between the RI identifier and other infrastructure initiatives at different levels (e.g., European Strategy Forum on RIs-ESFRI, national, regional, institutional levels).
 - Collect the contact information of individuals requesting access to RIs.
 - Link to the registration system (to use the facility) in the RIs digital catalogue.
 - Link to a catalogue where the research teams from the Una Europa universities and their transferable research results would be available online.
 - Technical support that allows researchers to request assistance for the use of RIs and to report technical problems.
 - User training that allows researchers to access guides and useful material on the use of RIs.
 - Notification and alert system.
 - Based on the advanced blueprint, the common catalogue could be created, and further functionalities and services should be developed to achieve an Una Europa shared portal of RIs services.

Pilot Evaluation 4: Matchmaking formats to improve the Una Europa RIR Sharing

Objectives and aims of the pilot

The aim of this pilot action was to experiment with a matchmaking format that brings together representatives of Una Europa RIs (researchers and RIs managers) to discuss possible paths for opening and sharing infrastructures and establishing collaborations in R&I and education. This RI matchmaking exercise was carried out in the thematic fields of Cultural Heritage and One Health, wherein two case studies were defined: Museums and Digital Collections, and Genomics. The pilot project aimed to address the “Sharing Infrastructure and Resources” transformation model. Considering the involvement of data infrastructures and the topics addressed in the workshop discussions, the pilot also indirectly contributed to the “Comprehensive mainstreaming of Open Science practices” transformation module.

The barriers to cross-border and cross-sectoral R&I collaboration addressed by the pilot are the following:

- Lack of mutual knowledge of assets, expertise, and services related to RIRs available in each university of Una Europa and relevant to different disciplinary fields.
- Lack of mutual knowledge on interests and activities, and low awareness of collaboration opportunities in research, education, and innovation connected to the activities of the self-steering committees of Una Europa.
- Lack of opportunities for sharing knowledge, experiences, and practices on topics of common interest, including theme-specific topics (e.g., related to protocols, technologies, etc.), as well as cross-cutting issues such as costing and funding models and Findable-Accessible-Interoperable-Reusable (FAIR) management of data infrastructure.
- Lack of a network and of consistent exchange between the personnel working on RIs (including researchers and RIs managers), with bottom-up participatory processes promoting sharing of knowledge and experiences among RIs representatives being crucial to enable a prospective opening and sharing of RIs across the Alliance.

This pilot aims to foster Open Science and open access to scientific results and data (e.g., online open notebooks, OERs, open data, etc.), whilst also encouraging an opening and sharing of RIs. In doing so, the pilot seeks to support a desired institutional change towards opening and sharing. To support the achievement of this change, the intended audiences of the pilot project are:

- In the short term: Universities in general, research performing organisation, researchers, and professional staff of RIs.
- In the medium/long term: Universities in general, research performing organisations, researchers, research and development businesses and industry, citizens, NGOs, and professional staff of RIs.

The beneficiaries of the pilot are as follows:

- In the short term: Researchers, RI managers, teaching staff, and students.
- In the medium/long term: Researchers, teaching staff and students, RI managers and experts, funding and policy officers, non-academic stakeholders (businesses, cultural organisations, etc.), citizens, other universities, and European University Alliances.

In the design phase, a synergy was sought with the pilot action implemented within WP1 in the field of One Health (i.e., Pilot Evaluation 1 in this document). The One Health self-steering committee suggested that WP2 could test the matchmaking format on the RIs involved in the proposals that were being developed in the framework of the WP1 pilot action. The WP2 team explored the possibility of setting up a matchmaking exercise in connection with a proposal on Cluster 6 of Horizon Europe, related to the theme of Biodiversity and with a view to laying the basis for the creation of an RIs network in this field. However, the discussion among potential partners did not lead to the preparation of a proposal. Therefore, the synergy between the two pilot projects did not materialise. In general, it is worth noting that there are similarities in the underlying concepts of the two pilot actions, notably the importance of “connecting people”, i.e., creating formats and opportunities of matchmaking targeted to the research community of the Alliance to develop projects or other forms of collaborations.

A meaningful synergy was established between the Una.Resin WP2 and the RiTrain Plus project. The joint workshop with RiTrainPlus (Bologna, October 2022) highlighted the importance of collaborating on training programmes that prepare future managers and

operators of European RIs and Core Facilities, and to enable the continued training of those who already hold such positions. Training was one of main needs that emerged during the pilot, and it was discussed by participants from both the Cultural Heritage and One Health field. The collaboration between the Una Europa Focus Areas and RiTrain Plus was also discussed in June 2023 in Leiden and will be taken forward in collaboration with the interested self-steering committees.

Initial design and implementation of the pilot project

One of the key inputs emerging from the mapping exercise initiated at the start of Una.Resin, which was also further discussed during the co-creation workshop, was the need to create communities on RIs. This element is considered in the specific objectives and actions proposed in Pillar 1 “Promoting openness of RIs and data infrastructures to foster research collaboration” of Deliverable 2.2, and became the main objective of the pilot actions that were designed and tested by WP2. WP2 developed a pilot action that addressed the need to creating communities on RIs by connecting (i.e., creating networks of) researchers, RIs managers, and experts across the Alliance to give them the opportunity to get to know each other, share knowledge, interests, ideas and expertise, and initiate collaborations.

The matchmaking exercise among RIs was carried out in the thematic fields of Cultural Heritage and One Health, with the specific case studies, Museums and Digital Collections and Genomics, chosen in collaboration with the Cultural Heritage self-steering committee and the RI Cluster. The matchmaking format thus targeted representatives of RIs in these two thematic fields and brought together academics, managers, and technicians to discuss possible paths for opening and sharing infrastructures and for exploring new collaborations in R&I and education. The need to connecting people is closely linked to the need to develop common tools for sharing information on the RIs available across Una Europa universities, which is the focus of the other WP2 pilot action (Pilot Evaluation 3 in this document).

The first step of the pilot action was defining the scope of each thematic field in agreement with the Cultural Heritage and One Health self-steering committees. Based on the selected scope, the WP2 team identified the relevant RIs that could be involved using the list of infrastructures that participated in the mapping exercise and the participants of the WP2 co-creation workshop as the starting point. These lists were the main data sources used to identify the RIs potentially interested in the pilot action.¹¹ In addition, the Una.Resin Project Managers, the members of the RI Cluster and the Cultural Heritage and One Health self-steering committees were asked to identify further RIs that could be potentially interested in joining the pilot process.

During the implementation of the pilot action, preliminary data was collected from representatives of RIs that expressed interest in participating in the matchmaking workshops. The following data collected (through a google form) in the registration phase:

- Name of the RI represented;
- Short description of the RI;

¹¹ The participation in the pilot action was as follows: for Museums and Digital Collections, 31 researchers/RIs managers from 9 universities (including the University of Zurich and the University of Paris-Nanterre) expressed interest in the pilot representing 27 infrastructures, and 22 RIs were involved in the two workshops; and for Genomics, 17 researchers/RIs managers from 6 universities (including the University of Zurich) expressed interest in the pilot representing 11 infrastructures, and 10 RIs were involved in the two workshops.

- If the infrastructure represented completed a questionnaire as part of the Una.Resin mapping exercise and/or participated in the co-creation workshop held in June 2022;
- If the infrastructure represented is already open (i.e., accessible) to local, national or international partners including external academics but also non-academics;
- If the infrastructure represented already has plans to open and share services at local, national or international level;
- What support (e.g., training, funds, visibility, etc.) is needed to help share and open your infrastructure; and
- What the expectations are in relation to the participation in the workshops.

The data provided by the participants was analysed and presented during the first workshop for both case studies. For the case study “Museums and Digital Collections”, the majority of infrastructures had participated in the Una.Resin mapping exercise and/or in the WP2 co-creation workshop, while this was not the case for the “Genomics” infrastructures. In both case studies, the majority of infrastructures declared their openness to local, national or international partners and that they had plans regarding opening and sharing of services. In terms of needs, funding for training, staff exchange, IT development, collaboration and visibility were all highlighted. Participants expectations for the pilot action were as follows: exchange of best practices and mutual learning, collaboration and networking, joint proposal development, joint research, and visibility. This preliminary data was taken into account in the discussion that took place during the workshops. The outcomes of the workshops were shared with the Cultural Heritage and One Health self-steering committees, with both committees including the objective to continue collaborating with RIs in the Una.Futura framework in their Strategy and Action Plan.

In conclusion, a very inclusive and bottom-up approach was adopted in the process of designing and implementing the pilot action. Collaboration with, and gaining feedback from, stakeholders (self-steering committees, pilot participants, RI Cluster, Una.Resin project managers) was key in all phases of the pilot and led to a positive follow-up of the action itself.

The pilot action carried out in the field of Cultural Heritage was planned and implemented with the substantial contribution of the RI Cluster members and the Cultural Heritage self-steering committee. The methodology was defined in collaboration with the cluster members and they also supported with the workshop preparation. Furthermore, RI Cluster members actively encouraged involvement from RIs within their universities.

The Cultural Heritage self-steering committee defined the scope of the pilot action addressing Museums and Digital collections. The pilot action was then implemented through two workshops aimed at promoting matchmaking, networking, and community building across the Una Europa Museums and Digital collections, with a view to fostering mutual knowledge, exploring collaborations, and developing concrete ways of opening and sharing infrastructures across the Alliance. The chair of the Cultural Heritage self-steering committee was actively involved in the conception and moderation of the two workshops named “Sharing Una Europa infrastructures: Museums and Digital collections” (30th of March and 4th of May 2023). During the first workshop, participants presented their infrastructures and expertise and discussed their mutual interests. In the second workshop participants discussed their interests in relation to the draft action plan developed by the Cultural Heritage self-steering committee in the

framework of the Una.Futura project. Specific relevance was given to the project aimed at creating a Virtual Museum of the heritage of Una Europa universities. The objective to collaborate systematically with the RIs involved in Una.Resin was integrated in the Strategy and Action Plan subsequently developed by the Cultural Heritage self-steering committee.

Regarding the implementation of the pilot action in the field of One Health, the RI Cluster members were involved in the planning phase and supported with defining the methodology, as well as in the preparation and moderation of the workshops. RI Cluster members were inputted into defining the scope of the Genomics pilot action. During the WP2 co-creation workshop, this topic emerged as one of the most interesting in terms of available facilities, expertise, and potential collaborations. The workshops were chaired by the UEDIN representative in the RI Cluster in collaboration with the WP2 team. Even though the One Health self-steering committee did not participate directly in the workshops, the outcomes were shared with the committee and ideas for a possible follow-up were discussed, such as the importance of having a more in-depth understanding of the expertise and strengths of each institution. The Strategy and Action plan developed in the framework of the Una.Futura project referenced the sharing of RIs (such as Genomics core facilities) and providing RIs in the field of One Health with increased visibility to the Una.Resin WP2 pilot format.

During the workshops scenarios for collaborating and opening/sharing RIs were discussed by participants in both fields. The RIs representatives appreciated for the opportunity to meet their colleagues in other universities. However, without any certainties regarding funding, it was challenging to design and plan concrete actions that would guarantee the sustainability of the network and support its collaboration activities. In this regard, it is very positive that the self-steering committees have already expressed their interest both in engaging RIs in their Strategy and Action plan and taking forward some actions (e.g., Virtual Museum of the Una Europa universities heritage) in the framework of the Una.Futura project. However, as highlighted in the Una.Resin Deliverable 2.2, dedicated funding and resource for interconnecting RIs (i.e., for network creation) would be needed to sustain and scale up the piloted matchmaking format. Creating a Una Europa RIs community through networking and matchmaking in thematic areas (also supported by physical mobility) is a prerequisite for concretely sharing and opening RIs. Yet, carrying out bottom-up processes of stakeholders' engagement is resource and time intensive, and there is a that risk these activities will not be systematic and sustainable without dedicated funding.

Another important challenge was related to the difficulty of addressing the complexity of the Una Europa RIs landscape. The mapping carried out in the first phase of the project, as well as the active collaboration of stakeholders, provided a solid basis for involving RIs in an inclusive manner. However, Una Europa institutions are large, comprehensive universities, which makes it difficult to have a complete and up to date overview of infrastructures and expertise and to keep stakeholders engaged. In this regard, it is crucial to develop digital tools to share information (see WP2 pilot action "blueprint for a common catalogue of research infrastructures" in this document) and platforms that can facilitate engagement and dialogue among stakeholders.

Outcomes and impact of the pilot project

Implementation of the matchmaking format in the Cultural Heritage and One Health field has

achieved several important outcomes. The primary achievement of these workshops is the establishment of networks consisting of RIs managers, experts, and responsible researchers in the field of Museums and Digital Collections, and Genomics. These workshops allowed the participants to become familiar with each other, understand their specificities and needs, and define their mutual interests.

Under the guidance of the WP2 team, the established network goes beyond a mere collection of contacts to serve as a reflection-oriented network. In the long run, the hope is that the network will serve as a solution-oriented network. During the workshops, participants have not only reflected on possible partnerships and collaborations, but also opened their minds to new forms of collaboration that extend beyond the established frameworks and target the creation of a barrier-free research ecosystem. As a result, the pilot project raised the participants' awareness about the importance of opening RIs and the need to reflect on the openness and shareability of their data and services. The pilot also sought to inspire the opening up to international partners and cooperation on a European level, despite the represented infrastructures being small to medium in size.

The pilot project illustrated how establishing a network of RIs goes beyond the mere exchange of experiences and best practices and fosters joint collaborative activities (including research or educational projects) based on the impetus provided by researchers. Another important outcome of the pilot is, therefore, the establishment of the direct connection between participating RIs and the Una Europa self-steering committees. Even though the involvement of the Cultural Heritage and One Health self-steering committees were different during the implementation phase, both expressed interest in taking forward the collaboration with RIs in the framework of Una.Futura.

The connection between the participating RIs and the self-steering committees holds multiple benefits and prospective impacts. Firstly, it enables the RIs to support activities that will be validated as part of the Una.Futura project action plan, whilst empowering RIs to bring their own vision and suggest their own collaboration activities for research enhancement. In a long-term perspective, empowering RIs as actors of international collaboration could transform the institutional vision of infrastructure from solely being a support system, with them also being perceived as a driving force behind research activities. This change in perception can help improve the valorisation of RIs, and both encourage and support policy makers in developing global solutions on openness and shareability.

In summary, the initial outcomes of the pilot project have demonstrated a high level of interest from RIs regarding collaboration and the potential for scaling up. The success of this pilot indicates that repeating and expanding such projects can generate interest from other types of infrastructures and other scientific domains. Moreover, the alignment of the initiatives discussed during the workshops with the self-steering committees' action plans holds great potential for reinforcing the research ecosystem and positioning RIs more effectively within institutional policies.

The pilot project has successfully achieved its stated goals and outcomes and laid the basis for promoting a barrier-free collaboration in R&I. In both case studies, many ideas for collaboration in R&I, but also in education, emerged and as mentioned above, the self-steering

committees have already taken some of these actions forward in the framework of Una.Futura. Moreover, this pilot action strongly contributed to raising awareness on the importance of RIs as enablers of a barrier-free R&I ecosystem, and a systematic collaboration with RIs is now included as a strategic objective in the Strategy and Action Plans of the both the Culture Heritage and One Health self-steering committee.

Concerning the pilot on Museums and Digital collections, various ideas for collaboration between RIs and the Cultural Heritage self-steering committee emerged. These include:

- Creating a "virtual museum" to showcase the RIs and their collections, hence providing visibility to their assets. This initiative could serve as an alternative to a joint catalogue, considering that most RIs already have their own online catalogues or are part of broader national or European catalogue initiatives.
- Supporting Una Europa's participation in other projects such as the Knowledge and Innovation Communities (KIC) (European Institute of Innovation & Technology (EIT) Culture & Creativity), as well as fostering important external partnerships with organisations and projects like ARCHE, European Heritage Hub, Europeana, Nemo, etc.
- Participating in joint calls, such as "A European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage," which aims to develop RIs and their tools.
- Contributing to the organisation of joint events like the European Academic Heritage Day or the European Archaeology Days.
- Facilitating the exchange of best practices, particularly in collaborating with non-academic partners such as NGOs, institutions, businesses, and the wider civil society.

In addition to these collaborative actions, research and educational activities were also considered. For research, several joint actions and ideas were discussed:

- Positioning RIs as catalysts for new research projects and research activities, including PhD research. Specific calls could be launched to study RI collections or methodologies such as conservation, digitisation, AI imaging, and more. Una Europa RIs can provide support and inspiration to Transnational Research Teams (TRTs) established within the framework of Cultural Heritage Doctoral programs.
- Supporting Una Europa Cultural Heritage initiatives in expanding their research topics to include Asia, Africa, and Latin America, as well as other interdisciplinary research projects aligned with Una Europa's Focus Areas.
- Assisting researchers in publishing their research as open access and facilitating joint publication initiatives.
- Hosting or participating in scientific conferences on relevant subjects.

In terms of promoting the use of RIs in educational activities, collaboration between RIs and the Cultural Heritage self-steering committee can yield fruitful results:

- RIs can propose trainings or courses to develop specific skills, such as digitisation, imaging, data modelling, open-science policies related to cultural heritage, and specialised humanities disciplines, 3D representations, AI applied to forms/images, study of ancient materials, and more. These trainings/courses could be offered as massive-open-online courses (MOOCs) or summer schools.
- Integrating these courses into existing PhD programs or incorporating them into future Bachelor's and Master's programs.

Concerning the pilot on Genomics, the ideas that emerged, and the following resulting recommendations, are key for the Alliance to move towards opening and sharing RIs and, ultimately, build a barrier-free research ecosystem:

- Develop tools to allow the research community to learn and explore the range of RIs available across the Alliance and provide a common information point. This will allow complementary assets to be identified and enhance RI visibility to potential users and collaborators.
- Connect people to promote contact across RI staff and with academic researchers, and matchmaking for RIs in specific research domains. This can take the form of articles, newsletters, and success stories that can be shared through digital platforms.
- Enhance the role of RI in fostering Open Research and FAIR data management, work on the development of common guidelines on operationalisation of FAIR principles.
- Assess costing and funding models, secure funding in order to cover access fees, stimulate researchers applying for grants to cover RI costs, and allocate seed-funding for initial research collaborations. It would be important to adapt pricing systems and business models for Alliance members by taking multiple perspectives into account (e.g., government regulations and user perspectives). The difficulty in managing different expectations on costing from different stakeholders (i.e., users, institutional funders, and funding agencies) was highlighted as a critical point.
- Strengthening knowledge and skills in RI management, e.g., through mutual learning, training, and micro-credentials. As previously mentioned, there is an interest to promote staff mobility and interdisciplinary research, and to work very closely with the One Health self-steering committee to integrate the proposed actions into their visions and objectives.
- Create policies and strategies to overcoming barriers, such as the co-design and promotion of an Una Europa charter for RIs that will encourage the adoption of common general principles. This can be concretised through undertaking a common advocacy action to strengthen RIs.

The project was based on a solid methodology and piloted a simple “start-up process” for establishing a network of RIs that could be applied to different thematic fields and different types of infrastructures. The process can be summarised as follows:

- Definition of the scope (e.g., theme, type of RIs, type of technology, etc.) in alignment with the self-steering committee interests and activities, and also in collaboration with RI experts.
- Identification of relevant RIs that could be involved based on a mapping process and on the consultation with key stakeholders.
- Launch of a call for EoIs targeting the relevant group of RIs representatives (academics and RIs managers). The EoI should be launched through a specific form used to collect basic information but also preliminary inputs on needs and expectations of participants. This data can then be used to shape the workshops’ agenda and drive the discussions.
- The group of interested RIs are invited to attend a series of matchmaking workshops that lay the basis for establishing a network. The first step will be mutual knowledge of participants, followed by a more specific discussion on mutual interests, ideas for joint actions and collaborations in relation to self-steering committees’ activities, and paths (considering barriers and enablers) towards opening and sharing RIs. Discussion could

be supported by Miro boards and organised in breakout rooms.

- The first output could be a report/roadmap for undertaking concrete actions in the short, medium, and long run (and specifying the resources needed). The link with relevant self-steering committees as Una Europa Interdisciplinary Hubs is key, but infrastructures should also be empowered to bring their own proposals and visions.
- As recommended in the Una.Resin Deliverable 2.2, it is crucial to seek funding for the sustainability and scaling up of the activities.

The format of this process does not require specific tools and, therefore, is easily accessible and transferable. All the materials (data on mapped RIs; call for Eols; Google form; materials related to the workshops, final reports) are available to Una.Resin teams and the RI Cluster. These materials can be considered as an initial toolkit that can be used to scale up the format in other thematic fields, taking into consideration the lessons learnt from Una.Resin.

The outcomes of this pilot project informed the Una Europa Strategy and Action Plan for Sharing Research Infrastructures and Resources (Una.Resin Deliverable 2.2), where the need to create a RIs community is strongly underlined. The recommendations of the Una.Resin Deliverable 2.2 were shared with the institutional decision-makers of the Una Europa universities, and the Board of Directors and Research Strategy Group approved the project deliverables and recognised the importance of the Una.Resin strategies. In particular, the Una Europa Research and Innovation Strategy (Una.Resin Deliverable 1.2) and the Una Europa Strategy and Action Plan for Sharing Research Infrastructures and Resources (Una.Resin Deliverable 2.2) informed the vision on the transversal theme on R&I of the Una.Futura project.

In parallel, a two-phase survey was launched within the Alliance to prioritise R&I actions and allocate resources for implementation. In this framework, institutional decision makers are evaluating the possibility to take forward the matchmaking format piloted as part of the Una.Resin project, creating thematic networks of infrastructures that can collaborate and find ways of sharing services and facilities. This action would strengthen the visibility of small-medium scaled university infrastructures towards external users (including non-academic users and the civil society).

In the future, this action could influence decision-makers at the European level. It promotes decisions advancing the development of specific funding calls dedicated to supporting bottom-up networking and community-building processes as a prerequisite for sharing and opening infrastructures. Thus, the action could foster the development of decisions that strengthen the connection and integration of the RI ecosystem of the Alliances.

Sustainability of the pilot project

At this stage, it is still not precisely defined when the insights and outcomes delivered through the pilot project will be continued or replicated/scaled up. As mentioned, the self-steering committees are in the process of finalising their Strategy and Action plans in the framework of the Una.Futura project. Systematic collaboration with RIs based on the outcomes of the Una.Resin activities is already included in the action plans of the Cultural Heritage and One Health self-steering committees. Some specific actions, such as the creation of a Virtual Museum of Una Europa universities heritage, will be undertaken in Una.Futura and will engage the research and data infrastructures that have been involved in the Una.Resin pilot. By

mapping and bringing together digital collections from all the Una Europa universities, the pilot project inspired the prospective creation of a new, shared virtual museum of the (tangible and intangible) academic heritage of Una Europa universities based on the sharing of digital infrastructures. The virtual museum will not be a mere additional database, but will be focused on infrastructural development and the creation of tools and applications that will foster new display formats of preserved digital material for various forms of storytelling.

In general, the engagement of RIs and data infrastructures in the self-steering committees' research and education activities is key to ensure sustained and committed development that build on the insights and outcomes of the pilot action. Since the action plans are specific for each Focus Area, it is likely that the type and level of RIs engagement will vary across Focus Areas and across institutions.

In relation to the continuation, and possible scaling, of the matchmaking format piloted in Una.Resin, it is important to consider that this action is part of the Una Europa Strategy and Action Plan on sharing RIRs (Una.Resin Deliverable 2.2). In this document, the proposed action, named "Creating a RIs Community" (see Una.Resin Deliverable 2.2, Pillar 1 – Action 2), is focused on theme-specific matchmaking workshops and events for RIs and, at higher levels of ambition, the creation of thematic networks of RIs and scaling to other Focus Areas, and, in the long run, towards possible synergies with other alliances.

The priorities and actions on research and data infrastructures proposed in the Una.Resin Deliverable 2.2 have informed the Una Europa R&I Vision and are now being assessed for prioritisation by the governance of the Una Europa institutions. More specifically, a prioritisation exercise at the higher decision-making levels of the Alliance has been launched in relation to potential future activities in the area of R&I. This exercise is based on a matrix of potential actions, including the priorities on infrastructures proposed in Una.Resin Deliverable 2.2, which will be ranked through a two-stage survey; the preferred level of ambition and resource allocation for the prioritised actions will also be defined. The outcomes of this exercise will inform the development of a common R&I action plan for the Alliance. This plan will be discussed by the Board of Directors and Research Strategy Group and, based on a clear agreement on the prioritised actions and resources to be committed, actions will either be implemented under the framework of Una.Futura, with institutional resources, or with institutional resources focused on attracting external funding.

As explained above, ensuring the connection between RIs and self-steering committees, and finalising the Una Europa prioritisation exercise of R&I actions (including the continuation and scaling up of RIs matchmaking format) is key to assess the feasibility of scaling up the pilot project beyond the Una.Resin project. The format is easily accessible based on the available materials and lessons learnt. This initial toolkit will enable the continuation of the matchmaking process and empower RIs to initiate and lead workshops autonomously. In this respect, it is important to underline that there was an initial interest expressed by a UEDIN representative in the RI Cluster to start a RIs network in the field of Mass Spectrometry via the matchmaking format (this action has not been undertaken yet).

The continuation and scaling up of the matchmaking format piloted in Una.Resin would lead to a consolidation of a methodology that could also be of interest to other alliances. In a longer

perspective, joint matchmaking events could be organised at national and European levels to scale up the RIs cooperation. In order to guarantee the sustainability of the format, it is crucial to ensure an effective communication and valorisation of collaborative activities among RIs. Una Europa should provide visibility to the thematic networks of infrastructures through its communication channels, to promote awareness and engagement among relevant stakeholders. Moreover, to further stimulate systematic and sustainable bottom-up matchmaking and community-building activities, a dedicated funding call from the EC would be needed, specifically aimed at connecting RIs and creating theme-focused networks of RIs (between universities, alliances but also with ESFRI infrastructures). Funding for organising in-person seminars, workshops, and events and to support physical attendance would be key to supporting the sustainability of this pilot action.

In terms of cost-benefits analysis, it is important to consider that bottom-up engagement processes require a lot of resources but yield a high benefit return. Una.Resin WP2 pioneered the Alliance work on RIs and, in the initial phases of this work (mapping and co-creation workshop), the first and most important topic that emerged was the need of researchers and RIs managers to know each other's available assets, expertise, and interests. This was the rationale behind the choice of a bottom-up participatory format, focused on specific case studies with a scalable methodology. This required a high degree effort and, due to the limited resources, only two "start-up" workshops were organised per each case study. This initial community-building exercise helped create awareness among RIs stakeholders about the assets of other universities, as well as an awareness of opportunities for collaboration across the Alliance. These bottom-up processes, and the concrete collaborations among RIs that arose, represent a crucial step for supporting interdisciplinary research addressing complex challenges and for moving towards opening and sharing RIs across the Alliance. National and European policymakers should invest in these processes by allocating dedicated funding to Alliances (and more in general, universities) and supporting the development of a more connected and integrated ecosystem of RIs via decision-making and policy.

Lessons learnt

A series of lessons have been identified from designing and implementing this pilot:

- The format of the pilot project was successful. Workshops enabled the establishment and strengthening of networks of RIs and created opportunities for participants to exchange ideas, explore potential partnerships, and identify areas of common interest that can lead to fruitful collaborations.
- Continuing and scaling up the workshops to different types, disciplines, and Focus Areas is crucial for creating a knowledge community of RIs. This can lead to the formation of interdisciplinary teams that can tackle complex challenges and develop innovative solutions, thus contributing to the implementation of the R&I agenda of the Alliance.
- Identifying mutual interest and implementing joint activities is a crucial step for the opening up and potential sharing of RIs.
- Collaborations forged through workshops and matchmaking activities can extend beyond initial interactions, and serve as a springboard for joint research projects, collaborative grants, and educational initiatives.
- The alignment and synergy between the Una Europa's Focus Areas and RIs are essential for unlocking the full potential of collaboration. By identifying areas of convergence, we can leverage the expertise and resources of RIs to address the

challenges and research questions within the Focus Areas.

Recommendations for the future

The pilot offers a number of recommendations giving direction to future activity:

- Planning a series of workshops dedicated to RIs presentations and discussions. It would also be useful to build in time for workshops/seminars that address specific issues (e.g., costing and funding models; FAIR data management) or for sharing knowledge and expertise on topics of common interest.
- Having small groups (e.g., formed on the basis of RIs type) can facilitate discussions. A digital platform – including articles, newsletters, and success stories – could be created to facilitate the connection among RIs representatives and give visibility to the network activities.
- Representatives from the Una Europa self-steering committees should be present during the workshops in order to provide the necessary context and information on the framework of the Focus Area activities.
- It is important to find synergies with other collaborative actions of the Alliance, including educational programmes.
- It is important to find resources for collaborative activities through the development of joint applications, as well as resources to promote staff mobility for onsite visits, training, and the organisation of physical workshops and events.

Pilot Evaluation 5: Una Europa citizen science Toolkit

Objectives and aims of the pilot

The Citizen Science Toolkit is a pilot project dedicated to citizen science and aimed to address the “Embedding Citizens and society” transformation module. As part of WP3, it also plays a role in bolstering the “Strengthening Human Capital” transformation module. The pilot targets early-stage researchers and aims at enhancing their transdisciplinary skills that are crucial to diversifying their career paths. By promoting more open, inclusive, and transparent research the pilot also contributes to the “Comprehensive mainstreaming of Open Science practices” transformation module.

The pilot addresses several barriers to cross border and cross-sectoral R&I collaboration:

- Lack of sustainable and accessible knowledge-sharing formats: A significant challenge lies in the absence of sustainable and easily shareable formats for exchanging knowledge.
- Limited awareness of partner universities' expertise and projects: There is often a lack of awareness about the expertise and ongoing projects within partner universities. This issue is particularly prominent in the context of citizen science where the visibility of initiatives is usually insufficient.
- Deficiency in interdisciplinary proficiency: An essential element in promoting cross-sectoral collaboration is having the necessary interdisciplinary expertise. Citizen science projects, in particular, frequently require collaboration across diverse domains, necessitating a wide range of expertise.
- Lack of networking opportunities: The lack of networking opportunities hinders the ability to bring together specialists from different disciplines who are addressing

common global challenges.

This pilot aims to animate institutional change by developing material for the integration of science and society in curricula (e.g., covering STEM, public engagement, ethics, gender), and enlarge the scope of R&I activities by fostering informal science education (museums, science centres), promoting citizen science, and engaging civil society actors and citizens. The desire is to foster Open Science and open access to scientific results and data (e.g., online open notebooks, OERs, open data, etc.) in relation to citizen science projects. The main target group of the pilot project are early-career researchers, with the secondary target group being researchers at any stage of the career who are interested in participative projects and/or willing to initiate a citizen science project. The main beneficiaries are researchers, including early-stage researchers, with research support managers and policy makers being secondary beneficiaries.

In the early stages of the project design, it was essential to take into account other Una.Resin pilot projects. To avoid creating multiple online platforms that were similar, it was decided to steer the pilot project toward alternative formats. Despite discussions regarding the potential benefits of a Citizen Science Hub, the decision was made to create an online platform designed to facilitate collaboration between researchers and citizens. This platform sought to be a solution to address the numerous bottlenecks in the enhancement of citizen science practices.

The experience of the Cultural Heritage self-steering committee played a significant role in shaping the pilot project's concept. The self-steering committee had already been working on joint projects that were participative in nature. One of these projects, the Cultural Heritage at The Edge (CUTE) project (2021-22) developed within the 1Europe project (funded under the Una Europa seed funding initiative), served as an example from which to develop the toolkit. The continuation of this project, CUMET-Cultural Heritage in The Metropolitan Peripheries, 2023-2026, JPI CH (Joint Programming Initiative on Cultural Heritage), also includes collaboration with citizens.

The experience of the self-steering committee illustrated the need to develop knowledge of citizen science methodologies and the skills for effective engagement of citizens across Una Europa universities. Consequently, it appeared crucial to harness expertise in citizen science practices to assist potential research teams in planning and executing collaborative projects that incorporate citizen participation. Moreover, with the existence of the UnaHerDoc joint doctoral program in Cultural Heritage, the pilot project's results will directly serve PhD students enrolled in this program.

The idea and format for this pilot were also influenced by the OER Toolkit developed during the 1Europe project. This served as both a model and inspiration for creating support materials that are open and accessible to all.

Initial design and implementation of the pilot project

One of the primary goals of the Una.Resin project is to reshape the institutional structure of member institutions, enabling them to proactively address the upcoming global challenges. This transformation encompasses frameworks that actively engage citizens and non-

academic entities across all regions within the Una Europa ecosystem and throughout every phase of the R&I process, and thus, provided the rationale for inclusion of dedicated citizen science pilot. Citizen science serves as an effective tool to close the gap between science and society, promoting openness and enhancing the overall impact of research. By involving citizens in research initiatives, universities are working towards the democratisation of knowledge and strengthening trust in scientific research.

The initial phase of the Una.Resin project further supported the need for a dedicated citizen science pilot. The mapping and brainstorming exercises conducted in the initial phase underscored the universities' strong dedication to citizen engagement, yet also highlighted a deficiency in the support for, understanding of, and infrastructure around citizen science. Consequently, the decision was made to concentrate the pilot project's efforts on enhancing awareness of citizen science, sharing exemplary approaches, and consolidating expertise.

As an integral component of WP3, this pilot project is also aligned with the overarching goals of this WP, which revolve around enhancing the capabilities of early-stage researchers by equipping them with transversal skills that can facilitate diverse career paths. In this context, the primary target audience for this pilot project comprises early-stage researchers. Its central objective is to inform early-stage researchers about the various manifestations of citizen science, elucidate its benefits, requirements, and impact, and strengthen their abilities in project design and implementation. The pilot project, therefore, investigates the possibility of co-producing knowledge on citizen science through the exchange of best practices. Additionally, it explores the feasibility of converting the know-how required to initiate a citizen science project into a transversal skill or a set of transversal skills needed to achieve impactful and responsible research.

To accomplish these objectives, it was decided that the project should take shape in the form of a toolkit. The Una Europa Citizen Science Toolkit comprises eight interviews conducted with renowned researchers, representing eight Una.Resin universities, who are experts in the field of citizen science. These experts were asked eight questions addressing the following key aspects: 1) project presentation, 2) project design and funding, 3) citizen engagement, 4) the role of citizens, 5) identifying bottlenecks and barriers, 6) evaluating impact and sustainability, 7) examining institutional support and recognition, and 8) advice for early-stage researchers. The interviews have been made publicly accessible on the Una Europa website, accompanied by guidelines distilled from the insights shared within them. Consequently, the toolkit offers first-hand knowledge grounded in personal experiences and forged through this collaborative activity. Importantly, the toolkit is licensed as an OER, aligning with Una Europa's commitment to openness, inclusivity, and the dissemination of innovative work for the benefit of a wider community.

A four-steps approach was applied to the pilot. The first two steps were primarily focused on mapping the strategies, policies, support services, and best practices in the field of citizen science. The data collection was carried out through different questionnaires shared with administrative staff, researchers, and university policy makers. The acquired data was analysed based on the following two documents: Mapping HR Strategies and Priorities for Joint Strategy (Una.Resin Deliverable 3.1.) and Analysis of the Open Research Support Services and Practices (Annex Una.Resin Deliverable 2.2). Additionally, a series of webinars

were organised to showcase exemplary citizen science projects and a cartography of citizen science initiatives in the One Health and Cultural Heritage Focus Areas.

The subsequent two phases revolved around brainstorming sessions and workshops organised by the Citizen Engagement cluster. These sessions aimed to facilitate the exchange of experiences, delve into challenges, and propose potential solutions to enhance citizen science within the Alliance. An essential milestone in this endeavour was the co-creation workshop, which was held online on 1st July 2022. During this workshop, participants discussed various aspects of citizen science, including the types, methodologies, challenges, and potential formats for institutional collaboration aimed at sharing support structures. One of the most important outcomes of the workshop was the mapping of potential solutions to bolster citizen science, categorised into four areas: 1) project incubator, 2) sharing of best practices, 3) training, and 4) support services. These steps, alongside the associated collected inputs, provided a foundation from which to develop the first idea for the pilot action, which was presented and discussed during the brainstorming session held in Edinburgh on 29th September 2022.

After developing the pilot concept, a session was organised with the researchers involved in the project to obtain their insights. Notably, the feedback from the researchers was used in formulating the interview questions, ensuring their relevance to all research projects. The interviews conducted with the researchers can also be seen as a source of data collected via the project. This data was subsequently analysed and utilised in the formulation of the recommendations that accompany the videos within the Citizen Science Toolkit. Feedback was also sought from PhD students enrolled in the joint PhD program in Cultural Heritage via a brief online questionnaire.

The pilot was designed and implemented by the Citizen Engagement cluster. Cluster members of each university were responsible for identifying experts for the interviews and for connecting with local audio-visual services during the production phase. As the decision was made to concentrate the pilot on cultural heritage, consultations were held with the Cultural Heritage self-steering committee. The self-steering committee expressed their interest in the pilot and approved the suggested format. Furthermore, in one of the interviews, the CUTE project, initiated by the self-steering committee, was featured as an example of a citizen science project.

A number of challenges arose during the design phase. Firstly, the list of actions needed to enhance citizen science at the level of the Alliance was extensive, and it was challenging to decide which needs should be addressed in the first place. Hence, the final concept of the pilot project addresses several needs: raising awareness, showcasing best practices, pooling expertise, and developing joint support materials. Secondly, the project faced challenges related to its scope, timeline, and available resource. Many initial concepts required significant financial investment, as well as the acquisition of additional expertise. Thus, the final concept of the pilot project was built in a way that ensured all the work could be done by the Citizen Engagement Cluster and without extra funding, outsourcing only the production of the videos. Finally, it was hard to estimate the sustainability within the timeline of the Una.Resin project, as the impact of the toolkit could not be fully understood by the end of the project. However, once the pilot is published, it does not require any maintenance and it can be continuously

used without any assistance.

There were also challenges in the implementation phase. It was a challenge to find relevant experts in Cultural Heritage as, in some universities, citizen science projects are still mostly associated with environmental or hard sciences. Furthermore, researchers do not always identify their projects as citizen science even though they engage citizens and are profoundly participative. To this end, the range of the disciplines and engaging practices was kept as broad as possible, with participant researchers coming from different disciplines (historians, cultural heritage managers, archaeologists, linguists, etc.) and often employing different practices to engage citizen. Despite difference in discipline and methodology, all researchers had an interest in cultural heritage. Not all universities had available audio-visual services for the production of the filmed interviews. These universities could connect their researchers with UP1, who provided the required audio-visual service.

Outcomes and impact of the pilot project

The primary achievement of the project is the development of educational support materials on how to initiate and run a citizen science project. These materials, in a form of a toolkit, are accessible to the public through the Una Europa website, and their open licensing ensures that they can be widely used. This openness is particularly advantageous for educators who can leverage these materials in their upcoming projects.

By harnessing the expertise from eight Una Europa institutions, the project enabled a collaborative production of new knowledge, which took the form of a set of recommendations complementing the videos within the toolkit. Furthermore, the project has generated recommendations aimed at institutions and alliances, offering guidance on how to bolster citizen science initiatives and amplify citizen participation in research. The pilot project has also provided participating researchers with a platform to exhibit their projects to a broader audience. It has allowed them to present their work from a fresh transdisciplinary perspective, placing a strong emphasis on the involvement of citizens. Moreover, the project effectively increases awareness of various citizen science practices, methodologies, and strategies for engaging citizens. As a result of this initiative, researchers at all career stages can gain a deeper comprehension of participatory approaches and may find inspiration to initiate their own citizen science projects. The project also provides a means for researcher to enhance their capabilities to successfully launch such projects. For research managers, the project provides a better understanding of how to support citizen science projects, identifying the specific assistance they may require. The pilot brought together eight Una Europa experts in citizen science, laying the foundation for a network of researchers specialising in participatory projects. It has pioneered a new format that can be applied to the creation of support materials across various disciplines or for other interdisciplinary topics.

The project aims to produce a transformative shift in the R&I landscape of the Una Europa universities. By raising awareness and providing guidelines and recommendations on how to initiate citizen science projects to our primary audience, the pilot aims, in the long term, to catalyse a surge in the number of citizen science projects or projects that involve participatory elements. It also has the potential to stimulate the creation of collaborative, interdisciplinary projects that tackle current global issues, effectively bridging the gap between science and the pressing needs of society. Overtime, the initiative may have a cascading effect, leading to a

more significant cultural shift towards deeper citizen engagement in R&I. Moreover, the ability to initiate citizen science projects can be viewed as a cross-cutting skill applicable across all disciplines. Cultivating cross-cutting skills empowers researchers to open new pathways in their careers.

The cultural transformation expected as a consequence of the project is not necessarily confined to researchers; it has the potential to extend to research support officers and policymakers. For instance, this transformation could influence the evolution of research support offices, prompting the creation of more customised assistance for citizen science projects or the establishment of essential infrastructure to facilitate collaboration with external stakeholders.

The primary objectives of the Una.Resin project centre around barrier-free collaboration in R&I. This encompasses forging new pathways for collective research endeavours, sharing experiences, and co-creating new knowledge. Through this pilot project, experts in Citizen Engagement could map institutional practices related to citizen science and facilitate the exchange of experiences. The toolkit itself represents an innovative approach to jointly constructing knowledge; researchers not only share their insights through interviews, but their collective experiences result in a set of recommendations for implementing citizen science projects. The project, therefore, exemplifies how pooling expertise can yield new and innovative knowledge.

One of the most significant outcomes of the project is the enhanced understanding that researchers gain regarding citizen science practices. This heightened awareness has the potential to boost the number of citizen science and participatory projects, thus stimulating initiatives aimed at addressing societal challenges. In essence, the pilot project directly contributes to the goal of making R&I within the Una Europa Alliance more impactful and responsive to global challenges.

The recommendations derived from the project not only pertain to the conception and implementation of citizen science projects but also encompass how universities should guide and support citizen science. These recommendations directly tackle the issue of building a collaborative research ecosystem involving non-academic stakeholders, including citizens.

The structure of this pilot was intentionally designed to have broad reach and accessibility. The Citizen Science Toolkit has been made publicly available on the Una Europa website ensuring access for a wide audience, and the CCBY license is attributed to the content making it free to use in other projects. To enhance accessibility, English subtitles have been included in the videos. The format of short 3-5-minute responses was selected to make the content engaging. This attractiveness is crucial for the pilot's objective of increasing awareness.

The pilot's format can be readily expanded and adapted by other universities or alliances. This format can be outlined in five distinct steps:

1. Determine the project's scope, identifying the specific academic disciplines, Focus Areas, or thematic focus that will be emphasised.
2. Identify the suitable participants who possess the experience and expertise relevant to the project.

3. Collaboratively formulate interview questions that are universally applicable to all the projects within the pilot, generating a set of five to eight core questions.
4. Conduct interviews with concise responses, ensuring that answers to each question do not exceed three to five minutes in length.
5. Compile the recommendations by distilling the insights from these experiences and synthesis the findings for each question, thereby generating new knowledge from the collective expertise.

It is important to highlight that the Citizen Engagement Cluster provided an input to the Una.Resin R&I Strategy. The Cluster made a proposal regarding the sustained collaborative efforts to improve citizen engagement practices, including citizen science, throughout the Una Europa Alliance. This proposal has been highly influenced by the learnings gained from this pilot project. Secondly, the project itself conveys a lucid message to the institutions regarding the support they can offer to researchers for the advancement of citizen science. A set of recommendations directed at institutions and alliances has been distilled from the interviews and forms an integral component of the project. These recommendations encompass the following suggestions:

- Offer educational resources that guide researchers in applying for grants involving citizen engagement activities.
- Deliver training programs focused on refining relevant project management skills.
- Aggregate expertise in citizen science methodologies, creating a centralised knowledge hub for researchers.
- Establish a repository of available funding sources.
- Provide researchers with toolboxes on possible stakeholders and associations of citizens organised to support with engaging citizens.
- Propose tailored assistance in reaching out to local communities.
- Allocate funding opportunities for experiments, allowing researchers to explore innovative research methods on a smaller scale.
- Foster a network of citizen science experts, providing an opportunity for a recurrent knowledge exchange and collaboration.

Sustainability of the pilot project

As the work on barrier-free collaboration in R&I transitions from Una.Resin into the Una.Futura project, it is possible that the outcomes of this pilot will have an influence on forthcoming Una.Futura activities. This influence is particularly relevant in the context of Una.Futura WP4, which has been tailored to extend and build upon the Una.Resin activities, with a specific emphasis on training early-stage researchers. If the knowledge of how to initiate a citizen science project is recognised as an essential, cross-cutting skill, the pilot project can be continued in the form of training. Moreover, the pilot project may find a natural continuation in the activities of the self-steering committees scheduled during the Una.Futura project period. Many self-steering committees have already underscored citizen engagement and collaboration with non-academic actors as vital tools for fortifying their infrastructures and networks. The future scaling-up of the project beyond the conclusion of Una.Resin currently lacks a definitive roadmap. A critical prerequisite for the project's continuity hinges on the ongoing efforts of the Citizen Engagement cluster, which should persist into the Una.Futura lifecycle.

Generally, the pilot project format does not inherently demand extra funding, relying primarily on the universities' in-kind contributions. Nonetheless, if a university lacks a specialised service for audio-visual content production, this particular aspect of the project may necessitate external funding and outsourcing. Furthermore, it is important to ensure the availability of support staff to oversee the project's progress and handle the synthesis of interview content.

Lessons learnt

The key lessons learnt from the pilot project can be summarised as follows:

- Embrace a wide definition of citizen science: Some researchers engage in participatory research practices without explicitly labelling their projects as citizen science, so inclusivity is vital to find participants.
- Consider interdisciplinary: Even if a project is primarily focused on a specific discipline, it is crucial to acknowledge that many citizen science projects are inherently interdisciplinary. These projects can span various fields, making rigid classification problematic.
- Collaborate with self-steering committees: Collaborating with self-steering committees is vital to ensure ongoing interest and engagement from research teams. Their involvement can guarantee beneficiaries of the project.
- Co-create questions with participating researchers: Engage in the collaborative process of formulating questions with researchers who will take part in the interviews. This ensures that the questions align with the specifics of their research projects, making the interviews more relevant and meaningful.
- Define clear target groups: It is crucial to determine the primary audience and the key beneficiaries and it should be understood that these groups may vary in their awareness regarding citizen science practices and in their experience and skill level.

Recommendations for the future

Several suggestions on how to scale up the pilot project can be formulated:

- Organise a networking event: While the project does not require researchers to be acquainted, organising an online or offline networking event can be valuable. Fostering connections among researchers interested in citizen science can lead to the creation of a network that consolidates the project's results.
- Incorporate citizen and partner perspectives: Although it presents logistical challenges, involving citizens and associated partners in the interviews can be of benefit. Their insights can provide a unique and valuable perspective, enriching the overall content and offering a more comprehensive view of citizen science initiatives.
- Broaden the project scope to other disciplines: Maintain the project's current structure while extending its reach across various disciplines, Focus Areas, or themes. This approach introduces a discipline-specific perspective, highlighting particular challenges and tactics. By encompassing multiple cases from diverse fields, the project will offer a diverse array of practices and methodologies.
- Provide other support materials: Transform the Citizen Science Toolkit into a foundational resource that serves as a basis for creating complementary materials. These additional resources can take different formats and employ various approaches to engage researchers. The ultimate goal is to establish an online, freely accessible knowledge hub.

- Develop an educational course: Explore the possibility of enhancing the project's format to create an educational course. This may involve bolstering the educational aspects and using the toolkit as a cornerstone for crafting an online course, providing structured learning opportunities. The course can be seen as a progressively expanding pool of information that evolves over years.

Pilot Evaluation 6: Open Science

Objectives and aims of the pilot

The Open Science pilot project was designed to simultaneously develop and experiment with two issues. First, the goal was to test an innovative method for discussing a key policy issue in the framework of a European University Alliance via a mechanism for formulating and debating bold hypotheses. Secondly, we aimed to offer a fresh look at the very idea of Open Science in the hope of further developing the concept of Open Science and making it more understandable to researchers, professional staff members, and the public.

In light of the above, the Open Science pilot project addressed the following transformation modules:

- Foster Open Science and open access to scientific results and data (e.g., online open notebooks, OERs, open data, etc.): The pilot action directly addressed the importance of Open Science, its benefits, and the ways to effectively implement it, promoting a culture of openness and collaboration in scientific endeavours.
- Develop material for integration of science and society in curricula (e.g., covering STEM, public engagement, ethics, gender): By discussing the broader implications and benefits of Open Science for the public, the pilot action touched upon the relevance of integrating science within society, potentially paving the way for new curricular materials that bridge this gap.
- Engage with multiple stakeholders for R&I decision making at local, national, regional EU or global level: Through the open panel discussion, the initiative brought together academics, students, and professional staff, fostering a collaborative environment for decision-making and gathering insights from various stakeholders on Open Science.

The pilot action delved into the ambiguities surrounding the concept of Open Science within the European Research and Innovation Area. These ambiguities not only touch upon its definition but also highlight how Open Science is understood diversely across various research cultures. This diversity of understanding poses a challenge to effective cross-border and cross-sectoral research collaborations. Furthermore, the pilot project contributes to ongoing debates about Open Science emphasising its value and three key dimensions: accessibility, understandability, and sharing. By focusing on these dimensions, the project aligns with the EC's transformative measures to make research findings easily accessible and comprehensible to the broader society, and to foster the sharing of various research outputs. Furthermore, by identifying challenges and potential actions, the project offers pathways for institutions to adapt and transition towards a more inclusive and open research landscape. Emphasising Open Science as a value, rather than just a procedural requirement, indicates a broader understanding of the concept's significance.

The pilot project sought to initiate desired institutional change by:

- Developing gender equality plans/measures.
- Developing material for integration of science and society in curricula (e.g., covering STEM, public engagement, ethics, gender).
- Helping uphold human rights and high general ethical standards, by adoption, development and/or implementation of codes of conduct, ethical review, etc.
- Developing activities to anticipate the potential social, environmental, and economic impacts of research (e.g., risk assessment, threat assessment, foresight, impact assessment, gender analysis).
- Developing a social corporate responsibility dimension to foster responsible innovation.
- Helping develop R&I standards that enhance social responsibility, inclusiveness, and sustainability of R&I processes and products.
- Enlarging the scope of R&I activities by fostering informal science education (museums, science centres), promoting citizen science, and engaging civil society actors and citizens.
- Engaging with multiple stakeholders for R&I decision-making at local, national, and regional EU level or at the global level.
- Fostering Open Science and open access to scientific results and data (e.g., online open notebooks, OERs, open data, etc.).

To support the achievement of this change, the intended audiences of the pilot project are: universities in general, research performing organisation, public authorities, international organisations, researchers, businesses and industry engaged in R&D, citizens, and NGOs. With the beneficiaries of the pilot being: researchers, external users (academic and non-academic), citizens, other universities, and European University alliances.

Initial design and implementation of the pilot project

The pilot project was designed as a process leading to the formulation and discussion of bold hypotheses related to the concept of Open Science. These bold hypotheses provide a mean by which to interrogate understandings on Open Science, whilst providing inspiration and impulse for developing new tools and formats of cooperation to make science more open.

In the first stage, the topic of the pilot project (i.e., the question of how Open Science should be understood) was chosen via an open discussion and consultations with various stakeholders (WPs, Una Europa Future University Lab, clusters, the Project Steering Committee). In the second stage, Una Europa's think tank, the Future University Lab, was entrusted with developing a concept note, i.e., a document which provides a fresh look at the way Open Science is understood. The Future University Lab operates as a space for innovative, out-of-the-box thinking, where the task is to offer a new, often unexpected perspective on the discussed issue, question common assumptions, and enable a genuine creative process. The writing team appointed by the Future University Lab developed a concept note in which the understanding of Open Science as a value was presented and investigated in detail.

In the third stage, the draft of the concept note was discussed internally (i.e., within the Una.Resin Project), with various stakeholders (i.e., WP leaders, clusters - the Open Research cluster in particular), and with the Project Steering Committee (PSC) members. The inputs

collected during this process were used to update the draft. In the fourth stage, the final version of the concept note was adopted by the Future University Lab's Steering Committee, presented to the Una.Resin PSC and Una Europa Board of Directors, and distributed online among the Una Europa Community and beyond. A dedicated communication channel was made available for the Una Europa community to share their views. In the fifth and final stage, the concept note was discussed during an online panel discussion, open to anyone interested. Among the panellists, there were both experts involved in the Una.Resin project, as well as those who did not work on the concept note, or who were not even members of the Una Europa community.

The realisation of the pilot project encountered two major challenges. First, it was relatively difficult to organise a consultation process including so many stakeholders in the short timeframe available. Secondly, the consultations illustrated the immense difficulty of discussing ideas that go beyond established views and existing assumptions, with stakeholders having a tendency to go back to the well-known ways of conceptualising Open Science. However, with time and effort devoted to discussing the methodology behind the pilot project, the usefulness of the proposed approach was acknowledged by the stakeholders.

Outcomes and impact of the pilot project

The selection of the pilot project topic resulted from the conclusions of the Mapping Exercise of HR policies of Una Europa partner universities, which was conducted in the first phase of Una.Resin project. From the mapping exercise, it was noted that researchers have a narrow understanding of the nature and importance of Open Science, and that universities do not do enough to advance this understanding. The pilot project sought to address this, with the resulting outcomes including:

- The concept note "Open Science as a Value" developed by the Una Europa Future University Lab.
- A (recorded) online panel discussion on the value of Open Science
- An increased understanding among the Una Europa community of the nature of Open Science practices, and in particular how openness of science constitutes an integral aspect of any rational scientific inquiry.
- An increased understanding among the Una Europa community of the usefulness of the methodology which consists in providing bold (and often controversial) ideas to fuel broad discussions of policy-related issues.

The outcomes of the project may potentially lead to a degree of institutional change at the level of the Una Europa University Alliance, as well as in the broader context of the European Research Area. On the one hand, it may contribute to a broader understanding of Open Science, as well as help researchers and professional staff members to see how Open Science is intertwined with the quality of research and the social responsibility of the researcher. On the other hand, the outcomes of the pilot may inform the development of new tools and formats which will help expanding Open Science practices (e.g., the wording of documents/instructions pertaining to Open Science, inclusion of Open Science-related issues into the curricula, developing new, comprehensive communication formats pertaining to Open Science, etc.).

Sustainability of the pilot project

The insights and outcomes delivered through the pilot serve as the basis for further developments at three different levels:

- Discussion pertaining to the understanding of Open Science should continue, with the axiological dimension of the Open Science practices emphasised by the concept note in mind. Also, the format for generating discussions on the key policy-related issues tested in the pilot should be replicated in relation to other key problems.
- The conclusions of the concept note should constitute a point of reference in developing policies, cooperation formats, and tools pertaining to Open Science developed within the Una Europa European University Alliance.
- The issues addressed in the concept note may be further discussed at the level of national and European policy-making.

Lessons learnt

The lessons learnt in this pilot project could be summarised as follows:

- **Conceptual expansion:** Researchers and professional staff members tend to understand Open Science in a narrow way, making it difficult for them to see the real benefits of Open Science.
- **Value integration:** A broader understanding of Open Science as a value may be beneficial to creating a more coherent view of science, one in which the quality of research is strengthened by both an individual and a public understanding of what science is.
- **Innovative dialogue:** It is difficult to discuss out-of-the-box ideas among researchers and professional staff members as they tend to understand the issues involved in an established, 'conventional' way.
- **Critical discourse:** It is beneficial to provide discussion mechanisms to discuss bold and controversial hypotheses to support with identifying limitations to existing ways of thinking.

The lessons learnt point to the necessity of reshaping academic culture to embrace a broader, more integrated understanding of Open Science, which can enhance the overall quality of research. Additionally, fostering environments that encourage critical discussions of unconventional ideas is essential for challenging the status quo and promoting intellectual growth.

Recommendations for the future

Future efforts should focus on cultivating ongoing discussions that reinforce Open Science as a core principle in policy-making and collaborative practices. It is also crucial to create platforms that encourage the exploration of unconventional ideas, challenge existing paradigms, and foster transformative developments in scientific policy.

Pilot Evaluation 7: Team Science

Objectives and aims of the pilot

The idea behind the Team Science pilot action was to develop and experiment with an innovative format for enriching the human capital development framework of the Una Europa

University Alliance in relation to the issue of Team Science. The pilot aimed to develop a joint Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) on Team Science and a practically-oriented workshop for researchers and professional staff members. The MOOC and workshop together constitute an experimental format for the future skills development and certification framework of Una Europa, but transferrable and scalable to other European University Alliances. The selection of this topic for the pilot resulted from previous work in Una.Resin, which exemplified how the issue of Team Science is not well-understood among researchers, and that universities do not provide sufficient training in this area.

The Team Science pilot was designed to provide knowledge on interdisciplinary team science, as well as demonstrate the principles of collaborative research in its structure and delivery. The target groups for the project were researchers and professional staff, specifically those at the forefront of research teams. The pilot includes all the critical facets of team science, from the psychological aspects of collaborative endeavours to the practical challenges of leading research teams. The Team Science pilot strategically engaged with the following transformation modules:

- **Anticipation of Research Impact:** With focus modules like "Team science and its science", the pilot delved into the potential implications of collaborative research, such as understanding cognitive bias.
- **Promotion of R&I Standards:** By emphasising leadership and team management aspects, the pilot emphasised aligning research operations with ethical standards and societal considerations.
- **Broadening the Scope of R&I Activities:** The pilot advocated for expansive research collaboration beyond traditional settings, emphasising stakeholder engagement and collaborative models like the quadruple helix.
- **Stakeholder Engagement in R&I Decision Making:** Ensuring a comprehensive and democratic approach to knowledge creation by strengthening ties between academic institutions and external entities.
- **Advocacy for Open Science:** With an emphasis on transparency in research funding, the pilot underscored the value of making scientific outputs accessible and transparent.

The Team Science MOOC and the following workshop were focused on several challenges connected to the broader theme of effective interdisciplinary collaboration:

- The nuances of leading diverse research teams and managing inherent complexities.
- The limitations posed by rigid academic boundaries, which often deter cross-border collaboration.
- A lack of comprehensive stakeholder engagement, potentially narrowing the scope and applicability of research endeavours.
- Limited understanding and application of Open Science principles, especially in funding and dissemination of research.

The Team Science pilot, culminating with the Team Science MOOC, has made progress towards addressing the targeted transformation modules. It has exposed the complexities and opportunities of interdisciplinary collaboration, creating a blueprint for future initiatives. The multi-staged approach, starting from the creation of the MOOC to its wide-scale dissemination and the collecting of feedback, ensures a comprehensive engagement with the EC transformation modules. The envisaged Una Europa certification system further amplifies the

pilot's commitment to institutional transformation, aiming to set collaborative research benchmarks.

The pilot project sought to initiate desired institutional change by:

- Developing Gender Equality Plans/measures.
- Developing material for integration of science and society in curricula (e.g., covering STEM, public engagement, ethics, gender).
- Helping uphold human rights and high general ethical standards, by adoption, development and/or implementation of codes of conduct, ethical review, etc.
- Developing activities to anticipate the potential social, environmental, and economic impacts of research (e.g., risk assessment, threat assessment, foresight, impact assessment, gender analysis).
- Developing a Social Corporate Responsibility dimension to foster responsible innovation.
- Helping develop R&I standards that enhance social responsibility, inclusiveness, and sustainability of R&I processes and products.
- Enlarging the scope of R&I activities by fostering informal science education (museums, science centres), promoting citizen science, and engaging civil society actors and citizens.
- Engaging with multiple stakeholders for R&I decision-making at local, national, and regional level of the EU and/or at the global level.
- Fostering Open Science and open access to scientific results and data (e.g., online open notebooks, OERs, open data, etc.).

To support the achievement of this change, the intended audiences of the pilot project are: universities in general, research performing organisation, public authorities, international organisations, researchers, businesses and industry engaged in R&D, citizens, and NGOs. With the beneficiaries of the pilot being: researchers, external users (academic and non-academic), citizens, other universities, and European University Alliances.

Initial design and implementation of the pilot project

This pilot was structured in six distinct stages:

- Stage 1: Identification of the joint team for developing the format (specialists in: psychology, philosophy, etc.).
- Stage 2: Development of the content of the MOOC as well as the workshop.
- Stage 3: Recording of the MOOC.
- Stage 4: Participation in the MOOC by selected researchers/professional staff members.
- Stage 5: The online workshop.
- Stage 6: Collecting feedback.

The project curriculum was collaboratively designed to provide a comprehensive insight into interdisciplinary team science, mirroring collaborative principles both in content and delivery. Additionally, the broader ambition was to initiate a certification system endorsed by Una Europa. This certification seeks to recognise the expertise of researchers and standardise the knowledge acquired in interdisciplinary team science, resonating with the commitment of Una Europa and the larger European University Alliance to advocate for collaborative research

standards.

Various sources of data were employed throughout the pilot. Initially, participation metrics were gauged upon the introduction in the MOOC to the Copernicus College platform. Subsequent to this, feedback played an essential role. An online workshop was orchestrated where participants dissected the MOOC's content, critically reflecting on its applicability and relevance in their research domains. Professor Mateusz Hohol's presentation (UJ), centred around team science's cognitive elements, further facilitated in-depth discussions and feedback. This multi-pronged feedback mechanism allowed for a comprehensive understanding of both stakeholder experiences and the course's impact.

The Research Careers and Culture Cluster (RCCC) involvement was imperative to ensuring representation from all collaborating institutions, overseeing feedback mechanisms, and strategising the pilot's future trajectory, especially in aligning with the broader objectives of the Una.Resin project.

One of the issues faced in creating the Team Science MOOC was the identification of appropriate specialists to lead and contribute to the course, since there are no virtual mechanisms in place in Una Europa to support facilitation. Moreover, the initial budget did not cover the costs of recording the MOOCs. Thus, forcing the organisers to seek additional funding, external to Una.Resin, to meet the production needs.

Outcomes and impact of the pilot project

The Team Science pilot project aimed to emphasise the importance and intricacies of interdisciplinary collaboration in research. The creation of the MOOC, tailored for researchers and professionals, marked a significant step in standardising interdisciplinary team science. The course not only provided knowledge on the subject but also demonstrated collaborative principles through its structure and delivery. The pilot's most important outcomes are:

- The MOOC (or rather, pre-MOOC) was recorded and tested, with feedback on what to improve.
- We tested the combination of a "theoretical" MOOC and "practical" workshop, and collected feedback on how to improve it.
- Good experience in collaboration on such a format with colleagues from different universities was obtained. The accumulated knowledge of specialists from various universities made it easier to develop a comprehensive MOOC; their various points of view contributed to making it better.
- Useful experience in generating feedback was acquired, with various points of view from different universities making the feedback even more useful.
- We further developed the comprehensive understanding and importance of Team Science – a topic which is very much neglected in skill development programs and HR policies.

The MOOC has played a pivotal role in translating and synthesising Una.Resin's knowledge and innovations into an accessible format. Modules like "Anticipation of Research Impact" and "Promotion of R&I Standards" not only convey the project's core values, but also ensure that participants are well-equipped with the latest interdisciplinary research methodologies. By making this course more broadly available, the pilot will ensure that the synthesised

knowledge reaches a broader audience, further amplifying its impact.

While the immediate uptake of the pilot project's outcomes by decision-makers at institutional, national, and EU levels might still be in its nascent stages, the potential for influence is vast. The pilot could inform policies related to research collaboration and standardisation, emphasising the need for interdisciplinary approaches. Based on this the pilot, we anticipate a future, positive shift in the perception and endorsement of collaborative research endeavours across various decision-making platforms.

Lessons learnt

By integrating the lessons learnt, future initiatives can be structured to maximise the effectiveness and reach of professional development programs within the Alliance. The lessons learnt are as follows:

- Expertise collaboration: Pooling of expertise within the Alliance helps to develop comprehensive educational and skills-development tools and materials.
- Targeted skill focus: Addressing often overlooked areas of skill development offers valued growth opportunities for researchers and professional staff.
- Collaborative integration: Facilitating collaborative environments, such as practical workshops, where researchers and professional staff can coalesce, has been crucial. This approach fosters a unified understanding and application of skills in the development programs.
- Alliance support: The development of substantial projects like MOOCs signals a need for enhanced support at the Alliance level. Effective backing endorsement can significantly streamline the process and the necessary resources for MOOC development and implementation.

Recommendations for the future

Adopting the following recommendations could significantly elevate the effectiveness and appeal of future skill development initiatives, leading to more adept and versatile research teams:

- Model exploration: Continued experimentation with the integrated format of MOOCs paired with workshops is advised, which is promising for future skills development programs and accompanying certification processes.
- Inclusive development: The recommendation is to inclusively involve both researchers and professional staff in the creation and refinement of skills development programs. Their joint efforts can yield a more holistic and pragmatic educational approach.
- Collaborative participation: Encourage and facilitate the simultaneous participation of researchers and professional staff in these programs. Such cross-functional engagement can enhance learning experiences and foster a more collaborative research culture.
- Specialised focus: Prioritising underrepresented areas of skill development could fill existing gaps and meet the latent needs within the research community, enhancing the overall competency framework.
- Team Science enhancement: There is a need to expand and enrich programs that specifically bolster team science skills. These are essential in navigating the interdisciplinary demands of contemporary research endeavours.

Pilot Evaluation 8: Fostering business-academia cooperation

Objectives and aims of the pilot project

The purpose of this pilot is to develop a preliminary prototype of a common catalogue of research groups and transferable research activities at the Una.Resin level. Through this preliminary prototype, the possibilities of creating a catalogue in the future will be examined. Hence, this pilot project addressed the following transformation modules: enlarge the scope of R&I activities by fostering business-academia cooperation, and promoting cooperation between research groups.

The pilot project sought to initiate desired institutional change by fostering business-academia cooperation with the aim of enlarging the scope of R&I activities, and promoting networking between researchers. To support the achievement of this change, the intended audiences of the pilot project are researchers, businesses and industry engaged in R&D, citizens, and NGOs, with the beneficiaries being the universities of the Una.Resin Project.

Initial design and implementation of the pilot project

The analysis carried out in a previous mapping exercise within Una.Resin (see Una.Resin Deliverable 3.1) shows that the main challenge for the universities, regarding business-academia cooperation, is the overall coordination of activities undertaken by different units/agendas to ensure synergy effects.

Two main needs were identified to promote business-academia cooperation:

- The need to promote cooperation and information sharing between research groups and foster contact between researchers from other countries, disciplines, etc. This sharing will ensure an up-to-date understanding across groups and of individual knowledge and skills and, ultimately, support academia in offering the highest quality services to industry.
- The need to improve the way in which information about research groups is shared with industry and to identify and give visibility to the activities performed by the research groups that can be transferable to industry. Many research groups can offer different services to private companies, the third sector, governmental organisations, etc. However, the services they can provide are sometimes unknown to potential users. A necessary first step in bringing academia and business closer is to give visibility to the "transferable research activities". Complementary to this, sharing information between universities through a catalogue could also be very advantageous.

These two emerging needs lead to the main goal of the project of developing a research groups and transfer catalogue. First, desk research was carried out and clusters/WPs were consulted to identify recommendations. After that, a prototype was developed. Following a meeting with the PSC where the initial pilot was presented, comments and feedback from the Una.Resin members were taken into account and the pilot was updated. In addition, a meeting with WP1 (within which recommendations for a collaboration platform were being developed) was held to develop synergies that can benefit Una.Resin as a whole. These meetings highlighted the need to focus the pilot on the Focus Areas of Cultural Heritage and One Health, and simplify the consultation process among the Una.Resin members.

A proposal on how to share information about research groups and transferable research activities and a proposal for a fact sheet on how to collect the information were shared with the WP3 and the PSC. After integrating the received feedback, the following principle good practices were identified to overcome possible challenges:

- Focus on specific areas of knowledge to make the pilot more accessible. This reinforces the previously stated idea of focusing on the areas of One Health and Cultural Heritage.
- Clearly define the information to be shared in detail with universities.
- Make the information collection process as simple as possible. Ideally, an automated way of collecting information should be developed. At this early stage, it is not necessary to collect a large amount of information since the target is the production of an example catalogue. A short questionnaire was adequate that could then be improved and expanded in the future.

The biggest challenge was gathering the necessary information. To overcome it, an online questionnaire was created.

Outcomes and impact of the pilot project

A prototype of a research groups and transfer catalogue has been built. If this information is shared at the Alliance level, in an accessible and simple way, the different universities could benefit in several ways. Firstly, they could see the international collaborations between research groups increasing and, secondly, there could be a widening of the markets for transferable research activities at the international level. More precisely, universities will improve the way in which information is shared about their research groups and their transferable activities, which is currently challenging. Moreover, they will be able to gain this information at an international level, which will support the important work carried out by the relevant offices of each university.

The pilot has produced a prototype that is easy to use and which synthesises the main results so they are widely accessible. A final version of this prototype could be shared with the general public in the future, and act as an example of good practice in information exchange.

Sustainability of the pilot project

This pilot could be scaled up in Una.Futura project if there is agreement between the Alliance members. The scaled-up version could cover all Una Europa Focus Areas and offer a public online platform with information on research groups and activities transferable to industry. The benefits are superior to the costs, with the resulting costs split between two main categories: IT personnel (one person can be in charge of the platform) and researchers' time (for filling out the online survey to provide details about their activities). Scaling up the pilot could lead to a framework for promoting collaboration among Alliance members, as well as business-academia cooperation.

Lessons learnt

A series of lessons have been identified from designing and implementing the pilot:

- Researchers are supportive of a framework that fosters business-academia cooperation.
- The benefits are superior to the costs, especially as the framework needs to allow for information to be easily shared.
- It is important to ensure ample visibility of the research teams' activities that are

transferable to industry activities so as to enhance the business-academia cooperation.

Recommendations for the future

The pilot offers a number of recommendations giving direction to future activity:

- This pilot should be scaled up in Una.Futura.
- The scaled-up version should address all Una Europa Focus Areas.
- The prototype developed within this pilot project could be transformed into a publicly accessible online platform with information on research groups and activities transferable to industry.

ERA Policy Brief

Final Version

Sophia Karner

25/01/2024

Feedback on Progress

1. **Please describe the challenges your Alliance encountered in Reporting Period 2 regarding cooperation between universities in the field of R&I in relation to the institutional change areas (transformation modules) foreseen as well regulatory obstacles hampering the cooperation.**

Founded in 2019, Una Europa is an Alliance of now eleven **leading research-intensive universities** from all corners of Europe, who have come together to jointly shape the future of high-quality education and **excellent research of high impact in Europe** and beyond. The **scale, international outlook and complementary strengths** of the Una Europa universities are the very foundation of the Alliance's ambition to achieve greater societal impact and drive the international competitiveness of the European higher education sector at large. Such an ambitious mission does not come without its challenges. Each of the Una Europa partner universities operate in **distinct national contexts** both in terms of policy and funding and are subject to **different national rules and regulations**, such as in the areas of research assessment, research funding as well as research and digital infrastructures. This naturally results in different levels of maturity, strengths and interests across the partners in relation to transformation modules as well as strategic priorities in the area of research & innovation more broadly. It is crucial to bear this complexity in mind before diving into the concrete challenges faced across various transformation modules.

Funding & policy context

European Universities alliances are navigating a **challenging policy environment and funding landscape** at regional, national and European levels, which must develop further in order to fully accommodate the needs of this new and innovative type of transnational collaboration. It must be highlighted that overall funding levels for the European Universities Initiative thus far does not seem to be on par with the European Commission's high political ambitions for the initiative as well as related policy objectives, most recently set out in the European Strategy for Universities. This is particularly felt in the area of research & innovation, where the **absence of a clear funding perspective at European level** to translate common

research & innovation strategies and action plans into practice is a particular concern. In addition, recent enlargement of alliances means that the **new partner universities** also require investment for the research & innovation dimension of the Alliance.

At the same time, the current **project-based funding approach** has led to difficulties in internal resourcing as well as uncertainty in terms of staff retention and staff turnover at the participating universities, which has been increasingly apparent in the second half of the project's reporting period. This also holds true when it comes to **regional and national co-financing** for the European Universities Initiative. While some Una Europa partner universities have received co-financing either for their overall participation in the Alliance or linked to certain activities at certain times, the approach across participating countries has been fragmented and unpredictable in the medium to long-term. Equally, the use of co-financing often comes with constraints both in terms of thematic scope and timeline, resulting in a suboptimal lever for collaboration. A more **systematic, equal, and aligned approach** is needed in the future, where regional, national, and European policies and funding programmes move into the same strategic direction. Such an approach must also include decision-makers from the United Kingdom, recently re-associated to Horizon Europe, and Switzerland, currently in the process of entering formal negotiations with the European Union.

In this respect, Una Europa advocates for a **more streamlined and strategic policy and funding approach** towards supporting transnational collaboration of higher educational institutions across the whole ERA in the future, following the **core principles of excellence, impact and quality enhancement**. This requires meaningful policy initiatives and dedicated funding streams at regional, national and European levels that support this strategic priority. The European Commission, Member States and other participating countries must come together to strengthen their efforts in aligning rules and regulations related to education, research and innovation in order to arrive at a **truly integrated European Higher Education Area (EHEA) and European Research (and Innovation) Area**. These framework conditions must be ensured to support European Universities alliances in order to empower European Universities as a driving force for the implementation of the ERA objectives.

Transformation modules

Una Europa's flagship Horizon 2020 project Una.Resin has been a key vehicle to driving our Alliance's research & innovation dimension, at the core of our ambition of creating a **seamless Una Europa ecosystem for research and innovation**. The Una.Resin project has provided an important space for the **development of first joint strategies** and growing **pilot initiatives** across three key inter-connected transformation modules: Building a Common R&I Agenda, Sharing Infrastructure and Resources, and Strengthening Human Capital. In addition, three further areas – cooperation with non-academic actors, open science, and embedding citizens and society – were dealt with transversally in the project. The SwafS instrument has been a useful tool to kick-start first initiatives and mappings across a number of transformation modules in an alliance-context. However, this has equally pointed to the challenge of working across numerous ERA policy priorities simultaneously. Often, such policy priorities are also the focus of other international networks, in which many Una Europa partner universities engage, which risks duplicating efforts. This first experience has shown that it is crucial for Una Europa to be able to focus in the future on a smaller number of policy priorities that are in line with overall strategy and where clear added value can be created for the partnership.

Key challenges identified across transformation modules can be found in the subsequent sections.

The Una.Resin project specifically focused on exploring the **sharing and opening up of RIRs** with an emphasis on small- and medium-sized infrastructures across the Alliance. Generally speaking, building cross-institutional links at the level of these medium/smaller scale RIRs continues to be hampered by administrative, managerial, and technical barriers that hinder the development and sustainability of these RIRs. This is mainly due to the **lack of long-term financial and human resources** as well as existing **legal obstacles** that prevent sharing these resources in an open and accessible manner. Furthermore, a challenge of **bottom-up engagement** aimed at community-building across a diverse group of large universities has been perceived. Pilot actions, implemented as part of the project, have been instrumental in exploring more in-depth the concrete challenges the Alliance faces to achieve this ambitious objective. First and foremost, the need for **continuous exchange of knowledge and good practices** among experts, taking into account the differences across Una Europa universities, was highlighted. Furthermore, there is a clear need for **specific resources**, including for hiring dedicated personnel to progress in the different phases of sharing and opening up of research infrastructures and resources. Resources are also needed to support the concrete collaborative activities among RIs. Due to the current lack of continued funding, there is a risk that these activities will not become systematic and sustainable in the short- to medium-term. In this respect, it is important that the European Commission and national policymakers i) provide more funding to calls oriented towards the specific ecosystems of research infrastructures and resources at (alliances of) universities and ii) support institutions/alliances to co-design and promote the adoption of common guiding principles for sharing and opening RIRs across institutions going forward.

In Una.Resin, a dedicated survey was designed and conducted across the Una Europa partner universities to identify challenges in relation to **Open Science**. The survey found that **cultural change** is still required in many institutions to fully embrace Open Science practices and principles. In addition, an increased need to invest in Open Science practices in the fields of Social Sciences & Humanities was observed. The Una Europa partner universities are subject to different **national and/ or institutional regulations and requirements**, which vary considerably. There is also a perception that additional regulation and compliance obligations (i.e., GDPR, ethics, ...) both result in an increased complexity of research activities and research policy. This increases the **(administrative) burden** for researchers and policymakers in institutions who are already under pressure. Furthermore, the **exchange of data**, i.e., clinical and medical data, between partners remains a challenge due to the complex and – at times - restrictive regulations that also apply to research organisations. It is important to note that institutions operate at different levels of maturity in this area. Going forward, this may result in the need to work in variable geometries both within and outside of the Alliance.

When it comes to **human capital development**, it should be noted that human resource (HR) strategies are strongly linked to both **national frameworks** as well as **institutional autonomy** of the partner universities. Una Europa is not aiming to create a supra-institution but rather to invest in ways to facilitate more efficient and in-depth collaboration between the partner universities, built on trust and common values. While an exchange on different human resource strategies can be of added value, it is not desirable or feasible to develop a single

common HR strategy at the level of the Alliance. It is also true that there are already several European initiatives ongoing in this area, in which the Una Europa partner universities engage to various degrees. This therefore questions the concrete added value of focusing on this particular area within the Alliance at this point. Una Europa is committed to leverage ongoing initiatives to ensure that developments within the Alliance, such as systematic support structures for **early-career researchers**, takes into account relevant frameworks and guidelines at European level. There are still many barriers to the **free movement of knowledge and knowledge workers**, including linked to the variety of social security systems, tax regulations and visa administration across Member States. This is a fundamental barrier to realising the European Research Area and progress in these fields would be a tremendous step forward – both for European Universities and the higher education sector at large.

Una.Resin revealed that Una Europa can be an excellent platform for the creation of an exceptional ecosystem in the localities of the partner universities. However, building **collaboration with non-academic actors** in the surrounding ecosystems of the partner universities is a highly complex topic that requires time and dedicated resources. The creation of a true ecosystem beyond the partner universities requires long-term and trust-based human-to-human networking as well as bottom-up support and interest from the academic community, which goes beyond the timeframe and resources available in this pilot project.

In terms of joint doctoral training activities, the Alliance has been challenged by **diverging national regulations at PhD level**, which still vary considerably between countries across the European Higher Education Area (EHEA). So far, professional and academic colleagues across the Una Europa partner universities have developed creative solutions to these hurdles at regional and national levels and found ways forward on an ad-hoc basis to reconcile different approaches to admission procedures, language requirements, compulsory doctoral training elements, duration of the PhD track, examination traditions, award procedures and so on, whilst co-creating the **Joint PhD Programme on Cultural Heritage (Una-Her-Doc)**. The difference in the status of PhD students across EHEA countries and continuous funding challenges have been found to require constant attention and place a burden on both the institution and the PhD candidates themselves. More efforts are needed to tackle these challenges in a more systematic and comprehensive way. The **ED-AFFICHE project**, led by KU Leuven, selected under the European Commission's latest round of policy experimentation calls linked to the European Degree, has set out an ambitious work plan to investigate some of the most pressing challenges and develop possible solutions together with regional and national ministries as well as quality assurance and accreditation agencies across the EHEA.

2. Please describe how you tackled these challenges. Based on your project's experience, briefly outline case(s) that you consider as good practice and of interest to other universities or to policymakers.

Una Europa vzw, the Alliance's legal entity based in Brussels actively engages with the **European Commission and other relevant European stakeholders** and is a vocal advocate for a more sustainable policy and funding environment for European Universities, including their research & innovation dimension. At the same time, the partner universities are key stakeholders in **dialogues with their regional and national policymakers**. In many

regions and/or countries, higher education institutions engaged in alliances have joined forces for advocacy and the exchange of good practices. In order to tackle the uncertain external funding perspective for the Alliance's research & innovation dimension in the short- to medium-term, Una Europa has taken a two-pronged approach. On the one hand, research and innovation has been integrated – to the extent possible – into the Alliance's **Una.Futura project**, funded by the European Universities Initiative, rolled-out under Erasmus+. On the other hand, an **R&I Matrix exercise** was designed to outline potential future activities across three priority areas in research & innovation and to encourage a prioritisation exercise at the highest decision-making levels of the Alliance. This exercise not only serves to determine priority actions for the future, but also outlines levels of ambition with required resources at institutional, national and European levels to support their implementation.

A major success of Una Europa's collaboration thus far has been the development of **interdisciplinary academic hubs across six Focus Areas**, Cultural Heritage, Data Science & Artificial Intelligence, Europe and the World, Future Materials, One Health and Sustainability, driven by the active involvement of motivated academics who are creating joint strategies and actions plans for the future. Equally, the **Clusters of experts**, which bring together dedicated professional services colleagues in a wide variety of domains (Open Science, citizen science, human capital, research infrastructures, industry-academia collaboration, doctoral studies, ...) has been key in supporting both professional and institutional development. Clusters are pivotal for strengthening collaboration, providing support for the Una Europa academic community and shaping the practices and values that define European higher education. The **Una Europa Seed Funding Initiative** is another standout initiative of the Alliance. So far, a total of 44 projects have been funded, including a special edition for early-career researchers, supported by the Polish National Agency for Academic Exchange (NAWA) and secured by Jagiellonian University.

The development of the Alliance's first **R&I Strategy**, as part of WP1 of the Una.Resin project, has been a major achievement. Co-led by the University of Helsinki and Freie Universität Berlin, this process successfully balanced bottom-up involvement of the Una Europa community, to ensure that future priorities reflect the needs of researchers, and alignment with strategic developments, such as the **Una Europa 2030 Strategy**. In addition, the establishment of the **Una Europa Research Strategy Group**, which brings together Vice Rectors for Research Policy (or equivalent) as an established part of the Alliance's governance structure, is a significant development. While the involvement of researchers has not always been straightforward in the framework of the Una.Resin project, due to the intricacies of the SwafS instrument, the Alliance has successfully developed and implemented numerous new and innovative initiatives that have created clear value added for researchers across the Una Europa partner universities. This includes:

- Design of successful **matchmaking workshops** and events in various Focus Areas for Horizon Europe Pillar II calls, which have resulted in the submission of numerous joint research proposals between the Una Europa partner universities;
- Strategic positioning of Una Europa within **large-scale European projects and initiatives**, notably as part of the successful bid to set-up the newest Knowledge and Innovation Community (KIC), EIT Culture & Creativity;

- Creation of an **Una Europa Junior Fellowship scheme** under the Leuven Institute for Advanced Studies to attract young researchers from across the Una Europa partner institutions, up to tenure-track professors;
- Active engagement with research infrastructure researchers and experts in the Una.Resin Research Infrastructure and Resources strategy, the pilot actions on Cultural Heritage and OneHealth as well as the design of the blueprint for a common digital catalogue;
- Creation of **mutual learning activities and good practices** in the areas of Open Science, Team Science and Citizen Engagement in collaboration with researchers across the partner universities.

Transformation modules

Una Europa has taken the first steps to identify processes to **increase visibility, accessibility and mechanisms** for the sharing of the small and medium sized RIs hosted locally. There is a true added value to do this as an Alliance.

Matchmaking among RIs has been found to stimulate new collaborations across research & innovation, education and societal outreach. In particular, the pilot action carried out with Museums and Digital Collections revealed the willingness of a vibrant community of RIs to collaborate with the Self-Steering Committee for Cultural Heritage. For example, thanks to the involvement of RIs under the Una.Resin project, a **Virtual Museum** of Una Europa partner universities' heritage will be realised under the Una.Futura project.

In the long term, empowering RIs as actors of international collaboration can transform the institutional vision of infrastructures from being solely a support system to becoming a driving force behind research activities. This change in perception can help to improve the valorisation of RIs and can lead to the development of common solutions on openness and shareability, thus inducing the institutional change towards opening and sharing RIs across the Alliance. In addition, meaningful synergies were established between Una Europa and other projects, such as the **RiTrain Plus project** with the organisation of a joint workshop (Bologna, October 2022), which highlighted the importance of collaborating to develop training programmes targeted to current and future managers and operators of European RIs and Core Facilities. The **Open Science survey**, conducted in the framework of the Una.Resin project, has been key to providing a clear overview of the state of affairs in terms of open science and citizen engagement within the Una Europa partner universities, as well as an indication on areas where collaboration (between a selection of partners) can be mutually beneficial in the future. Thus far, a number of concrete actions have been successfully implemented:

- Provision of **regular open and engaging fora** for good practice exchange among research support staff;
- Realisation of a **monthly webinar series** to stimulate the exchange of good practice among researchers and research support staff of the Una Europa partner universities as well as the public at large;
- Development of a dedicated '**Citizen science toolkit**' which consists of filmed interviews with experts in Citizen Science across the partner universities, assessable on the Una Europa website. This format not only raises awareness about Citizen Science practices, but also showcases good practice examples and provides experience-based methodologies for the implementation of citizen science projects;

- Creation of a **MOOC on Team Science**, widely distributed across the partner universities and beyond.

When it comes to early-career researchers, the **Una Europa Doctoral Programme in Cultural Heritage** (Una-Her-Doc) and associated **PhD workshops and trainings** are flagship achievements of the Alliance. Una-Her-Doc moves beyond a simple curriculum and aims to create a place of exchange and regular interaction with the establishment of four **Una Europa Transnational Research Teams in Cultural Heritage (TRTs)**, which not only gathers professors and researchers, but also doctoral candidates of Una Europa universities. This European doctoral title provides a unique exposure to the European Cultural Heritage ecosystem and includes the supervision of the doctoral candidate by professors from two Una Europa partner universities featuring mobilities to several Una Europa partners. The programme is administered by joint structures for admission, selection, supervision and assessment. A **Handbook for Doctoral Studies within Una Europa** is being developed by Una Europa's Doctoral Training Cluster, which will be made available for further use by other relevant groups within the Alliance. Furthermore, a **common definition for early-career researchers** has been established at the level of the Alliance, successfully bridging differences across eleven institutions and countries.

3. Please describe the tangible progress that individual partners as well as the Alliance as a whole have made in terms of introducing changes in their entities as a result of this project.

First and foremost, it is important to note that Una Europa – and European Universities alliances – are still in the **early stages of their journey** of transforming into a University of the Future. Sustainable and sustained transformation at institutional level requires significant investments and time beyond the scale of a 3-year pilot project. The pilot phase of European Universities alliances has been primarily dedicated to the development of joint strategies and action plans. Moving into the consolidation phase, the focus is shifting to their implementation. It is equally important to highlight that change and transformation are not the only objectives of the European Universities Initiative. Una Europa also provides a unique space for the **strengthening of existing initiatives** by joining forces and encouraging the **strategic alignment** of existing policies and processes in the framework of the Alliance. Una Europa's involvement in strategic initiatives at European level, such as the EIT Culture and Creativity, as well as in key projects, such as the ARCHE project, RM Roadmap and others, further serves as a clear showcase of the combined strength of the Una Europa Alliance.

Una Europa has succeeded in the development of long-term common strategies at the level of the Alliance. The **Una Europa 2030 Strategy** sets out the strategic priorities for the Alliance in the decade to come across education, research & innovation and societal outreach. This strategy was developed in a bottom-up manner together with the Una Europa community and ensures close alignment with institutional policies of all the partner universities. Una Europa vzw is the guardian of this strategy and provides bi-annual reporting on progress made to the **Una Europa General Assembly**, consisting of the Rectors of the partner universities. As mentioned, Una.Resin has also facilitated the development of the Alliance's first common **Research & Innovation Strategy**, which sets out strategic priorities for the years ahead. At the same time, solid governance structures have been established, which ensures

representation and active engagement of a broad cross-section of senior leadership. This includes the **Una Europa Board of Directors**, consisting of Vice Rectors for International Policy (or equivalent), and the **Research Strategy Group**, bringing together Vice Rectors for Research Policy (or equivalent). Support of senior leadership is considered crucial for the long-term sustainability of the Alliance.

Institutional transformation

Since the Alliance's establishment in early 2019, Una Europa has become an increasingly **central component in the strategic plans** of many partner universities. This has ensured that Una Europa is weaved into the fabric of the partner universities and well-integrated into institutional strategies going forward. The Alliance has furthermore been a catalyst to strengthen the **nexus between education and research & innovation** through internationalisation. This has resulted in closer collaboration between the respective services at various partner universities, cross-cutting meetings as well as new joint initiatives. Una.Resin has been integral to ensuring that research & innovation is at the forefront of Alliance activities, which has directly led to **increased interest, participation and commitment** of research departments and offices of the partner universities throughout the pilot phase. Participation in Una Europa is generally perceived as a **pull for innovation at institutional level** through the establishment of mutual learning activities, the creation of fora for open exchange and knowledge-sharing as well as joint forces to push the boundaries of transnational collaboration together.

The **Una Europa Focus Areas** serve as unique fora for the creation of inter-, trans- and multi-disciplinary collaboration and understanding. They have encouraged institutional transformation at a number of partner universities, such as the establishment of the Leuven Institute for One Health, which was launched at the end of 2023 as a response to Una Europa's Focus Area on One Health. Jagiellonian University's 'Initiative of Excellence - Research University' project (2020 – 2026) has designed actions along select Priority Research Areas (PRA), which are inspired by and aligned with the Alliances Focus Areas. At the same time, dedicated match-making processes in the Focus Areas for competitive proposals under Horizon Europe Pillar II have brought together academics across institutional and disciplinary boundaries. Such processes have been found to be particularly effective in the Alliance context as they form part of sustainable collaboration, are part of a broader joint long-term strategy and benefit from dedicated institutional support.

Various Una Europa partner universities have made **strategic use of regional and national co-funding** to organise initiatives to the benefit of the whole Una Europa community, i.e. KU Leuven uses funding to stimulate bottom-up interaction with Una Europa partners with the Una Europa Research Acceleration Fund and Una Europa junior fellowship programme under the Leuven Institute for Advanced Studies, while Paris1 uses national funding to support the Self-Steering Committee on Cultural Heritage and the implementation of the Una-Her-Doc programme to the benefit of all partners. Jagiellonian University has dedicated funding from the Polish Ministry **Science and Higher Education, for example, to support actions of Una Europa's Future University Lab (FUL).**

The work within Una.Resin has further led to an increased awareness and understanding of the strategic importance of **top-quality and shared research infrastructures** for the

academic community, such as featured in the University of Bologna Strategy Plan 2022-2027. Una Europa's **Research Infrastructure Cluster** was instrumental in the development of a 'Shared Research Facilities' Hub for the University of Edinburgh's College of Medicine and Veterinary Medicine, which acts as a one-stop shop for researchers to explore core facilities, shared equipment, and to share expertise. In addition, **in-depth knowledge of best practices**, provided by the institutions where common catalogues of shared research infrastructures and equipment already exists, such as the University of Helsinki, provided concrete support for other partner universities in shaping objectives related to their developments. This exchange also pushed the partner universities to look beyond their own institutional borders and to think creatively about common solutions and strategies to be able to guarantee the maximum level of interoperability of each institution's catalogue in the long run. Early awareness about possible pitfalls as well as the availability of a clear roadmap of actions, based on experiences of the more advanced universities, are highly valuable for those partner universities that are in the development process.

The establishment of the **Una Europa Open Science Cluster** was crucial to the work of similar groups at institutional level, such as the Una Europa Open Science Working Group at Paris1. The members of this group benefitted from the exchange with Una Europa partners in the Open Science Cluster and use the experience gained to clarify the needs of the university in terms of human resources, strategy and OS policy. At the same time, the activities of the Open Science Cluster led to in-depth benchmarking of services and processes at the partner universities. For example, the University of Bologna developed processes, services and policies based on the example of partners that are more advanced in the field of OS. This process of institutional enhancement is an outcome that goes beyond the mere exchange of knowledge and best practices. The collaboration on OS within Una.Resin significantly accelerated the development of internal competencies and processes in a number of Una Europa partner universities, which would not have taken place without the Una.Resin project.

Policy Recommendations

- 1. The inclusive cooperation approach of the Alliances was shown to accelerate institutional change also in less R&I-intensive universities, clearly indicating it has a positive impact on capacity building in R&I, next to education. It is however unclear up to now if the approach also positively affects excellent research. Therefore, please provide arguments and concrete examples how your Alliance provides added value as compared to 'traditional' cross-border cooperation between researchers, such as through competitive collaborative research projects by the Framework Programme.**

Una Europa is a leading Alliance of **strong research-intensive universities** from all corners of Europe. The partner universities have an **impressive track record in EU R&I programmes**, securing a total financial contribution of €1.5 billion from the H2020 programme (2014–2020) and hosting 485 prestigious European Research Council (ERC) grants in the same period. The Alliance is uniquely positioned to address the most pressing scientific, global and societal challenges of today and tomorrow together. Uniting eleven partners from eleven different countries with different cultural, linguistic and social backgrounds which brings a depth of perspective, range of experiences and a variety of approaches that makes the partnership stronger.

European Universities are taking a radically new approach to transnational collaboration, which goes beyond previously tested models and traditional types of collaboration. The **scale of collaboration** within Una Europa and the **embeddedness** of the Alliance into the fabric of the partner institutions are truly unique. Una Europa has set out to develop a common ecosystem for research and innovation, with **trust, common values and long-term commitment** at the core. The objective is to provide systematic opportunities to collaboration, driven by a common overarching strategic direction. The development of joint long-term strategies, such as the **Una Europa 2030 Strategy** and the **Una Europa Research & Innovation Strategy**, which will be implemented in the Alliance in the decade ahead, are integral in this regard and lay the groundwork for building excellence in research in the future. Together, the partners provide the right **framework conditions and governance structures** for long-term collaboration of the **whole university community of academics, professionals and students**, which go beyond what is feasible within single collaborative research projects under Horizon Europe.

Since the Alliance's inception in 2019, Una Europa has already taken decisive steps to drive forward excellent inter- multi- and transdisciplinary research and innovation of high impact as well as high-quality joint education across geographical, institutional and disciplinary boundaries. To this end, Una Europa has selected **six Focus Areas** - Cultural Heritage, Data Science & Artificial Intelligence, Europe and the World, Future Materials, One Health, and Sustainability. In under five years, these Focus Areas have transformed into fora where the most excellent researchers from excellent institutions have initiated collaboration and pioneered joint initiatives, courses and programmes as part of joint education and research & innovation agendas that push the boundaries of transnational collaboration. Going forward, these academic Self-Steering Committees will be supported to develop into international hubs for education, research and innovation and societal outreach. Continued investment is expected to create strong long-term partnerships between the best researchers across Europe and lead to brave new findings in research, innovation and education.

Furthermore, excellence has been raised in Una Europa's **Clusters of Professionals** via good practice sharing in a trust-based environment across a variety of areas, such as Research Infrastructures and Resources, Open Science, Team Science and Citizen Science. Furthermore, this has led to strengthened **transversal skills development** of professional staff, i.e., through job shadowing formats ('Una Europa Live My Life'), international staff weeks as well as **benchmarking visits** at the partner institutions. Una Europa is unique in reaching the whole professional staff community of the partner universities and providing opportunities for international exposure and intercultural learning to staff, who otherwise would have no such opportunities. Furthermore, the partner universities have joined forces to share **interdisciplinary trainings for early-career and established researchers** and found low-threshold opening up of training opportunities and events, i.e., Doctoral Education Base Camp, RRI-self learning materials, sustainability courses and the Next Generation Genomics symposium. This approach takes optimal advantage of complementary expertise and strengths that together form the basis of Una Europa's exceptional offering.

The Una.Resin project has played a crucial role in shaping Una Europa's ambitions in the area of research & innovation, evident in the previous sections. The project was the **driver of many**

great successes for the Alliance, such as the launch of Una Europa's Research & Innovation Strategy, which is built around three core objectives identified by Una.Resin. Furthermore, the Una.Resin project has provided the space for **connecting various communities** of the partner universities. Notably, this includes Horizon Europe match-making workshops for researchers in all Una Europa Focus Areas as well as match-making opportunities among RIs in the field of Cultural Heritage (Museums and Digital Collections) and One Health (Genomics). Such initiatives have shown great promise and piqued the interest of the Una Europa academic community already in this first incubator period. It is clear that continued funding for **capacity building, also for alliances of research-intensive universities** is vital in the mission to create **future-looking models** for both higher education and research. This is not just crucial for European Universities themselves, but to ensure that alliances are in a position to continue good practices with other stakeholders across the European Research Area. European Universities should not be seen as an end in themselves but rather as tools to inspire transformation and stimulate innovation more broadly.

Funding instruments and tools provided to European Universities at European level thus far, via the European Universities Initiative in Erasmus+ and the SwafS instrument in Horizon2020, have not lent themselves to boosting excellence in the alliance context per se. These instruments at European level have had a clear focus on the capacity-building dimension of alliances and are geared towards supporting all types of higher education institutions in different parts of the European Research Area. Moving forward, an increasingly strong focus on driving the **excellence dimension and global competitiveness** of Europe's strongest higher education institutions on the world stage, in line with the initial concept behind the European Universities Initiative, is needed.

In this respect, it is important to reiterate that research excellence within European Universities is not a quick win, but requires **time, dedication and appropriate human and financial resources**. While the pilot phase has been key to developing first joint strategies and piloting first activities, more time and additional investment are crucial to support the next phase of building a truly joint ecosystem for research & innovation with research excellence at the core. Moving from the pilot to the consolidation phase, focus will shift from strategy building to implementation at the level of the Alliance. Una Europa has a clear and decisive plan in this regard, shaped by a common **Vision for Research and Innovation** and an accompanying action plan, which outlines priority actions for the future and required investments. At the same time, recent enlargements of alliances, which were incentivised as part of the European Universities Initiative roll-out phase, underline the need for further funding support in the area of research & innovation that also reaches new partners.

Furthermore, the **outward looking dimension** of European Universities remains insufficiently supported. The Una Europa partner universities are **global actors** each with a long history of international collaboration – as an Alliance, there is the potential to have ever more global reach and impact. Una Europa believes in addressing global challenges from diverse perspectives and establishing **value-adding multi-lateral partnerships** with like-minded partners in different parts of the world. Una Europa has made great progress in this regard in relation to collaboration with Africa, for instance with the launch of a first strategic project focusing on virtual mobility, UnaVEx, and a dedicated Seed Funding Initiative to initiate first collaborations across the **Una Europa – Africa Partnership**. Going forward, the European

Commission must focus more on supporting the **global dimension of alliances** to ensure that they are not in-ward looking but develop into **open global flagships for Europe**.

Ultimately, a **holistic funding instrument** is called for which provides a long-term funding perspective to European Universities alliances across all their missions: education, research and innovation and service to society. Currently, there is no other cross-border initiative that garners as much enthusiasm and political support at regional and national levels as the European Universities initiative. This must be leveraged in the future, in order to ensure true **co-ownership of the initiative at regional, national and European levels** both in terms of policy and funding. More details on this can be found in the next section of this report.

2. The Alliances have repeatedly asked the EU and Member States (MS) to design a holistic support system, covering all their missions at once and reducing administrative burden to a minimum. Please explain your views and suggestions on how this should be realised in practice on the medium and long-term.

As research-intensive universities, the Una Europa partner universities naturally integrate education, research, innovation and societal outreach on a daily basis. Una Europa reiterates the call for the development of a **dedicated funding instrument** for strategic collaborations of universities that allows for co-investment of regional, national, and European sources and provides a long-term funding perspective across education, research, and innovation. Such a funding instrument should:

- be **competitive in nature** and always be geared towards the principles of **quality, excellence, and impact**, in line with the core principles of the European research and innovation programmes;
- represent an **additional investment** and not take away from existing research and innovation priorities and associated funding;
- **recognise and support the diversity of higher education collaborations** in Europe to preserve individual research strengths, maintain and boost excellence, and deliver unique and innovative concepts for the continent and the world;
- pay increased attention to driving the **visibility and global competitiveness of Europe's strongest higher education institutions** on the world stage;
- **be open to the world**, encouraging participation and co-investment from like-minded institutions in different parts of the globe.

When it comes to **co-investment of regional and/ or national funding sources**, it is important to highlight that some level of coordination will be required even in the short-term, i.e., in terms of timings, budgets and scope to ensure equal support across Member States and participating countries and create a genuine lever for collaboration. The European Universities Initiative has created huge enthusiasm at regional and national levels, which must be translated into concrete co-ownership in the future. In this respect, the European Commission must play a coordinating role in encouraging increased alignment of both policies and funding streams not just across EU Member States but with the involvement of important neighbouring countries, such as Switzerland and the United Kingdom.

When it comes to the implementation of true synergies between education and research, we propose a strong focus on **strategic support for early-career researchers**, which are naturally at the nexus of education and research and innovation. This is where European

University alliances can create clear added value in terms of **transnational education and research opportunities** offered by and for early career researchers. Una Europa has seen great successes with the establishment of the Transnational Research Teams in Cultural Heritage (TRTs), which embed PhD candidates directly into Europe's Cultural Heritage ecosystem. Based on this experience, additional **types of grant schemes** for transversal skills development around leadership, interdisciplinarity and international collaboration for early-career researchers, in complement to existing MSCA and ERC models, are needed. At the same time, further funding for **international short-term mobilities** of early-career researchers, such as interdisciplinary summer / winter schools, that are flexible in nature, would go a long way in tackling funding challenges currently placing a burden on both the institutions and the PhD candidates themselves.

European Universities alliances should further receive more recognition and support as ideal vehicles to implement international and interdisciplinary research. The transnational research ecosystem created by Una Europa in the form of **International Hubs for Research, Education and Knowledge Transfer** has huge potential to advance our understanding of the world and to develop new solutions to increasing global challenges, such as on climate change, one health and sustainable development. Such approaches are key for enhancing Europe's competitiveness in the world.

Furthermore, investment in the **long-term sustainability of actions** is key, as this will ultimately determine the long-term sustainability of the alliances themselves. In the ever-continuing quest for new and innovative actions, there must also be sufficient consideration for the long-term sustainability of existing actions. Alliances need to be afforded the appropriate time and funding to focus on deepening the processes and practices developed thus far and to intensify the engagement of their academic community, in order to strengthen the European research and innovation landscape in a bottom-up manner.

National Examples

There are various examples of funding programmes in education and research & innovation in different EU Member States that may inspire the development of a holistic funding instrument for transnational collaboration of universities. While it is important to recognise that they are often linked to specific national and regional contexts, different elements may be adapted and inspire the scope and shape of a Europe-wide funding instrument.

- The **German Excellence Initiative** includes various elements that may inspire the development of a European instrument to support transnational collaboration of universities. The Excellence Strategy is a funding programme of the German Federal Government and the 'Länder' to strengthen cutting-edge research at universities across two main funding lines: Clusters of Excellence and Universities of Excellence.
 - The **Clusters of Excellence** funding line provides project-based funding in internationally competitive fields of research at individual universities or university alliances. The Clusters of Excellence involve researchers from various disciplines and institutions working in a collaborative project. The funding provides them with the opportunity of focusing intensively on their research objective, training early-career researchers and attracting the best global talent. Clusters of Excellence receive long-term support with an initial funding period of seven years, which may be extended for another seven years.

- Support and training of early-career researchers**, who at the nexus of education and research at universities, are natural elements of holistic funding.
- The **Universities of Excellence** funding line sets out to strengthen universities or university alliances as institutions and to expand their leading international position in research on the basis of successful Clusters of Excellence. Universities must therefore already have at least two Clusters of Excellence – and in the case of university alliances at least three Clusters of Excellence – in order to be eligible to apply for the status of University of Excellence. Universities of Excellence receive permanent funding but must submit to a review of the prerequisites for funding every seven years. This means that Universities of Excellence must regularly participate in the competition for the funding of the necessary number of Clusters of Excellence by submitting regular new applications.
 - Freie Universität Berlin (FUB) has joined forces with Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Technische Universität Berlin, and Charité – Universitätsmedizin Berlin in the creation of the Berlin University Alliance (BUA), unique in its concept. The overarching objective is to strengthen Berlin's position as one of Europe's leading hubs of knowledge and research and create added value for science and scientists throughout Berlin. Many strategic activities are being realised within the framework of the BUA, such as a **Postdoc Academy** to create a supportive environment for early-career researchers, and **Berlin Universities Publishing** to promote the uptake of Open Access.
 - In 2021, the **French National Agency for Research** issued a call entitled “ExcellencES in all its forms” (“Excellence sous toutes ses formes”) with the overarching aim of supporting higher education and research institutions with ambitious transformation projects at the scale of their respective campuses in implementing their unique strategies, developed based on their local dynamics and specific needs. The project of Paris 1 “Sorbo’Rising” was successful in this call and was allocated EUR 18.4 million to initiate a new dynamic and implement innovative projects. Its overall objective is to enhance the attractiveness of Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) while demonstrating that they are essential to addressing the major challenges of our world. This transformative project is organised into four areas of intervention: research, education, capacity building, and engagement with society. Spanning over 8 years, Sorbo’Rising revolves around three key challenges:
 - Educating students about the 21st-century issues, particularly ongoing political, social, environmental, and digital transformations;
 - Strengthening transdisciplinarity and disseminating research results in SHS beyond the academic sphere;
 - Supporting the institution's staff in these transformations.
 - In Finland, the **Research Council of Finland** grants competitive funding to Finnish universities to support them in strengthening their research profiles. The aim of the funding is to support and speed up the strategic profiling of Finnish universities in order to improve the quality of research. However, it is important to note that the funding has been seen to create a holistic effect on universities, due to the possibility of using funding to create more tenure-track positions and to incentivise more cross-unit collaborations, for example bringing together the education and research and innovation departments, in institutions.

- In Ireland, the **'Science Foundation Ireland Research Centres'** link scientists and engineers in partnerships across academia and industry to address crucial research questions. These are research-focused and of scale with researchers recruited from doctoral and postdoctoral researcher across the Irish universities that participate. They are a collaborative effort of Irish universities which are seen as a medium- to long-term endeavour of 5-10 years and beyond. Each centre has a platform budget to support joint infrastructure and technologies required and an operations budget to support management activities, public engagement etc. This initiative has created an environment where multi-institutional and multidisciplinary collaborations are now the norm, and where academia engages in deeply collaborative research partnerships with national and multinational industries to deliver internationally lead research, cutting edge technologies and advancements.
- In **Spain**, the Ministry of Science, Universities and Innovation established, through different calls, the creation of **Campus of Excellence at the Universities** national level, to improve infrastructure, and attract talent internationally, providing specific funds for this: strengthening synergy between institutions. This program has consolidated these campuses of excellence and strengthened common programs at an academic and research level. Moreover, on this basis, successful **Clusters of Excellence** have been established. This has established campuses of excellence at the national level between universities of the same autonomous community, or between universities of different autonomous communities.

In addition, numerous partner universities have received national and regional co-funding, which has been strategically leveraged to support Una Europa priorities during the Alliance's pilot phase. As referenced prior in this document, Una Europa advocates for **strategic alignment of such national and regional co-funding**, in terms of thematic scope and timelines, to create a true **lever for collaboration**.

- In France, the **Ministry of Higher Education** has provided targeted funding to Université Paris 1 Panthéon-Sorbonne to set up a three-year experimental interdisciplinary research laboratory in Europe, designed to strengthen links between the Una Europa partner universities. The laboratory, which was inaugurated in November 2023, is titled '3E: Europe, Espace, Environnement'. Its core aim is to produce innovative, open and European projects bringing together education, research and innovation.
- In addition, the **French Ministry of Higher Education and the French National Agency for Research** provided equal levels of financial support to French universities that are part of European Universities alliances. At Paris 1, this funding has allowed the recruitment of administrative staff dedicated to supporting both education and research activities linked to Una Europa, the launch of four annual internal calls for research projects on the Una Europa Focus Areas, support for the mobility of doctoral researchers, as well as administrative and academic staff across various departments and faculties of the university.
- In Flanders, KU Leuven has received funding from the Flemish Government to stimulate bottom-up interaction with the Una Europa partners universities. Actions funded so far concern both the **Una Europa Research Acceleration Fund** and Una Europa junior fellowship programme under the **Leuven Institute for Advanced Studies (LIAS)**. LIAS gathers scientific insights on major societal challenges, based

on international and interdisciplinary discussion between leading researchers. In subsequent calls, the junior fellows programme specifically targeted young researchers (Ph.D. students, postdocs or junior faculty members) from Una Europa institutions on different timely themes, such as the “Societal Aspects of Climate Change” and “New Living arrangements for the boomer generation”.

- In 2019, Jagiellonian University (JU) was selected by the **Polish Ministry of Science and Higher Education** to participate in the "Initiative of Excellence - Research University" (2022-2026). The initiative, which at JU has taken the acronym ID.UJ, enables the university to strengthen areas such as international partnerships, innovative research, research-led education, citizen science and open science, as well as knowledge and technology transfer. ID.UJ is organised around the '4 I principle': internationalisation, interdisciplinarity, innovativeness and integrity, in alignment with Una Europa’s strategic goals. The actions of ID.UJ are implemented at the level of Priority Research Areas (PRA), which has been inspired by and designed in synergy with the Una Europa Focus Areas. Major activities of ID.UJ are developed within Flagship Projects (FPs) which are aimed to enrich the research ecosystem of Jagiellonian University significantly, by creating innovative forms of scientific activity, combining research with education and cooperation with the socio-economic environment. These include:
 - the **Centre for Advanced Sustainability Studies (CASS)**, which acts as a sustainability accelerator at the university;
 - the **Critical Heritage Studies Hub (CHSH)**, an interdisciplinary initiative focusing on heritage research. It aims to be a platform for cooperation among the academic community, educational institutions, cultural institutions, non-governmental organisations, government entities, and the business community;
 - the **Future University Lab (FUL)**, Una Europa’s think tank which aims to serve as a reference point for the future development of both the European Higher Education and Research Area.

3. Please illustrate with concrete examples how your Alliance will integrate the work on the transformation modules developed under this H2020-SwafS support with the Erasmus+ support to the Alliance project. Please provide the current state-of-affairs and your plans to integrate all your missions.

Una Europa has taken the strategic decision to take a holistic approach to the development and implementation of the **Una.Futura project**, funded by the Erasmus+ programme’s European Universities initiative. The Una.Futura project features **six transversal themes** as guiding principles for our collaboration, including one theme dedicated to ‘research and innovation’, championed by the University of Edinburgh, Coordinator of the Una.Resin Project, and Universidad Complutense Madrid. Defined as Deliverable 1.1. under WP1 of the project, each transversal theme has delivered a vision and action plan. While deeply anchored in Una Europa’s 2030 Strategy, these visions and actions plans are also building on results, lessons learned and experiences gathered within other strategic Una Europa projects, such as 1 Europe (2019 – 2022) and Una.Resin (2021 – 2024).

The project also includes a dedicated **Work Package: Una Europa for Researchers (WP4)**, led by Universiteit Leiden and supported by the University of Edinburgh, the Coordinating Institution of the Una.Resin project. The aim of this work package is to build in a **long-term perspective and a solid basis for academic collaboration** in Una Europa with a **strong link to joint education and research**. The work towards this aim will involve different processes at different levels (and evolving at different speeds) which will need to be aligned and integrated within the Alliance. These processes are three-fold: i) the successful implementation of the Una.Resin project aimed at building an Una Europa Research ecosystem; ii) the engagement of the broader community via the Una Europa Research Strategy Group, representing Vice Rectors for Research from all partner universities; and iii) the further development of our Self Steering Committees into interdisciplinary hubs for education, research and knowledge transfer in the framework of this project. This alignment will constitute the overarching goal of this work package. Careful planning and the organisation of continuous feedback loops between the Una.Resin project, the Work Package lead, the management of this project, the Research Coordination Cluster and the Research Strategy Group are pivotal to the long-term success of this work package. Concretely, this Work Package foresees an **Una.Resin benchmarking exercise**, which will feed into a road map to the further development of Una.Resin initiatives. In addition, this Work Package will support the Una Europa Self Steering Committees to evolve into hubs for interdisciplinary challenge-based research, education and knowledge transfer, and develop a feasibility study and roadmap for a **possible Joint Institute for Advanced Studies** across Una Europa partner universities. Furthermore, it will comprise the development of joint innovative educational formats at doctoral level, including a **joint Doctoral Interdisciplinary Methods Training (DIMT) Curriculum and Framework**, joint **Summer and Winter Schools** as well as further **joint doctoral programmes**, inspired by the Una Europa Joint Doctoral Programme in Cultural Heritage. Una Europa is further elaborating its internal **quality assurance process for joint education**, including joint doctoral education, building on the blueprint for an internal quality assurance system for joint programmes developed in preparation for the Una Europa Joint Bachelor of Arts in European Studies. Quality assurance of joint doctoral training will be addressed in 2024. In addition, Una Futura's **WP10 on 'Building the Backbone'** focuses on identifying and addressing administrative and legal barriers at institutional, national and European level. This includes a focus on removing barriers for free movement of knowledge workers. Activities will be kicked off in autumn 2023.

In addition, Una Europa decided to design an **R&I Matrix exercise** in the final year of the Una.Resin Project in order to ensure that the project's key results are taken forward. The R&I Matrix presented potential future activities in research & innovation for Una Europa with the aim of encouraging a prioritisation exercise at the highest decision-making levels of the Alliance. The proposed activities mirrored the ambitions expressed in the **Una Europa R&I Vision**, which distils and frames the more comprehensive Una Europa Research & Innovation Strategy developed under the Una.Resin project in a future-looking way. They are anchored in three strategic overarching objectives: Objective 1: Support for the development of Una Europa's international hubs for research, education and knowledge transfer; Objective 2: Providing an international framework for training targeted at Una Europa early career researchers and Objective 3: Developing a stronger and more integrated Una Europa Research infrastructure Ecosystem.

A dedicated online survey was designed to allow partner universities to make strategic choices in an open and transparent manner. This process took place between June and September 2023. The results of the survey were subsequently processed and interpreted centrally by Una Europa vzw, together with select colleagues from the Una.Resin project who helped conceive and design the exercise. These results were then presented to the Una Europa Research Strategy Group at a virtual meeting in October 2023. Subsequently, a physical meeting of the Una Europa Research Strategy Group and Board of Directors in November 2023 was utilised for a discussion in relation to levels of ambition and level of resourcing required to ensure the implementation of chosen activities. A dedicated R&I Action Plan is expected to be signed off in June 2024.